

Direct Photon Production in Au+Au Collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV

A Dissertation Presented

by

Wenqing Fan

to

The Graduate School

in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

for the Degree of

Doctor of Philosophy

in

Physics

Stony Brook University

December 2020

Stony Brook University

The Graduate School

Wenqing Fan

We, the dissertation committee for the above candidate for the Doctor of Philosophy degree, hereby recommend acceptance of this dissertation.

Axel Drees – Dissertation Advisor
Professor, Department of Physics and Astronomy

Dmitri Kharzeev – Chairperson of Defense
Professor, Department of Physics and Astronomy

Xu Du
Professor, Department of Physics and Astronomy

Alexander Bazilevsky
Physicist
Brookhaven National Lab

This dissertation is accepted by the Graduate School.

Eric Wertheimer
Dean of the Graduate School

Abstract of the Dissertation

**Direct Photon Production in Au+Au
Collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV**

by

Wenqing Fan

Doctor of Philosophy

in

Physics

Stony Brook University

2020

A fundamental feature of QCD is color-confinement, that the color-carrying objects – quarks and gluons – are ordinarily confined in color neutral states – hadrons. However, it is predicted that under extremely high temperature and/or density, hadronic matter will transit into a color deconfined state called the Quark Gluon Plasma (QGP). Within the laboratory set-up, ultrarelativistic heavy-ion collisions are used to create QGP. Direct photons are useful probes to study the properties of QGP and the dynamic evolution of the collision system as they do not interact with the medium strongly. Low transverse momentum (p_T) direct photons are believed to originate primarily from thermal radiation; however, calculations of thermal photon emission fall short in describing the measured direct photon yield and the anisotropy at the same time. The question is tied to the photon production mechanism in heavy ion collisions, whether the production rates of the known photon-emitting sources need to be modified or there are some other sources need to be included in the current theoretical picture. To provide more

insight into this question, the high statistics dataset of Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}}=200$ GeV collected by the PHENIX experiment at the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) in 2014 is studied. A new algorithm is developed to reconstruct and identify photons, which convert into electron-positron pairs in certain detector materials, to ensure good purity and momentum resolution. After accounting for the detector effects and photons from hadronic decay, the p_T spectrum of direct photon is obtained from 0.8 GeV/c to 10 GeV/c with unprecedented precision. An excess of direct photons above the N_{coll} scaled yield measured in p+p collisions is observed from 0.8 GeV/c up to ~ 5 GeV/c. The excess yield cannot be well described by an exponential distribution with one single inverse slope (T_{eff}) across the whole p_T range. Instead, we found the extracted T_{eff} increase towards higher p_T . Therefore two exponential fits are performed separately for the low p_T range, $p_T < 2$ GeV/c, and intermediate p_T range, $2 < p_T < 4$ GeV/c. While a weak increase of T_{eff} is observed towards larger collision system in the low p_T range, no significant system size dependence is observed for T_{eff} in the intermediate p_T range. Besides the p_T dependence, we also studied the direct photon production as a function of collision system size. A power law scaling behavior is observed which can be formulated as $dN_{\gamma}/dy = A \times (dN_{ch}/d\eta)^{\alpha}$ with $\alpha \sim 1.1$ for direct photons integrated within $1 < p_T < 5$ GeV/c. Using finer p_T integration windows, no strong p_T dependence is observed for the scaling power α , which is in tension with the current hydrodynamic model prediction.

To my family.

Contents

Acknowledgements	xi
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Quarks, Gluons and Quantum ChromoDynamics	1
1.2 Quark Gluon Plasma and Relativistic Heavy Ion Collisions . .	3
1.2.1 Deconfinement and the Phase Diagram	4
1.2.2 Relativistic Heavy Ion Collisions	4
1.2.2.1 Bjorken Energy Density	4
1.2.2.2 Space Time Evolution	7
1.3 Direct Photon Production	7
1.3.1 Prompt Photons and the p+p “Baseline”	9
1.3.1.1 Photons from Hard Scattering Processes	10
1.3.1.2 High p_T Direct Photon Production in p+p Col-	
lisions	11
1.3.1.3 Prompt Photons in A+A collisions	14
1.3.2 Thermal Radiation	15
1.4 Direct photon measurement	16
1.4.1 Direct Photon Yield	17
1.4.2 Direct Photon Flow	17
1.4.3 Theoretical Models	19
1.4.3.1 Direct Photon Puzzle	22
1.4.4 Direct Photon Production as a Function of System Size	23
1.5 Scope of this Thesis	23
2 Experimental Overview	25
2.1 The Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider	25
2.1.1 Accelerator Complex	25
2.1.2 Bunch Crossing and Luminosity	26
2.1.3 The RHIC Experiments	29
2.2 The PHENIX Experiment	30
2.2.1 The PHENIX Coordinate System	30

2.2.2	Global Detectors	33
2.2.2.1	Beam Beam Counter	34
2.2.2.2	Zero Degree Calorimeter	36
2.2.2.3	Minimum Bias Trigger	37
2.2.2.4	Centrality Definition and Determination	38
2.2.3	Charged Particle Tracking System	39
2.2.3.1	Central Arm Magnet	39
2.2.3.2	Drift Chambers	41
2.2.3.3	Pad Chambers	42
2.2.3.4	Track Reconstruction	46
2.2.3.5	Momentum Determination and the Track Model	49
2.2.4	Calorimetry	51
2.2.4.1	Electromagnetic Calorimeter	51
2.2.4.2	Lead-Scintillator Calorimeter	52
2.2.4.3	Lead-Glass Calorimeter	53
2.2.4.4	Energy and Position Resolution from the Test Beam	54
2.2.4.5	Electromagnetic Shower Profile in PbSc	56
2.2.4.6	Shower Reconstruction / Clustering Algorithm	60
2.2.4.7	Photon Identification	63
2.2.5	Particle / Electron Identification	66
2.2.5.1	Energy over momentum ratio of charged particles	66
2.2.5.2	Track-EMCal Matching Displacement	68
2.2.5.3	Ring Imaging Cherenkov Detector	68
2.2.6	Detector Simulation	73
2.2.6.1	PHENIX Integrated Simulation Application	74
2.2.6.2	Simulation Framework	75
3	Methodology	76
3.1	External Conversion Photon Method	76
3.1.1	Off-vertex Tracks with Standard PHENIX Track Recon- struction	77
3.1.1.1	Track Properties: Degrees of Freedom	77
3.1.1.2	Mis-reconstruction of the External Conversions	78
3.1.1.3	Conversions at the VTX detector	81
3.2	New Conversion Reconstruction Algorithm	81
3.2.1	Single track trajectory	81
3.2.1.1	Lorentz Force and Equation of Motion	82
3.2.1.2	Initial and Final Conditions	83
3.2.2	Proof of Principle using Mathematica	85
3.2.2.1	Look-up table for $\{\alpha, p_T, r_{conv}, \Delta\phi_{conv}\}$	85

3.2.2.2	A Pair of Tracks and the Conversion Point . . .	87
3.2.2.3	z direction	91
3.2.2.4	Resolution of Reconstructed Conversion Points	91
3.2.3	Implementation in the PHENIX Reconstruction Frame- work	93
3.2.3.1	3D Lookup Table for $\{r_{conv}, \theta_{conv}, p, \alpha, \Delta\phi_{conv}, \Delta z_{DC}\}$	94
3.2.3.2	Local fit of $\Delta\phi_{conv}, \theta_{conv}, p$ as a function of $(\alpha, \Delta z_{DC}, r_{conv})$	94
3.2.3.3	Test Result with PISA	95
3.2.4	Conversion Selection Cuts	96
3.2.4.1	Pair Cut Candidates	97
3.2.4.2	Determining Cut Values	98
3.3	Direct Photon Signal R_γ	103
3.3.1	Double Ratio Tagging Method	103
3.3.2	Proof of Principle with Pseudo-data	105
3.3.2.1	Raw Yield N_γ^{incl}	106
3.3.2.2	Raw Yield N_γ^{tag}	112
3.3.2.3	Conditional Acceptance and Efficiency $\langle\epsilon_\gamma f\rangle$.	119
3.3.2.4	R_γ of Pseudo-data	119
4	Data Analysis	124
4.1	Data Sample and Trigger Condition	124
4.2	Quality Assurance	127
4.2.1	Global variables	127
4.2.2	Tracking and Electron Identification	129
4.2.2.1	DC Deadmap	129
4.2.2.2	DC Alignment	130
4.2.2.3	Momentum Scale Recalibration	130
4.2.3	EMCal	134
4.2.3.1	Dead map	134
4.2.3.2	EMCal Alignment	134
4.2.3.3	Sector by Sector Energy Recalibration	136
4.3	Event Sample	140
4.4	Inclusive Photon Sample	140
4.4.1	Electron (Positron) Track Selection	140
4.4.1.1	Single Track Cuts	141
4.4.1.2	RICH Electron ID Cuts	141
4.4.1.3	EMCal electron ID cuts	142
4.4.2	Pair Selection	145
4.4.3	N_γ^{incl} extraction	148
4.5	Tagged π^0 Sample	148

4.5.1	EMCal Photon Selection	148
4.5.2	N_γ^{tag} Extraction	150
4.6	Conditional Acceptance and Efficiency $\langle\epsilon_\gamma f\rangle$	155
4.6.1	EMCal energy response	155
4.6.2	Simulation/Embedding setup	156
4.6.3	Simulation and Real Data Crosscheck	164
4.6.3.1	Electron (Positron) Tracks	164
4.6.3.2	Photon Clusters	164
4.6.4	N_γ^{incl} Extraction	164
4.6.4.1	m_{ee} Comparison	168
4.6.5	N_γ^{tag} Extraction	169
4.6.5.1	$m_{ee\gamma}$ Comparison	170
4.6.5.2	Different Components in the π^0 Mass Window	170
4.6.6	Acceptance and Efficiency Break Down	175
4.6.7	$\langle\epsilon f\rangle$ Result	176
4.7	Cocktail Ratio	177
4.7.1	Neutral Pions	178
4.7.2	η meson	178
4.7.2.1	η/π^0 Ratio in p+p and p+A Collisions	180
4.7.2.2	η/π^0 Ratio in A+A Collisions	180
4.7.3	Other Mesons	183
4.7.4	Decay Photons	184
4.8	Systematic uncertainties	184
4.8.1	Systematic on $N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}/N_\gamma^{\text{tag}}$	185
4.8.1.1	π^0 Yield Extraction – Type A	185
4.8.1.2	Conversion Sample Purity – Type B	193
4.8.2	Systematic on $\langle\epsilon f\rangle$	193
4.8.2.1	Energy Scale and Resolution – Type B	193
4.8.2.2	Photon Efficiency – Type B	200
4.8.2.3	Conversion Photon Loss – Type C	201
4.8.2.4	Active Area and Geometry Acceptance – Type C	203
4.8.3	Systematics on Cocktail Ratio	207
4.8.3.1	η/π^0 Ratio – Type B	207
4.8.4	Summary of Systematic Uncertainties on R_γ	208
4.8.5	Systematic Uncertainties on γ^{direct}	210
4.8.5.1	Systematic Uncertainties on γ^{hadron}	210
4.8.5.2	Uncertainty Propagation and MC Sampling Method	210
4.8.5.3	Summary of Systematic Uncertainties on γ^{direct}	215

5	Results and Discussion	219
5.1	Results	219
5.1.1	Direct Photon R_γ	219
5.1.2	Direct Photon Invariant Yield	220
5.2	Discussion	225
5.2.1	Low p_T Direct Photon Excess	226
5.2.1.1	Very Low p_T Region	228
5.2.1.2	Intermediate p_T Region	230
5.2.1.3	Comparison with LHC Results	232
5.2.1.4	Comparison to Hydrodynamics Model	235
5.2.2	High p_T Direct Photon	238
5.2.3	Centrality Dependence	240
5.2.4	Revisiting the Direct Photon Puzzle	247
5.2.5	Conclusions	250
	Appendices	252
A	Kinematics in Hadron-Hadron Scattering	253
	Bibliography	258

Acknowledgements

It has been a long and fun journey during my entire graduate study, and I would not have made it to the end without so many people's help and support.

I want to start by thanking my advisor Axel Drees, who has been both a great mentor and a friend. He is a passionate and hard working researcher with great intuition in both analysis details and physics picture. His insights guided me through the whole analysis. And all the discussions we had make me able to transit from just following ideas to think more independently. In retrospect, I have made every mistake I can make during my PhD time, but thanks to his patience and encouragement, every mistake feels more like a valuable lesson rather than just a failure. There were also many crisis times – before my conference talk, before my interview, before my thesis defense etc, and Axel is always there with full support and belief so we can push things through. His many characteristics shaped my researching way and make me want to continue and explore more in this exciting field.

I also want to express my sincere gratitudes towards Gabor David, who closely followed through this analysis and offered countless valuable comments and suggestions at every step of it. All my knowledge about electro-magnetic calorimeter is from his tireless explanations.

We have a wonderful group in Stony Brook with experts covering a broad spectrum of nuclear physics. I'm more than grateful for being part of it and want to thank the group leaders – Axel, Thomas Hemmick and Abhay Deshpande – for keeping such a strong group with a liberal atmosphere. I will always remember the lively discussions on our Monday group meetings.

There are many scientists, postdocs and students in our group and I have been fortunate enough to closely work with many of them. I want to thank Alan Dion, who I worked with on my very first project. He is enthusiastic about both physics, coding, and in the mean time such a good teacher. He made my learning curve painless when joining the group and it was easy and fun working with him. I also want to thank Norbert Novitzky, who is great analyzer. He shared with me so many hands on analysis experience and skills. We had numerous discussions over almost every detail of my analysis, which

laid the foundation of all the results obtained at the end. I also want to thank Deepali Sharma, she helped me as an expert on electron analysis and also as a caring friend. I want to thank Prakhar Garg for patiently entertaining all my simplistic questions on the detectors and hardwares. I want to thank my fellow students, especially Yuehang Leung, Vladmir Khachatryan and Zhongling Ji for all the help, discussions and chitchat. I feel so lucky being in the same office with them. Some of my group members already started (or about to start) a new job and some of them are still in the group, I wish the best to all of them for their future endeavors.

Not only I received many help from the group, I was also afforded with many opportunities. My main PhD project is about data analysis, but I was also given a chance to work on a side project, the test beam study of Zigzag readout plane. It was an amazing trip and I learnt so much during it. I want to thank Axel, Tom and Alexander Kiselev for putting me on this project, and I want to thank everyone in this test beam for all their help, teaching, and patience of answering all my questions.

I also want to thank the administrators of our group, especially Socorro Delquaglio. She has been so kind to me and made me life much easier when dealing with paper works.

I'm both grateful and proud to be a part of the PHENIX collaboration. There are so many experts ranging from hardware, software to data analysis who are willing to help and in particular friendly and encouraging to junior members. I want to thank Takao Sakaguchi, Alexander Bazilevsky, Stefan Bathe and many other people for their comments and suggestions on my analysis. I want to thank Chris Pinkenburg in particular, who has been generously helping debugging my code and fixing the my condor jobs without any payment for a long time. I also want to thank the management team for arranging the physics group meetings, collaboration meetings, and especially schools, journal clubs, and maintaining the documentations.

My sincere thanks to my thesis defense committee members and everybody who come to my defense both virtually and physically. And I will always cherish the celebration we had afterwards – it was a difficult time during this COVID pandemic period, but I never felt alone because of everyone around me.

In the end, I would like to thank my friends and family. I want to thank Yue Zhao, Beibei Zhang, Shengnan Wang for all the warm company and laughters. I want to thank Na Zhu for all our fun trips together. I want to thank Roli Esha and Barak Schmookler, who sits through all my tedious rehearsal talks without complaining, and especially Barak for proof-reading and patiently editing my thesis. To my family, I owe more than what I can put into words.

They supported all my decisions with love and ask for nothing in return. I am who I am and where I am because of them.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Quarks, Gluons and Quantum ChromoDynamics

The Standard Model of particle physics is a framework which describes the interactions of the elementary particles under three of the four fundamental forces [1]. Details of these elementary particles, which comprise all visible matter, as well as the four fundamental forces are given in Tab. 1.1 and Tab. 1.2. In the Standard Model, Quantum ChromoDynamics (QCD) is the theory of the strong force and describes the interaction of the quarks and gluons. The quarks are spin-1/2 particles and come in six flavors: up, down, strange, charm, bottom, and top. They carry an electric charge of either $+2/3$ or $-1/3$ (relative to the fundamental charge) and one of 3 color charges, either *red*, *green*, or *blue*. The quarks interact with each other via the strong force through the exchange of gluons, which are massless spin-1 gauge bosons. Since gluons also carry color charges, they can couple directly to one another (unlike the photon in QED which carries no electric charge and can only couple to charged fermions). This non-Abelian feature of QCD has interesting implications for the behavior of strongly-interacting matter, as discussed below.

QCD has two important features relevant to the work in this thesis: asymptotic freedom and color confinement [1, 2]. Both of these features arise from interactions with the quantum vacuum, which lead to a change in strength of the interaction. This phenomenon is typically referred to as running of the coupling constant (α_s).

In QCD, a charge screening effect exists due to the production of virtual $q\bar{q}$ pairs. If this were the only effect present, as in QED, the strong coupling constant would increase with decreasing distance. However, the self interaction of the colored gluons produces an anti-screening effect which competes with

Name	Type	Charge
up	Quark	+2/3
down	Quark	-1/3
strange	Quark	-1/3
charm	Quark	+2/3
bottom	Quark	-1/3
top	Quark	+2/3
electron (neutrino)	Lepton	-1 (0)
muon (neutrino)	Lepton	-1 (0)
tau (neutrino)	Lepton	-1 (0)

Table 1.1: Table of elementary particles and some of their properties.

Force	Exchange Particle	Range	Relative Strength
Strong	gluon	∞	1
Electromagnetic	photon	∞	10^{-2}
Weak	Z^0, W^+, W^-	10^{-18} m	10^{-13}
Gravity	graviton	∞	10^{-38}

Table 1.2: Table of fundamental forces and some of their properties.

the screening effect described above. This gives the following scale dependence of α_s [1]:

$$\alpha_s(Q^2) = \frac{12\pi}{(11n - 2f) \ln(Q^2/\Lambda^2)} \quad . \quad (1.1)$$

In equation Eq. 1.1, Q^2 is the negative of the square of the four-momentum transfer at the strong interaction vertex. It gives the energy/resolution scale of the probe and is inversely related to the distance. Λ is the QCD Scale. n is the number of colors (3 in QCD) and f is the number of flavors (6 in QCD); since $11n > 2f$, α_s will decrease with increasing Q^2 (i.e. α_s will become small at short distance scales). The running of α_s is shown in Fig. 1.1. If $Q^2 \gg \Lambda^2$, perturbative calculations can be used successfully. If Q^2 is approximately the same size as Λ , however, then non-perturbative approaches are necessary.

Color confinement is another important consequence of the running of the strong coupling constant. Quarks and gluons (i.e. colored objects) are ordinarily confined in color-singlet states, and therefore we never observe free quarks or gluons. Color confinement can be understood qualitatively as follows: if the quark and anti-quark in a color-singlet meson are moved apart from one another, α_s and the potential energy will increase; eventually, the system will have enough energy to form new color-singlet $q\bar{q}$ pairs. This is why

Figure 1.1: Running of the strong coupling constant as a function of the momentum transfer. Figure taken from [3].

during scattering experiments, for example, we never observe a single quark or gluon in our detector – rather, we observe the result of the fragmentation and hadronization processes which converts all energy into production of particles in color neutral states.

We can study QCD in a unique way by using ultra-relativistic heavy ion collisions. The coupling constant also decreases in an environment with extremely high temperature and/or density. Thus if the temperature and/or density of a system of hadrons is increased, the color confined state of the hadrons is believed to transition into a color deconfined state called the Quark-Gluon Plasma (QGP). The heavy ion collisions discussed in this thesis are the best way to probe this unique regime of matter.

1.2 Quark Gluon Plasma and Relativistic Heavy Ion Collisions

The notion of the “Quark Gluon Plasma” phase and its existence in super hot and dense nuclear matter was first proposed by Shuryak in 1980 [4]. This novel state of matter, where the constituent partons are no longer bounded in color neutral states, is theorized to exist in the center of neutron stars and

just after the Big Bang.

1.2.1 Deconfinement and the Phase Diagram

Although the nature of the phase transition, whether it is first order or crossover, from ordinary hadronic matter to QGP is still unclear, the critical temperature is predicted to be $T_c \approx 155\text{-}170 \text{ MeV} \approx 10^{12} K$ at $\mu_B = 0$ from lattice QCD [5][6]. The corresponding energy density (ϵ_c) is around $1.2 \text{ GeV}/\text{fm}^3$, which is about 3 times higher than the nuclear density in proton.

Fig. 1.2a shows the result from a lattice QCD calculation. A steep rise of the scaled energy density ϵ/T^4 can be observed when the temperature T goes from $T < T_c$ to $T > T_c$. For a relativistic Fermi or Bose gas in thermal equilibrium, the scaled energy density ϵ/T^4 is proportional to the number of different particle species, including different charge, spin, flavor and color states. Thus ϵ/T^4 reflects the available degrees of freedom in the system. The sharp transition of ϵ/T^4 at T_c can then be interpreted as the transition of a system going from hadronic degrees of freedom to partonic degrees of freedom.

Fig. 1.2b shows a predicted phase diagram for QCD matter, along with the coverage of a few current (e.g. RHIC and LHC) and future experiments (e.g. FAIR). These experiments utilize heavy ions colliding at relativistic energies to create QGP, study its properties, and explore the nature of the phase transition at different temperatures and baryon densities in the laboratory environment.

1.2.2 Relativistic Heavy Ion Collisions

In relativistic heavy ion collisions, the nuclei will appear pancake-shaped due to the Lorentz contraction ($\gamma \sim 106$ at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200 \text{ GeV}$) before colliding with each other. The initial colliding geometry, as shown in Fig. 1.3, can be characterized by the transverse size of the nuclei and the impact parameter b , which is the distance between the center of the two nuclei. The nucleons inside the overlapping region interact and are called participants in the collision, and the nucleons in the non-overlapping region are called spectators, as they will continue moving along the beam direction. Part of the kinetic energy of the participants will be deposited into the overlapping region. If the energy density exceeds the critical energy density ϵ_c , QGP will be formed.

1.2.2.1 Bjorken Energy Density

A simple way of estimating the energy density at the QGP formation time τ_0 was introduced by Bjorken [8] and is illustrated in Fig. 1.4.

Figure 1.2: Left: Lattice QCD result of suitably normalized pressure, energy density, and entropy density as a function of the temperature, where T_c is the critical temperature. Figure taken from [6]. Right: Schematic phase diagram of QCD matter. Figure taken from [7].

Figure 1.3: A cartoon illustrating the geometry of the two colliding nuclei just before and after the collision happens.

The total energy produced during the collision is related to the total energy of the particles produced at mid-rapidity $d\langle E\rangle/dy|_{y=0} \approx d\langle E_T\rangle/dy|_{y=0}$ (longitudinal velocity is negligible at $y = 0$). At time $t = \tau_0$, the energy inside

Figure 1.4: An illustration from Bjorken of the geometry of initially produced particles at time t after the overlap of the incoming nuclei. Figure taken from [8].

a thin slab at the center of thickness $2d$ can be estimated as:

$$E = \frac{d\langle E \rangle}{dy} \Delta y = \frac{d\langle E \rangle}{dy} \Big|_{y=0} \frac{2d}{\tau_0} \approx \frac{d\langle E_T \rangle}{dy} \Big|_{y=0} \frac{2d}{\tau_0} \quad (1.2)$$

The volume of this thin region of interest can be calculated:

$$V = 2d \cdot A = 2d\pi R^2 \quad (1.3)$$

where R is the nuclear radius.

Combining Eq. 1.2 and Eq. 1.3, the energy can be obtained:

$$\epsilon_{BJ} = \frac{E}{V} = \frac{1}{2d\pi R^2} \frac{d\langle E \rangle}{dy} \Big|_{y=0} \frac{2d}{\tau_0} \approx \frac{1}{\tau_0\pi R^2} \frac{d\langle E_T \rangle}{dy} \Big|_{y=0} \quad (1.4)$$

Assuming $\tau_0 \sim 1$ fm, $\epsilon_{BJ} \approx 5$ GeV/fm³ in central Au+Au collisions at 200 GeV, and $\epsilon_{BJ} \approx 14$ GeV/fm³ in central Pb+Pb collisions at 2.76 TeV. These energy densities are above the predicted critical energy density $\epsilon_c \sim 1.2$ GeV/fm³ corresponding to the phase transition.

1.2.2.2 Space Time Evolution

From the time when the nuclei first overlap to the time the final state particles are produced and freely stream into the detectors, the collision system undergoes various phases. The details of each phase are still under investigation, but a commonly used picture of the evolution of the matter is shown in Fig. 1.5.

At time $t = 0$, many inelastic nucleon-nucleon collisions occur in a short time. This is followed by a short pre-equilibrium stage, where free partons are released and scatter off each other. The multi-parton system quickly equilibrates and QGP is formed at $t = \tau_0$. Once the equilibrium is achieved, the medium can be characterized by thermodynamic quantities like pressure and temperature. During the QGP stage, the evolution of the system can be described by almost ideal hydrodynamics, meaning the system will behave like a very low viscosity fluid. The system will expand and cool, and once the temperature crosses the transition temperature of ~ 160 MeV (used in [9]) at $t = t_C$, hadronization will occur. During this transition, there can be a mixed phase of QGP and hadrons if it is a first order phase transition. After $t = t_H$, the system consists of hadrons which undergo inelastic interactions. This stage is often referred to as the hadron gas (HG) or hadron fluid stage. As the system continues to expand and cools to the freeze-out temperature of ~ 100 MeV, the hadrons will only interact elastically and the produced particle species will be fixed. The momentum distributions of particles will be fixed after the temperature drops further to the kinetic freeze-out temperature. Finally, the produced particles (or their decay products) will stream out freely and can be measured by the detectors.

Fig. 1.5 also includes the typical time scale and temperature of different stages of the evolution. These quantities are model dependent. The values shown are typical estimates for collisions at RHIC and LHC. Generally the QGP phase is believed to be short lived (1 - 10 fm/c). As experiments can only measure the final products after the complicated space-time evolution, observables which are most sensitive to the QGP (so called “QGP signatures”) are needed in order to examine the existence and property of QGP. Many QGP signatures have been proposed and observed over the years [10–13]. The study of the production of thermal photons emitted from the hot-dense medium is the main topic of this thesis.

1.3 Direct Photon Production

Of all the photons produced in high energy heavy ion collisions, the majority (~ 80 - 90%) are photons from hadronic decay after the chemical and kinetic

Figure 1.5: Space time evolution of the medium produced in relativistic heavy ion collisions. The displayed times and temperatures of different stages are from [9].

freeze-out. While these *decay photons* may be of interest themselves, they are not sensitive to the earlier stage of the collision. Hence we usually subtract the decay contribution to extract photons emitted directly from the interaction, and these are commonly referred as *direct photons*.

Direct photons from heavy ion collisions are considered as a unique probe to study both the thermal properties and the space-time evolution of the collision. Unlike hadronic observables, direct photons are “color blind” probes, which means they will not interact strongly with the medium, and hence carry information of their creation point and of the temperature of the production medium. Also, direct photons are produced at almost all known or conjectured stages of the collision, as shown in Fig. 1.6. Therefore, by measuring direct photons one has access to the whole history of the evolution of the collision system.

Based on the production mechanism, direct photons can be roughly categorized into four classes:

- *Prompt*: photons produced from initial parton-parton scattering – quark anti-quark annihilation, quark gluon inverse Compton scattering or fragmentation processes.

Figure 1.6: Schematic of photon sources in heavy ion collisions.

- *Thermal*: thermal photons emitted from the QGP and hadron gas phase.
- *Parton-medium interactions*: photons produced from scattering between energetic partons from hard processes and the thermal partons in the medium, such as jet in-medium Bremsstrahlung [14], jet-photon conversion [15]*, etc. More details in Sec. 5.2.2 and Sec. 5.2.4.
- *Pre-equilibrium*: photons produced from the pre-equilibrium stage, like photons produced from Glasma [16–18], the strong initial magnetic field [19–21], etc. More details in Sec. 5.2.4.

As one can see, there are many sources contributing to direct photon production and one needs to rely on various differential measurements – like the p_T spectrum or flow coefficients (see Sec. 1.4.2) – to disentangle components. Different types of direct photons have dissimilar p_T spectra, as illustrated in Fig. 1.7. Prompt photons have the power-law shape and dominate in the high p_T region (above 4-5 GeV) of the direct photon spectrum, while thermal photons are predicted to dominate in the low p_T regime (below ~ 3 GeV) with a superposition of Boltzmann distributions reflecting the temperature evolution. The production of pre-equilibrium photons and parton-medium photons is under intense discussion, with some calculations showing that they can play a significant role in the intermediate p_T range.

1.3.1 Prompt Photons and the p+p “Baseline”

In heavy ion physics, a powerful diagnostic tool we use to study QGP medium effects is to compare the results from heavy ion-heavy ion collisions (A+A

*Sometimes also referred as jet-medium conversion or jet-thermal photons

Figure 1.7: Left: Schematic of photon emission rate produced by different sources as a function of the photon energy. Right: Spectra of photons from different sources in a theoretical calculation (figure taken from [22]).

collisions) to the results from proton-proton collisions (p+p collisions) after correcting for the effect of a larger number of nucleons present in A+A collisions. Therefore, we often refer to measurements made in p+p collisions as the “baseline” measurements. Direct photon measurements in p+p collisions play an important role in studying both the prompt component and non-prompt components in A+A collisions. Because QGP is not created in p+p collisions, the direct photons in p+p collisions are just prompt photons. Measuring and calculating the direct photons produced in p+p collisions can test our understanding of prompt photon production and also help us estimate the prompt photon contribution in the A+A collisions and separate out thermal photons. In this section we will introduce the calculation of prompt photons using perturbative-QCD (pQCD) in p+p collision and then the Glauber model which we use to estimate the prompt photons in A+A collisions from the p+p results.

1.3.1.1 Photons from Hard Scattering Processes

For the case of prompt photon production, the leading-order (LO) and a next-to-leading-order (NLO) reactions at the parton level are shown in Fig. 1.8. At LO, there are two contributing processes: $q(\bar{q}) + g \rightarrow \gamma + q(\bar{q})$ (inverse QCD Compton scattering or quark+gluon Compton scattering) and $q + \bar{q} \rightarrow \gamma + g$ (quark+anti-quark annihilation); at NLO, the photon can be produced by Bremsstrahlung or fragmentation.

The LO inverse QCD Compton scattering process dominates prompt photon production in proton-proton and nucleus-nucleus collisions. The parton-

Figure 1.8: LO and NLO diagrams contributing to prompt photon production. The top left diagram shows the inverse QCD Compton scattering process; a second “ \hat{s} channel” diagram (not shown) also contributes. The top right diagram shows quark+anti-quark annihilation; the gluon (photon) can also attach to the quark (anti-quark) line. The bottom center diagram shows photon Bremsstrahlung off the outgoing quark in elastic quark-gluon scattering; prompt photons can also be produced during the fragmentation process.

level cross section for $q + g \rightarrow \gamma + q$ is given by [23, 24]

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\hat{t}} = -e_q^2 \frac{\pi \alpha_s \alpha_{em}}{3 \hat{s}^2} \left(\frac{\hat{s}}{\hat{u}} + \frac{\hat{u}}{\hat{s}} \right) , \quad (1.5)$$

where the quark mass has been ignored. e_q is the charge of the quark, $\alpha_{s(em)}$ is the strong (electromagnetic) coupling constant, and $\hat{s} = (p_g + p_q)^2$, $\hat{t} = (p_g - p_\gamma)^2$, and $\hat{u} = (p_q - p_\gamma)^2$ are the Mandelstam variables. Note that as this is a $2 \rightarrow 2$ scattering process, the cross section is only differential with respect to a single variable.[†]

1.3.1.2 High p_T Direct Photon Production in p+p Collisions

Due to the asymptotic freedom that is present in QCD, cross sections at high momentum transfer ($Q^2 \gg \Lambda^2$) can be calculated using perturbative QCD (pQCD). The proton-proton scattering cross section at high-momentum transfers, for example, is described in pQCD as a convolution of the underlying

[†]The cross section is also differential with respect to the azimuthal angle, but trivially so due to symmetry considerations. To wit, if the azimuthal had not been integrated over, the cross section would simply be changed by a factor of 2π .

parton-parton scattering cross section and the parton distribution functions (pdfs) of the participating partons [3, 25]. This is known as pQCD factorization and is shown schematically in Fig. 1.9. The cross section for the reaction $pp \rightarrow X$, with underlying parton-parton reaction $ab \rightarrow X$, can be written as

$$\sigma_{pp \rightarrow X} = \sum_{a,b} \int_0^1 dx_1 dx_2 f_a(x_1, Q^2) f_b(x_2, Q^2) \hat{\sigma}_{ab \rightarrow X} \quad (1.6)$$

In Eq. 1.6 above, the total cross section is a function of the underlying parton-parton cross section, $\hat{\sigma}_{ab \rightarrow X}$, times the pdfs of the incoming partons, $f_{a(b)}(x_1, Q^2)$. The pdf for a specific parton species in the proton is equal to the number density of that parton at a given x and Q^2 , where x gives the fraction of the proton's momentum carried by the parton in the Infinite-Momentum Frame and Q^2 gives the four-momentum transfer [26].

Figure 1.9: Proton-proton high-momentum transfer reaction. The underlying parton-parton reaction shown here is a $2 \rightarrow 2$ reaction (i.e. $a + b \rightarrow c + d$). The outgoing partons c and d fragment into jets X and Y , respectively. The fragmentation functions D give the probability that a specific parton species with momentum \hat{z} will fragment into a specific hadron jet.

The full $p + p \rightarrow \gamma + q + X$ cross section for LO inverse QCD Compton scattering is a 3-fold differential cross section (two pdfs + the hard parton-parton scattering). We can rewrite the cross section as differential with respect to the rapidities of the outgoing photon and quark (y_γ and y_q) and the square of the transverse momentum of the outgoing photon and quark with respect to the direction of the incoming beams (p_T). This 3-fold cross section, $\frac{d^3\sigma}{dp_T^2 dy_\gamma dy_q}$, is Lorentz-invariant to boosts along the beam direction, and it can be expressed

as [27]

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^3\sigma}{dp_T^2 dy_\gamma dy_q} &= x_1 g(x_1) F_2(x_2, Q^2) \frac{\pi\alpha_{em}(Q^2)\alpha_s(Q^2)}{3\hat{s}^2} \times \\
&\quad \left(\frac{1 + \cos\theta^*}{2} + \frac{2}{1 + \cos\theta^*} \right) \\
&+ x_2 g(x_2) F_2(x_1, Q^2) \frac{\pi\alpha_{em}(Q^2)\alpha_s(Q^2)}{3\hat{s}^2} \times \\
&\quad \left(\frac{1 - \cos\theta^*}{2} + \frac{2}{1 - \cos\theta^*} \right) .
\end{aligned} \tag{1.7}$$

Here g is the gluon pdf, and F_2 is the structure function measured in electron-proton Deep-Inelastic Scattering experiments. In the quark-parton model, F_2 is directly related to the quark and anti-quark pdfs as $F_2 = x \sum_q e_q^2 (q + \bar{q})$. $\sqrt{\hat{s}}$ is the parton-parton center-of-mass energy, and θ^* is the angle in the parton-parton center-of-mass frame of the outgoing photon with respect to the first hadron (proton) beam (i.e. the beam moving in the +z direction).

The details of how to relate the experimentally measured quantities – p_T , y_γ , and y_q – to the other quantities in Eq. 1.7 – x_1 , x_2 , Q^2 , \hat{s} , and θ^* – can be found in Appendix. A. As a result of the derivations, Q^2 (in the “t channel” for example) can be expressed as:

$$Q^2 = p_T^2 (e^{y_4 - y_3} + 1) \tag{1.8}$$

Looking back at the cross section in Eq. 1.7 which was calculated using pQCD, we can see from Eq. 1.8 that this cross section formula is only valid if the transverse momentum is high enough to satisfy $Q^2 \gg \Lambda^2$, which would correspond to $p_T > \sim 1 - 2$ GeV for direct photons produced at the mid-rapidity.

If an experiment is measuring inclusive prompt photon production (i.e. $p + p \rightarrow \gamma + X$ for proton beams), then the cross section in Eq. 1.7 needs to be integrated over y_q . The inclusive cross section is then differential with respect to p_T and y_γ . Using the relation

$$\left(\frac{dp_z}{dy} \right)_{M_T} = M_T \cosh y = E \quad , \tag{1.9}$$

we can write the inclusive cross section as

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{d^2\sigma}{p_T dp_T dy} = \frac{d^3\sigma}{dp_x dp_y dy} = E \frac{d^3\sigma}{dp_x dp_y dp_z} = E \frac{d^3\sigma}{dp^3} \quad , \tag{1.10}$$

which is a form sometimes presented in the literature [27].

1.3.1.3 Prompt Photons in A+A collisions

In order to use data from p+p scattering to tease out cold and hot nuclear matter effects from proton-nucleus (p+A) and nucleus-nucleus (A+B) scattering, we need a model to scale the p+p results to directly compare to the p+A and A+B data. This is done using the *Glauber* model [28, 29] for high-energy scattering of composite particles. The model views the nucleus in terms of its individual nucleons. The model assumes the nucleons move on independent linear trajectories, an assumption that is valid at sufficiently high energies. In calculations using the *Glauber* model, experimental data on the distribution of charge inside the nucleus as well as the energy dependence of the inelastic nucleon-nucleon cross section are needed as inputs to the model. The charge distribution for heavy nuclei is usually parameterized as a Fermi or Woods-Saxon distribution [29]. With the above model assumptions and experimental inputs, it is straightforward to determine the number of nucleons participating in the interaction (N_{part}) and the number of individual nucleon-nucleon collisions (N_{coll}) as a function of the distance (the impact parameter, b) between the target and projectile centers.

The calculations of the geometric quantities (N_{part} and N_{coll}) in the *Glauber* model can be performed using in the Optical-Limit Approximation or using the *Glauber* Monte Carlo (GMC) method [29]. The optical approach allows for the analytic calculation of geometric quantities, but under a smooth-density approximation, which can lead to systematic errors in the calculation of the geometric quantities. Using the GMC approach in conjunction with realistic physics event generators to simulate experimental quantities gives the most accurate model calculations.

In the GMC approach for the collision of two nuclei, the nucleons in each nucleus are distributed according to the charge density relative to the center of the respective nucleus. For a given impact parameter, b , the nucleus-nucleus collision is treated as a set of independent nucleon-nucleon collisions. In the black-disk version of the GMC approach, the nucleons are treated as spheres with radii equal to $\sqrt{\sigma_{inel}^{NN}/\pi}/2$, where σ_{inel}^{NN} is the total inelastic nucleon-nucleon cross section. A collision between two nucleons takes place if their spheres overlap during the nucleus-nucleus collision. If many nucleus-nucleus collisions are simulated for a certain value of b , the average values of the geometric quantities, $\langle N_{part} \rangle$ and $\langle N_{coll} \rangle$, can be extracted. An example of a GMC Au+Au collision is shown in Fig. 1.10.

The geometric quantities calculated in the GMC model cannot be extracted directly from experimental data. Rather, the real events are ordered according

Figure 1.10: Example of a GMC event for an Au+Au collision with an impact parameter of $b = 5.8$ fm. The left plot shows the collision in the plane transverse to the beam direction; the right shows the collision in a plane containing the beam direction.

to their charged particle multiplicity, and then classified into centrality classes according to the fraction of the total cross section contained in the class. Centrality classes are then defined the same way in the GMC simulation, and $\langle N_{part} \rangle$ and $\langle N_{coll} \rangle$ are calculated for each class.

To quantify medium-induced effects on hard processes in heavy ion collisions, the nuclear modification factor, R_{AA} , is defined for a given p_T as [29]

$$R_{AA,x}(p_T) = \frac{dN_x^{AA}/dp_T}{(\langle N_{coll} \rangle / \sigma_{inel}^{NN}) d\sigma_x^{pp}/dp_T} \quad , \quad (1.11)$$

where dN_x^{AA}/dp_T is the differential average yield per inelastic A+A event of the hard process under consideration, and $d\sigma_x^{pp}/dp_T$ is the differential cross section for the same hard process in p+p scattering. In absence of the QGP, R_{AA} is expected to be close to unity[‡].

1.3.2 Thermal Radiation

The hot and dense medium will emit thermal radiation in terms of photons and low mass leptons (virtual photons γ^*). Such emissions come from both the QGP phase, where photons are produced from scattering between thermalized partons (Fig. 1.11a), and from the hadron gas phase, where photons are produced from interacting mesons and baryons (Fig. 1.11b).

Calculation of the photon emissions from thermalized QGP and hadron gas can be done with finite-temperature field theory. The escape rate of photons

[‡] R_{AA} can also be modified by the cold nuclear effects, such as nuclear absorption, parton shadowing and parton energy loss in initial and final states

Figure 1.11: Left: photon produced from thermal partons. Right: photon produced from thermal hadrons ($\pi\rho \rightarrow \pi\gamma$ shown as an example).

from the medium (photon emission rate R_γ of photons with energy E) is related to the imaginary part of the in-medium proper photon self-energy $\Pi_{\mu\nu}$ at finite temperature T :

$$E \frac{dR_\gamma}{d^3p} = \frac{-2}{(2\pi)^3} \text{Im} \Pi_\mu^{R,\mu} \frac{1}{e^{E/T} - 1} + \mathcal{O}(\alpha_{em}^2) \quad (1.12)$$

The thermal photon production can be calculated after combining the emission rate with the dynamical evolution of the system. Because the thermal photon emission rate is related to the local medium temperature, thermal photons provide us a “thermometer” to access the temperature profile of the medium.

1.4 Direct photon measurement

The search for direct photons began at the fixed target experiments at the CERN SPS in 1986. Over the years there have been fruitful results in elementary hadron-hadron collisions, hadron-ion collisions and ion-ion collisions from the SPS, FNAL and BNL AGS experiments. But it was not until the start of the RHIC program and later the heavy ion program at LHC that precision measurements of direct photons were made in heavy ion collision systems and in the lower p_T regime. In the following sections, we briefly summarize the measured direct photon yield and anisotropy at RHIC and LHC energies.

1.4.1 Direct Photon Yield

A summary of direct photon measurements reported by the PHENIX and ALICE experiments is shown in Fig. 1.12. There are two distinct regions, low p_T ($< 4\text{-}5$ GeV) where the spectrum is of an exponential shape, and high p_T where the spectrum is more like a power law shape. The spectrum shape changes because different photon sources dominate in different p_T regions. The high p_T photons are predominantly prompt photons, and hence they are consistent with the N_{coll} scaled pp result. pQCD calculations of the prompt photons describes the high p_T heavy ion results well. However, at lower p_T , an excess of direct photons is observed above both the p+p baseline and the pQCD calculation. Given the exponential-like shape and the expected momentum range of thermal photons, a natural interpretation is that the excess is mostly thermal photons from QGP and hadron gas. If one subtracts the estimated prompt contribution, an inverse slope of $T_{\text{eff}} \sim 240$ MeV is extracted from an exponential fit $\frac{dN}{dp_T} \propto e^{-p_T/T_{\text{eff}}}$ for central Au+Au collisions and ~ 300 MeV for central Pb+Pb collisions. One caveat is that the thermal photon spectrum will be blue-shifted because the photons are emitted from an expanding system (analogous to Doppler effect), and hence T_{eff} can be higher than the local temperature. However, taking T_{eff} and realistic space-time evolution of the medium into account, theoretical models predict a $T_{\text{init}} > 300$ MeV at formation time for central Au+Au collisions, still well above the expected critical temperature T_c .

1.4.2 Direct Photon Flow

Another observable to help understand the sources of low p_T direct photons is particle anisotropy, often referred to as “flow”. As we have discussed in Sec. 1.2.2.2, the space-time evolution of the QGP and hadron gas medium can be well described by low-viscosity relativistic hydrodynamics. In fact, the experimental evidence implies that the medium behaves like a “perfect fluid”, of which the viscosity over entropy ratio η/s is only 1-4 times the lower conjectured bound $-1/4\pi$. Because of this fluid-like nature, the particles inside the medium will expand collectively, or say *flow*. Moreover, if the medium has an anisotropic geometry, the flow of the medium will develop anisotropically.

In a non-central Au+Au collision, the initial interaction region is of an almond shape, as shown in Fig. 1.13a. If one defines a special plane formed by the impact vector and the beam axis, the *reaction plane*, the motion of the medium can be considered separately parallel to the reaction plane (*in plane*) and perpendicular to the reaction plane (*out of plane*). Because the pressure gradient is larger perpendicular to the reaction plane (*out-of-plane*) than par-

Figure 1.12: Left: a compilation of published direct photon yield results from the PHENIX experiment for Au+Au and p+p collisions at 200 GeV. Right: direct photon yield result from the ALICE experiment for Pb+Pb at 2.76 TeV.

allel to the reaction plane (*in-plane*), the medium will expand faster in-plane comparing to out-of-plane. Throughout the development of the flow motion, the initial space anisotropy will be converted into a momentum anisotropy. As a result, more particles will be observed in-plane. This effect can be quantified by looking at the Fourier decomposition of particle azimuthal distributions with respect to the reaction plane:

$$\frac{dN}{d(\phi - \Psi_k)} = N_0 \left[1 + \sum_n v_{kn} \cos n(\phi - \Psi_k) \right], \quad (1.13)$$

where ϕ is the azimuthal angle of the particles of interest, photons in this thesis, Ψ_k is the orientation of the k^{th} order event plane for a given event, for more details see [30]. v_{kn} is the n^{th} coefficient with respect to the k^{th} event plane. On the assumption that different order event planes are uncorrelated, $k \neq n$ terms will vanish. The remaining v_{22} and v_{33} are then usually shorted as v_2 and v_3 respectively. Based on the correlation between the initial geometric shape and the magnitude of the v_n signal, v_2 is often called *elliptical flow*, and v_3 is called *triangular flow*. In symmetric collision systems like Au+Au, v_2 arises from the elliptical interaction region, while v_3 arises from the initial

geometric fluctuation and is more sensitive to the viscosity of the medium.

Figure 1.13: Left: a cartoon illustration of the overlapping region of the collisions and pressure gradient around the medium. Right: A theoretical prediction for thermal photon v_2 (solid curve), where different color corresponds to different formation time of QGP. Figure taken from [31].

Fig. 1.14 shows the measured v_2 for different charged hadrons in Au+Au collisions at 200 GeV. One can see that the charged hadrons show a flow signal up to ~ 0.2 . After scaling v_2 by the number of valence quarks and converting p_T to KE_T/n_q , a universal trend is observed, which is consistent with the hydrodynamic models and indicates that the collective behavior originates at the partonic level.

The charged hadrons exhibit a strong flow signal because they are final state particles and experience the full expansion, which, however, is not the case for direct photons. Prompt photons are expected to have no flow signal since they are emitted before the formation of the QGP medium. The thermal photons, especially those from QGP radiation as compared to hadron gas radiation, are expected to have a small flow signal because the collective motion is not fully developed at that early of a time, as illustrated in Fig. 1.13b. Surprisingly, the measured direct photon v_2 turns out to be of similar magnitude to the hadron v_2 , as shown in Fig. 1.15.

1.4.3 Theoretical Models

There are many theoretical predictions on the market which employ different approaches for calculating the photon emission rate and modeling the space-time evolution dynamics. In the following section, we will briefly introduce

Figure 1.14: v_2 of identified hadrons as a function of p_T (left), KE_T (middle), where $KE_T \equiv \sqrt{p_T^2 + m_0^2} - m_0$. The right panel shows the v_2/n_q as a function of KE_T/n_q , where n_q is the number of valence quarks ($n_q = 2$ for mesons, $n_q = 3$ for baryons). Figure taken from [32].

Figure 1.15: Left: direct photon v_2 as a function of p_T for 20-40% Au+Au collisions at 200 GeV. Right: direct photon v_2 as a function of p_T for 20-40% Pb+Pb collisions at 2.76 TeV.

a few models; a comparison between these models and data can be found in Fig. 1.16.

Viscous Hydrodynamic Model The expansion of QGP is described by relativistic hydrodynamics. A 2+1D hydrodynamic model is used with shear and bulk viscosity corrections [15, 33]. The expansion of the hadron gas is modeled by a transport model—UrQMD [34, 35]. Calculation of the photon emission rate from the QGP phase assumes weakly coupled plasma and takes into account leading and next to leading order photon-production processes (thermal radiation, Bremsstrahlung in the plasma, effect of soft gluons, the Landau-Pomeranchuk-Migdal effect, etc.) in α_s [36]. The photon emission rate from the hadron gas includes both mesonic and baryonic contributions, together with an estimate of the meson-meson and meson-baryon Bremsstrahlung contribution. Two sets of calculations are shown in Fig. 1.16 – with and without the viscosity correction [37]. It can be seen that the yield goes up but the azimuthal anisotropy decreases after the viscosity correction.

Fireball model The medium evolution is described by a blast-wave type elliptic-fireball expansion [38], with a transverse acceleration profile constrained by experimental light- and strange-hadron spectra. In the same way as the hydrodynamic model described above, the thermal emission rates are taken from complete leading order processes for the QGP. An extensive set of thermal rates from the hadronic sector is employed [39], including contributions from baryons and anti-baryons. “Feed down” photons from short-lived resonance decay (like $\Delta \rightarrow N + \gamma$, etc.) are also included since they are usually not subtracted from the experimental data. This model was later updated with a lattice-QCD based EOS, an ideal hydrodynamical model with non-vanishing initial flow, and a “pseudo-critical” enhancement of the QGP and hadron gas thermal rate around the transition region [22]. The latest calculation [22] is shown in Fig. 1.16, where the “primordial” (prompt) photons are accounted for using either the NLO pQCD calculation or a parameterization of the p+p measurement, both scaled by the number of binary collisions.

Parton-hadron-string dynamics (PHSD) model The full evolution of the collision system from the initial hard scattering to the hadronic phase is described by a non-equilibrium microscopic transport approach [40]. The transport equations for a strongly interacting system are taken from Kadanoff-Baym theory [41–43]. The QGP phase is described by the dynamical quasi-particle model (DQPM) [44], which is tuned to match lattice QCD results. The hadron gas phase is modeled by the hadron-string dynamics (HSD) approach [45, 46], which contains binary meson-meson/baryon interactions, meson-meson and meson-baryon Bremsstrahlung and hadronic decays (including the A_1 and ϕ channel). Recent calculations [47, 48] also incorporate two-to-two vector

meson-nucleon interactions and Δ resonance decay.

1.4.3.1 Direct Photon Puzzle

From Fig. 1.16 one can see that none of the models can describe both the simultaneous observation of a large direct photon yield and a large flow signal to a satisfying quantitative level – this is often referred to as the “direct photon puzzle”. The problem lies in the interplay between the build-up of the collective flow and the cooling as the system expands. While the observed large yield of direct photons favors an early emission scenario where the medium has higher temperature, the large flow indicates that the photons are mainly from later emissions where the flow is sufficiently built up.

Figure 1.16: Comparison of theoretical predictions with the direct photon yield and flow measurements results. Figure adapted from [49].

The puzzle hints at our lack of understanding of direct photon production mechanisms and has triggered additional thinking on other unconventional photon sources like emission from the pre-equilibrium stage, or strong magnetic field effects, etc.

1.4.4 Direct Photon Production as a Function of System Size

Different sources of photons bear a different dependence on collision system size, which can be characterized by the charged particle multiplicity N_{ch} or the Glauber variables N_{part} , N_{coll} , etc... Hadronic decay photons should be proportional to N_{ch} and prompt photons, arising from the initial binary scattering, should scale with N_{coll} . Thermal photons emitted from the medium were originally expected to show a nearly quadratic dependence on N_{ch} because they are generated in the binary collisions of the constituents. However, taking into account that the medium undergoes expansion and cools down rapidly, the power α is much smaller, predicted to be $\sim 4/3$ by Feinberg [50] in 1976. Modern thermal photon calculations using the hydrodynamic approach predict an α around 1.2 to 1.5 [48, 51] depending on the p_T integration range, which will be discussed in more detail in Sec. 5.2.

To provide more insight, a study of the low p_T direct photon production as a function of system size was carried out by the PHENIX experiment. As shown in Fig. 1.17, the integrated direct photon yield from different collision species, centrality classes and beam energies are combined together and plotted against charged particle multiplicity, which is used as a reference for system size. A universal scaling behavior is observed which can be formulated as $dN_\gamma/dy = A \times (dN_{ch}/d\eta)^\alpha$ for A+A systems [52]. The scaling power is around 1.25, although no uncertainties are assigned currently. This simple relation across a wide range of beam energies and system sizes suggests the source of these low p_T direct photons must be similar.

1.5 Scope of this Thesis

This thesis presents a new measurement of direct photon production in Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV using the PHENIX detector. The high statistic dataset taken in 2014 is used, and a new photon reconstruction algorithm is developed in order to analyze it. Benefiting from the abundant statistics, the new measurement achieves very high statistical precision and a broad p_T coverage in the spectrum.

We look into details of the shape of the spectrum in the low p_T regime and extract the T_{eff} with an exponential fit. A more systematic study is done to examine the scaling behavior of the low p_T direct photons and a more precise slope is extracted based on the new direct photon yield results in every 10% centrality class. All these results are compared to the theoretical predictions (of photons from different sources) in order to gain more insight into the true

Figure 1.17: The integrated direct photon yield from $p_T > 1$ GeV/c for various collision systems and collision energies [53][54][55][56][57] as a function of the charged particle multiplicity at mid-rapidity. The black dashed line represents a power law function with a fixed $\alpha = 1.25$ slope. The magenta color band represents the N_{coll} -scaled $p+p$ data at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV and different solid lines correspond to the N_{coll} -scaled pQCD calculations at different energies.

nature of the low p_T direct photons: Are they thermal? Are they dominated by hadron gas emissions? Or are some other sources – which can give us another perspective on the QGP – ultimately responsible?

Chapter 2

Experimental Overview

This chapter will briefly introduce the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) and the PHENIX experiment located at one collision point of RHIC. This chapter also discusses the PHENIX detector focusing on the detector subsystems relevant to the analysis in this thesis, which are the global detectors and central arm spectrometers of PHENIX.

2.1 The Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider

The Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC), located at Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) in the United States, is the world's first and one of the only two currently operating heavy ion colliders [58]. The heavy ion beams are collided at relativistic speed to create the Quark-Gluon Plasma (QGP), which is then identified and studied by analyzing the data taken with detectors located at the RHIC collision points. RHIC provides an unparalleled versatility of collision combinations of fully-stripped ions such as $p + p$, $p + Al$, $p + Au$, $d + Au$, $p + Au$, $Cu + Cu$, $Cu + Au$, $Au + Au$, $U + U$, $Zr + Zr$ and $Ru + Ru$ over an energy range of two orders of magnitude from a few GeV to 500 GeV. It is also the only facility which collides polarized protons to study the proton spin structure.

2.1.1 Accelerator Complex

The chain of accelerations for Au ion beams is shown in Fig. 2.1. The Au ions are produced with a pulsed sputter ion source and then accelerated by the Tandem Van der Graaff accelerator to an energy of 1 MeV/nucleon. At the same time, the heavily charged Au ions travel through a series of stripping foils to peel off the extra atomic electrons. The Au ions exit with a charge of $Q =$

+32 and are then carried to the Booster Synchrotron (Booster), where they are accelerated to an energy of 95 MeV/nucleon. At the exit from the Booster another stripping foil removes 45 electrons, bringing the Au ions to a $Q = +77$ charge state. The ions then enter the Alternating Gradient Synchrotron (AGS). At the AGS, the Au beams are focused into bunches and accelerated to the RHIC injection energy of 10.8 GeV/nucleon. After that, the Au beams are taken down the AGS-to-RHIC (AtR) transfer line and the remaining two electrons are removed. At the end of this line, the Au beams are split into two paths by a switch magnet, one going left to the clockwise RHIC ring, called the “blue ring”, and the other going right to the counter-clockwise RHIC ring, called the “yellow ring”. In the RHIC rings, the counter-rotating beams will receive the final acceleration to 100 GeV/nucleon, after which they are made to collide at the interaction points which are equipped with detectors. (The proton beam starts with a slightly different path. It is first accelerated in the LINear ACcelerator (LINAC), before being injected into the AGS.) The beam can be stored in the ring for several hours while experiments collect data. The storage time depends on the energy of the beam (about 10 hours for an Au beam with energy 100 GeV/nucleon). There are 120 bunches in one fill (store) of the beam, 9 of which are kept empty for the beam dump purposes as shown in Fig. 2.2.

2.1.2 Bunch Crossing and Luminosity

Each RHIC ring has a 3.8 km long circumference and is actually of a sextant shape. The two rings of beam pipe run parallel and cross at six interaction points (IPs), where the beam trajectories are steered by magnets and the bunches cross each other as shown in Fig. 2.3. The crossing angle is very small for Au + Au collisions. The luminous longitudinal bunch area of the Au beam is 15 cm and the interaction length (r.m.s) is 20 cm. In the 2014 RHIC run period for Au + Au collisions at top energy (100 GeV/nucleon), each Au bunch contained $N = 1.6 \times 10^9$ ions.

Once all the parameters of the beam are given, the luminosity can be calculated by the following formula assuming the bunches are of a Gaussian distribution in the transverse direction [61]:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{k_b f_{\text{rev}} N_1 N_2}{2\pi \sqrt{(\sigma_{x_1}^2 + \sigma_{x_2}^2)(\sigma_{y_1}^2 + \sigma_{y_2}^2)}}, \quad (2.1)$$

where $i = 1, 2$ is for blue and yellow beams respectively, and N_i is the number of particles per bunch assuming all bunches in a given beam are of the same

Figure 2.1: Overview of RHIC accelerator complex.

Figure 2.2: Time structure of a RHIC ion bunch. Figure taken from [59].

intensity. k_b is the number of bunches and $f_{\text{rev}} = 78 \text{ kHz}$ is the revolution frequency of the particles. σ_{x_i} and σ_{y_i} represent the transverse size of the beam. The related term $\sqrt{\sigma_{x_1}^2 + \sigma_{x_2}^2}$ can be measured using the Vernier Scan technique [62], where one beam is swept horizontally (along x) across the other while measuring the collision rate as a function of beam displacement.

Figure 2.3: Left: Beam-beam interactions in RHIC. Right: Schematic of the RHIC interaction regions (DX is a dipole magnet). Figure adapted from [60].

A similar procedure can be performed to determine $\sqrt{\sigma_{y_1}^2 + \sigma_{y_2}^2}$ by sweeping the beam vertically (along y) in the scan. The transverse size is usually at the sub-mm level along both the x and y directions [63, 64].

The original design luminosity was $2 \times 10^{26} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ for Au ions and $2 \times 10^{32} \text{ cm}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2}$ for protons. The luminosity increased significantly over the running years (see Fig. 2.4) due to upgrades (e.g. 3D stochastic cooling of bunched ion beams [65]) to the accelerator, and it reached $\mathcal{L} = 50 \times 10^{26} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ during the 2014 Au+Au at $\sqrt{s_{\text{NN}}} = 200 \text{ GeV}$ data-taking period [66].

Not every bunch crossing yields a collision and not every collision yields an event of interest. The rate of a certain event type depends on both the luminosity of the beam \mathcal{L} and the cross section σ of the corresponding process:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \mathcal{L} \cdot \sigma \quad (2.2)$$

In reality, there is often an upper limit on the data taking (event recording) rate of a detector. To make the best use of the limited bandwidth of the data taking, we need trigger detectors to identify if the event of interest (e.g. an inelastic, non-diffractive, hard-scattering, high momentum transfer event) takes place, and then decide if that event will be recorded or not. The main minimum-bias (see Sec. 2.2.2.3) trigger detectors in PHENIX are the Beam Beam Counter (BBC) and Zero Degree Calorimeter (ZDC). More detailed descriptions can be found in Sec. 2.2.2.

The delivered luminosity in the 2014 Au+Au at $\sqrt{s_{\text{NN}}} = 200 \text{ GeV}$ run period was 23.1 nb^{-1} , and about 19 billion events of interest to the work of

this thesis were recorded [67].

Figure 2.4: Integrated nucleon-pair luminosity \mathcal{L}_{NN} for 2001 – 2014 heavy ions physics runs (Au + Au at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV). (The nucleon-pair luminosity is defined as $\mathcal{L}_{NN} = A_1 A_2 \mathcal{L}$, where \mathcal{L} is the luminosity, and A_1 and A_2 are the number of nucleons in the ions of the two beams, respectively.) Figure taken from [68].

2.1.3 The RHIC Experiments

RHIC started running in 2000 and was originally instrumented with 4 experiments, two small experiments – BRAHMS [69] and PHOBOS [70] – and two large experiments – PHENIX [71] and STAR [72]. BRAHMS was at the 2 o’clock of the RHIC ring (IP2) and was designed to measure charged hadrons over a broad range of rapidity and transverse momentum to study the mechanism of relativistic heavy ion interactions. PHOBOS was at 10 o’clock (IP10) and specialized in measuring the bulk properties of the collisions, like the angular distribution of the particles, event fluctuations, etc. PHOBOS completed data taking in 2005 and BRAHMS in 2006.

STAR sits at 6 o’clock (IP6) and was designed to specialize in identifying particle species and measuring their transverse momentum. In this analysis, we used the $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV Au+Au data taken by the PHENIX detector (IP8) in 2014. More details about the PHENIX detector can be found in the next section. PHENIX completed data taking in 2016. The STAR experiment will run until 2021, with the isobar program studying the chiral magnetic effect and the Beam Energy Scan program exploring the QCD phase diagram. A

new heavy ion detector, sPHENIX [73], will be installed in RHIC IP8 around 2023 to use quarkonia and jets to help understand the temperature profile and dynamics of the quark-gluon plasma to a new quantitative level. STAR has proposed a forward upgrade plan [74], aiming to run a dedicated cold QCD program which will produce more precise measurements of initial state effects like the partonic structure of nucleons or nuclei at the same time. After that, RHIC will be converted into the future Electron-Ion Collider [75].

2.2 The PHENIX Experiment

PHENIX, the Pioneering High Energy Nuclear Interaction eXperiment [71], is an exploratory experiment for the investigation of high energy collisions of heavy ions and protons with the primary goal of detecting the QGP and characterizing its physics properties. The detector was designed to specialize in measuring photons, leptons and hadrons. It uses global detectors to characterize the collisions, a pair of central spectrometers at mid-rapidity to measure electrons, hadrons and photons, and a pair of forward spectrometers to measure muons. A schematic view of the PHENIX detector is shown in Fig. 2.5. This analysis mainly utilized the global detectors and central arm spectrometers, and more details about the muon spectrometers can be found in [76].

A summary of the various PHENIX global and central arm subsystems along with their purpose is presented in Table. 2.1.

2.2.1 The PHENIX Coordinate System

All the PHENIX subsystems share one global coordinate system. Fig. 2.6 shows the global coordinate system in cartesian coordinates. The z axis is along the beam direction and pointing to the north (positive z). The x axis points from east to west and the interaction point is at the coordinate origin $(0,0,0)$. Because of the overall detector geometry, it's usually more convenient to use either cylindrical or spherical coordinates. $\phi = 0$ goes along the x axis ranging from $-\frac{1}{2}\pi$ to $+\frac{3}{2}\pi$, and, in spherical coordinates, $\theta = 0$ goes along the z axis ranging from 0 to π . θ is often used interchangeably with pseudorapidity η , which is defined as follows:

$$\eta = -\ln \left[\tan \left(\frac{\theta}{2} \right) \right] \quad (2.3)$$

The relationship between θ and η is also illustrated in Fig. 2.7, where $\eta = 0$ is in the transverse plane, $\eta = +\infty$ is along the positive z axis (forward) and

Subsystem	$\Delta\eta$	$\Delta\phi$	Purpose and Features	
Global detectors				
Beam-beam counters (BBC)	$3.1 < \eta < 3.9$	360°	Minimum bias trigger Start timing Fast vertex Reaction plane determination	
Zero-degree Calorimeter (ZDC)	$ \eta > 6.9$	360°	Minimum-bias trigger	
Central Arm Spectrometers				
Tracking	Central Magnet	$ \eta < 0.35$	360°	Up to 1.15T·m
	Drift Chambers (DC)	$ \eta < 0.35$	$2 \times 90^\circ$	Good momentum and mass resolution ($\Delta m/m = 0.4\%$ at $m = 1$ GeV)
	Pad Chambers (PC)	$ \eta < 0.35$	$2 \times 90^\circ$	Pattern recognition tracking in non-bend direction
	Time Expansion Chamber (TEC)	$ \eta < 0.35$	90°	Pattern recognition dE/dx
	Ring Imaging Cerenkov Detector (RICH)	$ \eta < 0.35$	$2 \times 90^\circ$	Electron identification
PID	Aerogel Detector (AGEL)	$0 < \eta < 0.35$	45°	High p_T Hadron identification
	Time-of-flight (TOF)	$ \eta < 0.35$	45°	Hadron identification ($\sigma < 100$ ps, good e^\pm/π^\pm separation at $p_T < 0.35$ GeV/c, K^\pm/π^\pm separation up to 2.4 GeV/c)
EM calorimeter	Lead-Scintillator (PbSc)		$90+45^\circ$	Energy measurement of electrons and photons Fine granularity for photon – π^0 separation
	Lead-Glass (PbGl)	$ \eta < 0.35$	45°	Electron/photon identification by shower shape (good e^\pm/π^\pm separation at $p > 1$ GeV/c)

Table 2.1: Summary of the PHENIX global and central arm subsystems.

Figure 2.5: The PHENIX detector layout in the 2012 run (the central arm detectors are the same until the last 2016 run). The upper panel shows the beam view where the two central arms and central magnet can be seen. The lower panel shows the side view where the two muon arms and the two muon magnets can be seen.

$\eta = -\infty$ is along the negative z axis (backward). η can also be written as a

function of the particle three-momentum \mathbf{p} :

$$\eta = -\frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{|\mathbf{p}| + p_L}{|\mathbf{p}| - p_L} \right) = \operatorname{arctanh} \left(\frac{p_L}{|\mathbf{p}|} \right) \quad (2.4)$$

where p_L is the component of the momentum along the beam direction. In the relativistic limit (where the mass of the particle is negligible), pseudorapidity converges to the definition of rapidity:

$$y = -\frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{E + p_L}{E - p_L} \right) \quad (2.5)$$

Pseudorapidity and rapidity are useful quantities because the rapidity difference between two particles is invariant under Lorentz boosts along the z axis.

Figure 2.6: The PHENIX global coordinate system.

2.2.2 Global Detectors

A few detector subsystems are implemented in the forward and backward rapidity range to measure the global properties of collisions. They determine the start time of a collision, measure the vertex along the beam axis, provide the trigger for data taking, and characterize the events into different centrality classes according to the particle multiplicity. In this section, we will introduce

Figure 2.7: Relationship between polar angle θ and pseudorapidity η ($\theta = 90^\circ$ is in the transverse plane). Figure taken from Wikipedia.

the Beam Beam Counter (BBC) and Zero Degree Calorimeter (ZDC), followed by a brief introduction on the minimum bias trigger and the definition of centrality.

2.2.2.1 Beam Beam Counter

The Beam Beam Counter (BBC) [77] is designed to provide a trigger signal, a collision vertex along the beam axis, and a precise start time for the collision [78], which is essential for the time-of-flight measurements.

Two identical BBCs are installed on both sides of the interaction point along the beam at $z = \pm 1.44m$. As shown in Fig. 2.8, one BBC consists of 64 tubes assembled in a honeycomb shape, covering $3.1 < |\eta| < 3.9$ in the θ direction and full 2π coverage in the ϕ direction. Each tube is a Cherenkov counter containing a 30 mm long fused quartz radiator followed by a photomultiplier tube (PMT) to measure the Cherenkov light signal. The Cherenkov emission angle θ_c for relativistic particles in the fused quartz is about 45° and most of the emitted Cherenkov light is internally reflected and transferred within the quartz to the PMT. Because of the strong residual magnetic field around the physical location of the BBC (~ 0.3 T), the PMT used for the BBC is designed and tested to be operational in a magnetic field up to 0.3 T.

Each BBC tube is connected to one read out channel. The signal gives both the total number of charged particles that hit the tube and also the hit time of the leading particle. To optimize the timing resolution of each element, the length of the radiator is carefully chosen to balance the two following effects:

- For a radiator with a shorter length, the Cherenkov light produced at the front and the end of the radiator will arrive to the PMTs at a similar

Figure 2.8: Left: Assembly of 64 BBC tubes. Middle: One BBC tube. Right: Schematic of 64 BBC channels on one side (north).

time. A shorter length means a narrower spread of photon arrival time, which then benefits the timing resolution.

- Because the amount of emitted Cherenkov light is proportional to the length the particle travels inside the radiator, a longer length means more Cherenkov light is produced and hence a better signal-to-noise ratio in the detector.

A 30 mm length is chosen at the end, and an intrinsic timing resolution of $\sigma_t \sim 50$ ps is achieved for a single BBC counter.

The start time t_0 can be calculated from the average arrival time of the hits on the north and the south side:

$$t_0 = \frac{t_N + t_S}{2} - \frac{L}{c} \quad (2.6)$$

where c is the speed of light and L is the distance from the interaction point to the BBC (1.44 m).

The collision vertex along the beam axis, z_{vtx} , can be calculated from the difference in the arrival times of the hits on the north t_N and south side t_S :

$$z_{vtx} = c \times \frac{t_N - t_S}{2} \quad (2.7)$$

The arrival time on either side is calculated by extracting the peak mean value of the timing distribution from all the PMTs with a valid timing signal [79]. In the case of low multiplicity events where there is not enough fired PMTs to extract the peak mean from a distribution, the arrival times of the leading particles are used instead. Both the t_0 and the z_{vtx} resolutions depend on the event multiplicity. The z_{vtx} resolution is about 0.3 cm for central Au + Au collisions and can be > 1 cm in peripheral Au + Au collisions or smaller

collision systems. More details can be found in the Sec. 4.6.2.

2.2.2.2 Zero Degree Calorimeter

The Zero Degree Calorimeters (ZDCs) [80, 81] are used to monitor the beam luminosity at the different interaction points. Identical copies of ZDCs are installed around all four experiments at RHIC. The ZDCs also play an important role in the trigger system and can be combined with the BBC for event characterization purposes.

The ZDCs are hadronic calorimeters designed to measure the evaporation neutrons [82] produced during the interaction of two nuclei in a very narrow cone around the beam ($\theta < 2$ mrad). The narrow cone size is determined by the extremely small transverse momentum (arising from the Fermi motion inside the nucleus) relative to longitudinal momentum (~ 100 GeV/c). They are placed on both the south and the north side and are 18 m away from the interaction point. At that location, the evaporation neutrons are supposed to be within 3.6 cm from the beam line, while the charged particles are deflected away by the DX dipole magnet, as shown in Fig. 2.9.

The ZDC is a sampling type calorimeter and consists of three modules along the beam direction (no transverse segmentation). Fig. 2.10 illustrates the mechanical design of one ZDC module. Each module is $10 \text{ cm} \times 13.6 \text{ cm}$ in the transverse direction. It has 27 layers of 5mm Tungsten alloy plates as the absorber interleaved with the PMMA based [83] optical fiber layers as the active area. This corresponds to about $2 \lambda_I$ (nuclear interaction length) and about $50 X_0$ (radiation length) for each module. The incoming neutrons undergo a hadronic cascade and convert their energy into the production of secondary particles. As those secondary particles pass through the optical fiber, they produce Cherenkov light which is collected by a single PMT at the end. The refractive index of PMMA is $n = 1.49$, which means the Cherenkov emission angle is $\theta_c \approx 45^\circ$ for $\beta \approx 1$ particles (100 GeV neutrons). The optical fiber used here can transmit light within 30° to the fiber direction. To have more light transferred inside the fiber by internal reflection, the module is tilted by 45° to the beam. A by-product of placing the module at such an angle to the beam is that the signal from background particles is suppressed.

As can be seen in Fig. 2.10, the fiber ribbons are trimmed to different lengths depending on their longitudinal position in the module. This is to compensate for the different arrival times of the hadronic shower at different depths, especially at the front and the end of the module. Three fiber ribbons are randomly selected and connected to an external LED flasher for gain monitoring purposes.

The three module together gave a 19% energy resolution at the test beam

Figure 2.9: Top: Beam view of the deflection of different particles at the ZDC location (18 m). Bottom: Side view of the interaction region and ZDC. Colored lines indicates the trajectories of different particles. Figure taken from [81].

using 100 GeV protons. The timing resolution is about 120 ps [84], which corresponds to a ~ 2.5 cm z vertex resolution based on Eq. 2.7.

2.2.2.3 Minimum Bias Trigger

As mentioned in Sec. 2.1.2, not every bunch crossing yields an event of interest. The detectors with fast response (trigger detectors) are used to quickly examine the event topology, based on which a decision is made on whether to record a certain event or not. There are different triggers depending on what events or processes are of interest. One of the most basic trigger types is to select all the inelastic nucleus-nucleus collisions – this is called the minimum bias (MB) trigger. In PHENIX, the minimum bias trigger [85] is constructed by:

- A coincidence of signals from the North and South BBCs (BBCN and BBCS), with a threshold set on number of fired BBC tubes.
- A coincidence of signals from the North and South ZDCs (ZDCN and

Figure 2.10: Left: Side view of the ZDC Tungsten module (beam direction indicated by the red arrow). Right: Front view (along the beam) of the module. Dimensions are in units of mm. Figure taken from [81].

ZDCS), with a threshold set on the deposited energy.

Requiring a ZDC coincidence helps reject the collision background such as particles hitting the magnet and bouncing back to the BBC. Limited by the finite acceptance of the trigger detectors, the minimum bias trigger efficiency is 93% for Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV, meaning only 93% of the inelastic Au + Au collisions are triggered. This trigger efficiency is evaluated by a PHENIX detector simulation with the HIJING event generator [86].

2.2.2.4 Centrality Definition and Determination

The events selected by the minimum bias trigger described above are classified into different centrality classes according to the charged particle multiplicity seen by the trigger detector BBC (N_{ch}^{BBC}). To determine the centrality class of a given event, we first measure the dN_{evt}/dN_{ch}^{BBC} distribution and then normalize

the total integral to the percentage of the total inelastic cross section triggered by BBC (i.e. 93% for Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{\text{NN}}} = 200$ GeV). The events are then mapped to 0 - 93% centrality from highest to lowest $N_{\text{ch}}^{\text{BBC}}$. By definition, equally wide centrality classes contain the same number of events. Given that particle multiplicity is monotonically related to the impact parameter b both at mid and forward rapidity, the centrality classes now provide us a natural ranking of events by the impact parameter b . Events with small centrality correspond to small impact parameter, meaning the collision is more head on (often referred to as central collisions). Events with large centrality correspond to large impact parameter, meaning two nuclei barely touch each other (often referred as peripheral collisions). Fig. 2.11 illustrates how centrality is defined from the charged particle multiplicity and how each centrality class is mapped to the collision geometry quantities such as impact parameter b and number of participants N_{part} which are calculated from the Glauber model [29].

2.2.3 Charged Particle Tracking System

The charged particle tracking system in the central arm mainly consists of three parts: the Central Arm Magnet (CM) [87], the Drift Chambers (DC) [88] and three sets of Pad Chambers (PC) [89]. The DC provides high resolution p_T measurements and also participates in the pattern recognition at high particle track densities by providing position information that is used to link tracks through the various PHENIX detector subsystems. The PC provides three-dimensional space points for the charged tracks and determines p_z/p_T . The DC along with PC1 form the inner tracking system, while PC2 and PC3 form the outer trackers.

2.2.3.1 Central Arm Magnet

Momentum measurement first requires a magnetic field to bend the trajectory of the outgoing charged particles. This field is supplied by the Central Arm Magnet (CM) for the central arm tracking system. The CM comprises two sets of concentric coils (inner and outer) which provide an axially symmetric field primarily parallel to the beam axis. Charged particles in the central arm acceptance will be bent in the transverse plane and the bending angle will be measured by the Drift Chamber (DC) to determine the particle momentum. The inner and outer coils can be run with the fields in adding (the “++” or “--” configuration) or bucking (“+-” configuration) mode. Fig. 2.12 shows the magnetic field lines for the two field configurations.

In the “++” configuration, the current in the inner and outer coils runs in the same direction and provides a strong magnetic field up to 200 cm, the

Figure 2.11: Schematic of the relationship between charged particle multiplicity (N_{ch}) and Glauber model calculated collision geometry quantities (b , N_{part}). The values shown are just illustrative rather than actual measurements. Figure taken from [29].

radius of the DC. At larger radii, the magnetic field drops rapidly and remains minimal in order to reduce the influence of the magnetic field on several detector components like the photomultiplier tubes, as shown by the red curve in Fig. 2.13. The minimal field strength in the tracking region also ensures that tracks go almost straight through the DC volume for easier pattern recognition in a high multiplicity environment. In the “+” configuration, the current in the inner and outer coils runs in opposite directions. As a result, the magnetic field is nearly zero in the range $0 < R < 50$ cm. The field integral $\int B dl$ at $z \sim 0$ is 1.5 T·m for the “++” configuration and 0.43 T·m for the “+-” configuration. At the center close to the beam axis, the field lines uniformly point along the beam direction z . However, the residual magnetic field above the DC distance is highly non-uniform and has a significant r component at large z .

Figure 2.12: Magnetic field lines in the PHENIX detector, for the two central magnet coils operated in the ++ (left) and +- (right) mode. Red arrows indicate the field direction.

Figure 2.13: Total field strength B_{tot} vs radial distance r for different field configurations.

2.2.3.2 Drift Chambers

The PHENIX drift chamber (DC) is a multi-wire gaseous detector located at a radial distance of $2.02 < R < 2.48$ m. There is one cylindrically shaped chamber on each arm, which are mirror copies of each other. They cover 90° in azimuthal direction and 2 m along the z direction. Each DC measures the trajectories of charged particles in the $r - \phi$ plane to determine their charge

and transverse momentum p_T .

The DC volume is defined by a titanium frame shown in Fig. 2.14. Each chamber is divided into 20 equal sectors covering 4.5° in ϕ , which is often referred to as a keystone. There are six types of wire modules stacked radially in each keystone: X1, U1, V1, X2, U2 and V2. One wire module contains 4 sense (anode) and 4 cathode planes forming cells with a 2 – 2.5 cm drift space in the ϕ direction. Fig. 2.15 shows the layout of the wires in a drift cell and the electric field lines around them. The anode wires are separated by Potential (P) wires and surrounded by Gate (G) and Back (B) wires [90]. P wires form a strong electric field and separate sensitive regions of individual anode wires. G wires limit the track sample length to roughly 3 mm and terminate unwanted drift lines. This minimizes the time spread of drifting electrons from a single track and thereby decreases the pulse width. The B wire has a rather low potential and terminates most of the drift lines from its side, essentially limiting the left – right ambiguity to a region of ± 2 mm. Once there is a charged particle passing through the cell, the ionized electrons will drift to the anode wires along the field lines. The ionization positions of the charged tracks can hence be calculated via the drift time and the known drift velocity ($\sim 50 \mu\text{m/ns}$). The chambers are filled with 50% Argon and 50% Ethane. Such a gas mixture is chosen due to its stable drift velocity at an electric field of $E \sim 1 \text{ kV/cm}$, high gain (on the order of 10^4) and low diffusion coefficient.

The alignment of different wire modules is shown in Fig. 2.16. The X1 and X2 wires are aligned parallel to the beam pipe to perform precise track measurements in the $r - \phi$ plane. The U and V wires have stereo angles of about 6° relative to the X wires and can measure the z coordinate of the track. The magnitude of the stereo angle was chosen to minimize track ambiguities by matching to the z resolution of the pad chambers.

To satisfy the requirement of efficient track recognition for up to 500 tracks, each sense wire is separated in the center into two halves by a $100 \mu\text{m}$ thick kapton strip and then read out independently. In total, the DC system contains roughly 6500 anode wires and thereby about 13000 readout channels. The single wire efficiency is on the order of 90-95%.

2.2.3.3 Pad Chambers

The PHENIX Pad Chambers (PC) are multiwire proportional chambers. There are three layers of PC in the central arm tracking system. The first layer (PC1) is mounted on the back of the DC in both arms. The second layer (PC2) is located after the Ring Imaging Cherenkov Detector (RICH) but only installed in the west arm. The third layer (PC3) lies right in front of the EMCal in

Figure 2.14: Construction of the DC frame.

Figure 2.15: Left: Layout of the anode and cathode planes in a drift cell. Right: Drift field lines around a track in simulation.

both arms. Fig 2.17 shows the coverage and the relative radial location of the

Figure 2.16: Left: Cut-away $r - \phi$ view of the wire layout within one keystone of the drift chamber. Right: The relative orientation of the U, V and X wire layers.

PCs.

Figure 2.17: Schematic view of PC1, PC2 and PC3 in the central arm.

PC1 is essential to determine the three momentum of the charged particles

by providing the z coordinate at the exit of the DC. Moreover, the DC and PC1 information gives the direction of the track outside the magnetic field. Due to the near-zero magnetic field after the DC, the trajectory of the charged particles is almost straight until the end of the central arm detector system – the electromagnetic calorimeter (EMCal). This straight line track projection through the RICH is used to determine the Cherenkov light angle to identify if the charge particles are electrons or hadrons (see Sec. 2.2.5.3).

PC2 and PC3 are critical for pattern recognition. The track projection together with PC2 and PC3 information are needed to resolve ambiguities in the outer detectors – where about 30% of the particles striking the EMCal are produced by either secondary interactions or particle decays outside the aperture of the DC and PC1.

Each PC contains a single plane of wires inside a gas volume bounded by two cathode planes, as shown in Fig. 2.18. One cathode plane is copper and the other is segmented into an array of pixels. Signals from pixels are routed outside the gas volume, where they are amplified and discriminated by the Read Out Cards (ROCs).

Figure 2.18: The cut view of a pad chamber.

The pixels are of a special design to ensure a high efficiency and reliable hit information with a relatively small number of readout channels. The designed readout pattern is illustrated in Fig. 2.19. Three pixels form a cell, and an avalanche must be sensed by all three pixels to form a valid hit in the cell. Such a triple coincidence largely reduces the false hits. Nine interleaved pixels are then connected together and read out by one common channel. The three pixels in a cell are always connected to different but neighboring channels so that each cell is defined by its unique channel triplet. This design saves a factor of nine readout channels compared to reading out each pixel individually.

For PC1, the design goal for the position resolution is about 4 mm. To

Figure 2.19: Left: The nine pixels forming one pad in the PC. Right: The interleaved pad design.

achieve this, anode wire spacing was chosen to be 8 mm and each cell has an area of $8.4 \times 8.4 \text{ mm}^2$. With this configuration, a $\pm 1.7 \text{ mm}$ position resolution along the z direction is reached. To maintain the same angular resolution for PC2 and PC3, the PC3 cells are 4 times larger since the radial position of PC3 is twice as large as the radial position of PC1. The total number of electronic channels in the PC system is 172,800.

2.2.3.4 Track Reconstruction

Fig. 2.20 shows a schematic view of how the charged particle trajectory appears in the transverse $r - \phi$ plane, which is often referred to as the bending plane since the magnetic field is uniform along the z direction (B_z) at small z . At larger z , the magnetic field starts to partially point towards the radial direction (B_r). This bends the charged particle in the $r - z$ plane, which is often referred to as the non-bending plane since B_r is much smaller compared to B_z . Another important feature is that the track no longer bends in or after the DC active volume, because the magnetic field quickly drops to near zero before the DC. The residual field within the DC volume is supposed to give only a small deflection ($< 1^\circ$) in the bending plane, and it is therefore safe to assume a straight track model within the DC volume. The inclination/bending angle α is defined as the angle of the track candidate with respect to an infinite momentum (i.e. straight) track having the same intersection point with the reference circle (220 cm) in the bending plane.

The track reconstruction within the DC is performed using a combinatorial

Hough transform (CHT) technique [91], as shown in Fig. 2.21. The key to this technique is to map the X1 and X2 hits pair-wise into a 2D space defined by the azimuthal angle at the intersection of the track with the reference radius, ϕ , and bending angle α . A straight line in the $x - y$ phase space will be represented by a single point in the $\phi - \alpha$ phase space. Hence the pairs of hits within the same track will form a local maxima in the mapped $\phi - \alpha$ space. These hits are then associated with the initial track candidate. A perfect track will deposit 6 hits in both the X1 and X2 wires. To ensure a good quality of reconstructed tracks (i.e. to have a reasonable momentum resolution and minimized false reconstruction) while keeping a good single track efficiency, tracks are considered valid only if there are a total of at least 8 X1 and X2 hits associated to them.

To reconstruct the track inside the DC volume in the non-bending $r - z$ plane, a straight line projection is done towards the PC1 in the $r - \phi$ plane. Once an unambiguous PC1 hit is found (with a maximum distance of 2 cm between the track projection point and the PC1 hit position in the $r - \phi$ plane), the track vector will be approximately along a straight line connecting the PC1 hit z position and the event vertex z coordinate. If there are hits within 5cm of the intersection point with the DC UV wires in the $r - z$ plane, UV hits will then be associated to the track.

Each reconstructed track is assigned a track quality value, Q_{track} , a 6-bit variable, based on the hit information of the X and UV wires in the DC and the associated PC1 hit.

$$Q_{track} = A \times 2^0 + B \times 2^1 + C \times 2^2 + D \times 2^3 + E \times 2^4 + F \times 2^5 \quad (2.8)$$

where A, B, C, D, E, F are binaries defined as follows:

- $A = 1$ if the X1 plane is used.
- $B = 1$ if the X2 plane is used.
- $C = 1$ if there are hits in the UV plane.
- $D = 1$ if there are unique hits in the UV plane.
- $E = 1$ if there are hits in PC1.
- $F = 1$ if there are unique hits in PC1.

A complete list of the track quality values is shown in Tab. 2.2. In this analysis, we use tracks with $Q_{track} = 63$ (highest quality, i.e. requiring hits in X1 and X2, unique PC1 and UV hits), 51 (i.e. requiring hits in X1 and X2, a unique PC1 hit, and no matching UV hit), and 31 (i.e., requiring hits in X1 and X2, a unique UV hit, and an ambiguous PC1 hit).

Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F	Quality, Q_{track}
$PC1^{found}_{unique}$ & UV^{found}_{unique}	1	0	1	1	1	1	61
	0	1	1	1	1	1	62
	1	1	1	1	1	1	63
$PC1^{found}_{unique}$ & no UV	1	0	0	0	1	1	49
	0	1	0	0	1	1	50
	1	1	0	0	1	1	51
$PC1^{found}_{ambiguous}$ & UV^{found}_{unique}	1	0	1	1	1	0	29
	0	1	1	1	1	0	30
	1	1	1	1	1	0	31
$PC1^{found}_{ambiguous}$ & UV^{found}	1	0	1	0	1	0	21
	0	1	1	0	1	0	22
	1	1	1	0	1	0	23
$PC1^{found}_{ambiguous}$ & no UV	1	0	0	0	1	0	17
	0	1	0	0	1	0	18
	1	1	0	0	1	0	19

Table 2.2: Summary of the DC and PC1 track quality.

Figure 2.20: Right: The track reconstruction in the transverse/bending $r - \phi$ ($x - y$) plane. X1 and X2 represent the X1 and X2 layers of the drift chamber; ϕ_0 describes the direction of the track at the vertex; ϕ describes the position of the track at the DC; and α describes the direction of the track in the DC. Left: The track reconstruction in the longitudinal/non-bending $r - z$ plane. θ_0 describes the direction of the track at the vertex; θ describes the position of the track at the DC; β and δ describe the direction of the track at the DC.

2.2.3.5 Momentum Determination and the Track Model

The tracking system only provides three observables: bending angle α , azimuthal angle ϕ_{DC} and the z position z_{DC} where the track hit the DC. However, these three observables are not enough to fix the track trajectory. The standard track reconstruction algorithm also assumes every track originates from the event vertex. With this assumption, the trajectory and momentum of the charged track can be fully determined.

α is proportional to the field integral from the interaction point up to the DC,

$$\alpha \simeq \frac{K}{p_T} \quad , \quad (2.9)$$

where K is the total field integral and p_T is the transverse momentum of the particle.

Because the magnetic field is quite complicated, one can not solve for the momentum of the particle analytically. Instead, a non-linear grid interpolation technique is used to calculate the momentum [92]. The grid is a four dimensional look-up table on the following variables: the total track momentum (p),

Figure 2.21: The left panel shows simulated hits from a central Au + Au collision for a small physical region of the drift chamber. The right panel shows the Hough transform feature space for this region. Tracks appear as peaks in this plot.

the radius (r) from the beam axis, the theta angle (θ_0) of the track and the position z of the collision vertex. The look-up table is generated by swimming particles with different p , z and θ_0 through the magnetic field map and integrating numerically along the trajectory until r to obtain the field integral $f(p, r, \theta_0, z)$ for different grid points. For any (p, r, θ_0, z) not on the field-integral grid, a four-dimensional polynomial interpolation will be used to determine $f(p, r, \theta_0, z)$.

First, an initial estimate of the charge and momentum is made based on α . θ is the initial guess for θ_0 . After that, $f(p, r, \theta_0, z)$ is calculated for each DC hit and a linear fit is performed in ϕ versus $f(p, r, \theta_0, z)$. The slope of the fit is q/p and the intercept is ϕ_0 :

$$\phi = \phi_0 + q \frac{f(p, r, \theta_0, z)}{p} \quad (2.10)$$

This new p is then used as the starting point for another iteration and a similar fit is performed to obtain a better set of p and ϕ_0 values. Often after less than four iterations, the fits will converge to a stable result [79].

The initial polar angle θ_0 is also determined by an iterative procedure using the equation $\theta = \theta_0 + \delta(p, r = R, \theta_0, z) - g(p, r = R, \theta_0, z)/p$, where δ is the bending angle in the $r - z$ plane.

The momentum resolution of the central arm tracking system is expressed

in Eq. 2.11. The first term is due to multiple scattering and the second term is due to the intrinsic DC resolution. Multiple scattering dominates the resolution at very low momenta, while the detector resolution dominates at higher momenta. In addition, the momentum resolution is not multiplicity dependent based on a central-central Au+Au HIJING simulation study.

$$\frac{\sigma_p}{p} = 0.7\% \oplus 1\%p \text{ (GeV/c)} \quad (2.11)$$

2.2.4 Calorimetry

As the tracking system can only measure charged particles, neutral particles are usually measured by the calorimeters, where the energy of the particles is measured via total absorption in the detector material. In general, there are two types of calorimeters – electromagnetic calorimeter and hadronic calorimeter – depending on whether the calorimeter is designed to measure electrons/photons or hadrons. PHENIX is equipped with an electromagnetic calorimeter in the central arm to identify and measure photons, electrons, and neutral pions (via $\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma + \gamma$) in mid-rapidity.

2.2.4.1 Electromagnetic Calorimeter

The primary goal of the electromagnetic calorimeter (EMCal) [93] in PHENIX is to identify electrons and photons, and measure their energy and position of impact on the surface of the EMCal. The EMCal also gives time-of-flight information for incident particles which helps with the particle identification (details can be found in [79]). The calorimeter converts the energy of incident electrons/photons into a cascade of secondary particles, referred to as an electromagnetic shower, through pair production and bremsstrahlung. In PHENIX, two types of calorimeters are used: lead-scintillator (PbSc) and lead-glass (PbGl). PbSc is a sandwich sampling detector, also called a Shashlik type calorimeter [94]. PbGl is a homogenous, Cherenkov type detector.

The largest single mechanical unit of the EMCal is a sector. There are 8 sectors in total in the central arm. The sectors sit around 500 cm away in the radial direction. Each sector has a cross section of 200 cm ($\approx 45^\circ$ coverage in the azimuthal angle ϕ) \times 400 cm ($\approx \pm 0.35$ coverage in η) and about 40 cm deep. All the sectors are positioned in such a way that photons coming from the interaction point hit the center perpendicularly. For neutral particles, the incident angle with respect to the normal ranges from 0° to 20° .

There are 6 sectors of the PbSc, covering the whole west arm (clockwise: the W0, W1, W2, and W3 sectors) and the top half of the east arm (clockwise: the E3 and E2 sectors). There are 2 sectors of the PbGl, covering the bottom

half of the east arm (clockwise: the East 1 and East 0 sectors). Both the PbSc and the PbGl are designed to have very fine lateral segmentation and accurate energy measurement in a wide range (MeV to 80 GeV). The basic lateral segment unit is called the tower. A tower has a size of about 5.5 cm \times 5.5 cm for the PbSc and 4 cm \times 4 cm for the PbGl. The tower size corresponds to about one Molière radius, which means on average $\sim 90\%$ of the electromagnetic shower is contained in one tower.

A summary of the basic parameters can be found in Tab. 2.3. The two types of calorimeters have different response characteristics and they have different strengths and weaknesses. For example, the PbGl has better granularity and energy resolution, but the the PbSc has better linearity and timing and the response to hadrons is better understood.

Electromagnetic Calorimeters	PbSc	PbGl
Type	Shashlik	Cerenkov
Radiation length (X_0) [mm]	21	28
Molière radius [mm]	43	36.8
Cross section of a tower [mm ²]	55.35 \times 55.35	40 \times 40
Depth [mm] ($[X_0]$)	375 (18)	400 (14.4)
$\Delta\eta \times \Delta\phi$ of a tower	0.011 \times 0.011	0.008 \times 0.008
Number of sectors	6	2
Number of towers	15552	9216

Table 2.3: Summary of the parameters of the Electromagnetic Calorimeters (EMCal) at PHENIX. The calorimeter consists of two types of detectors: lead-scintillator (PbSc) and lead-glass (PbGl).

2.2.4.2 Lead-Scintillator Calorimeter

Each lead-scintillator calorimeter (PbSc) [95] tower contains 66 sample cells. In each cell, there is first a Pb absorber layer (0.15 cm) to generate electromagnetic showers. The shower then enters the scintillator layer (0.4 cm) and generates flashes of light. The produced light is collected by the wavelength-shifting fibers woven through all layers and is taken to the photomultipliers at the back end of each tower. Towers are optically isolated from each other by Al plates around each tower.

4 towers (2 \times 2) are mechanically grouped together into a single-structure entity called a module (shown in Fig. 2.22). 36 modules (6 \times 6) are attached to a backbone and held together by welded stainless steel skins on the outside to form a rigid structure called a supermodule. 18 supermodules (6 \times 3) then

form a sector. In total there are 15552 channels for the PbSc calorimeter. The purpose behind the chosen grouping is to create a building block with a minimum of supporting components which can be easily assembled on a production line.

Figure 2.22: Interior view of the Lead-Scintillator Calorimeter (PbSc) module showing a stack of scintillator and lead plates, wavelength shifting fiber readout and leaky fiber inserted in the center hole.

2.2.4.3 Lead-Glass Calorimeter

The lead-glass calorimeter (PbGl) array comprises 9216 elements of a system previously used in the WA98 experiment [96, 97] at CERN. The PbGl is a homogenous detector, meaning the electromagnetic shower is both initiated and detected in a single medium, in our case lead-loaded glass crystal. The crystal is made from 55% PbO and 45% SiO₂, and it is a Cherenkov radiator with a refraction index $n = 1.648$. The electron-positron pairs in the shower generate Cherenkov light, and the Cherenkov light propagates to the photomultipliers at the end of the tower by internal reflection. Each tower is wrapped in reflecting mylar foil and a shrink tube.

24 towers (6×4) are glued together with carbon fiber and epoxy resin to form a self-supporting module (shown in Fig. 2.23). The LED in front of each module creates reference light for gain monitoring. Each sector contains 192 modules (16×12). In total there are 9216 channels for the PbGl calorimeter.

Figure 2.23: Interior view of the Lead-Glass Calorimeter (PbGl) module.

2.2.4.4 Energy and Position Resolution from the Test Beam

The performance of the PbSc and PbGl calorimeters are studied extensively with the test beam (a controlled beam environment) [98, 99]. The PbSc calorimeter was tested with particle beams from U70 (IHEP, Protvino), from the AGS (BNL) and finally from the SPS (CERN). The PbGl calorimeter was tested at the AGS (BNL) and SPS (CERN). An electron/positron beam was used to generate electromagnetic showers in the calorimeter. A few hadron beams (pions and protons) were also used to test the calorimeter response to hadrons. A broad range of beam energies was used during the test beam and the incident angle with respect to the detector was varied to study the response in different conditions. The test beam results provide essential information for the calibration and on the shower topology, which plays a central role in the position measurement, the energy measurement, the timing measurement and photon identification (hadron rejection) within the calorimeter. We will show the energy and position resolutions based on the test beam results first and then elaborate in more detail on how the position and energy are measured in the following sections.

PbSc

- energy resolution

$$\frac{\sigma(E)}{E} = \frac{6.1\%}{\sqrt{E} [\text{GeV}]} + 1.2\% \quad (2.12)$$

$$= \frac{8.1\%}{\sqrt{E} [\text{GeV}]} \oplus 2.1\%^* \quad (2.13)$$

- position resolution

$$\frac{\sigma_x(E, 0^\circ)}{E} = \frac{5.9 \text{ mm}}{\sqrt{E} [\text{GeV}]} + 1.6 \text{ mm} \quad (2.14)$$

$$\sigma_x(E, \theta) = \sigma_x(E, 0^\circ) \oplus (d \cdot \sin \theta) \quad (2.15)$$

where θ is the impact angle, which is defined as the angle between an incident particle and the axis normal to the surface of the calorimeter. $d = 0.8X_0$, where X_0 is the radiation length in the calorimeter module (22 mm for PbSc, see Tab. 2.3).

PbGl

- energy resolution

$$\frac{\sigma(E)}{E} = \frac{5.9\%}{\sqrt{E} [\text{GeV}]} \oplus 0.8\% \quad (2.16)$$

- position resolution

$$\frac{\sigma_x(E)}{E} = \frac{8.4 \text{ mm}}{\sqrt{E} [\text{GeV}]} \oplus 0.2 \text{ mm} \quad (2.17)$$

The energy resolution for both the PbSc and PbGl follows a similar form:

$$\frac{\sigma}{E} = \frac{a}{\sqrt{E}} \oplus b \quad (2.18)$$

The first term is usually referred to as the stochastic term, which arises from the intrinsic statistical shower fluctuations. The number of secondary particles produced in the electromagnetic shower N is proportional to the total energy E of the incoming particle, hence the fluctuation on the E would be \sqrt{E} . The second term is a constant term, which is usually due to inhomogeneities (hardware or calibration), non-linearities of the readout electronics, etc. The energy resolution for both the PbSc and PbGl calorimeters is shown in Fig. 2.24.

Figure 2.24: Energy resolution of the PbSc calorimeter (left) and PbGl calorimeter (right) from the test beam study. In both cases, an electron (positron) beam is used as the primary beam to generate an electromagnetic shower in the calorimeter. Figure taken from [93].

2.2.4.5 Electromagnetic Shower Profile in PbSc

One of the most important test beam studies is the parameterization of the shower shape [100], namely the spatial distribution of the energy deposited in different towers, as a function of the distance between the i th tower and the center of gravity (CG) of the shower (r_{CG}) in polar coordinates. This parameterization (shower profile) serves as a priori knowledge when we try to reconstruct and identify an electromagnetic shower (“cluster”) in the real data taking environment.

The simplest case is when a particle hits the calorimeter with a 0° impact angle (angle between the incident particle and the direction normal to the surface; 0° means perpendicular to the surface). The parameterization is straightforward as shown by the following formula:

$$\frac{E_i^{\text{pred}}}{E_{\text{all}}^{\text{meas}}} = p_1 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{r_{CG}^3}{p_2}\right) + p_3 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{r_{CG}}{p_4}\right) \quad (2.19)$$

where $\frac{E_i^{\text{pred}}}{E_{\text{all}}^{\text{meas}}}$ is the fraction of total measured energy deposited in the i th tower. The coefficients p_i are the parameters defined by the physics of shower development in this particular calorimeter and obtained from fitting the test beam data. Fig. 2.25 shows the fraction of energy in each tower in the 5×5 towers region around the shower center.

However, when particles hit with a non-zero impact angle, the shower shape will be skewed, as shown in Fig. 2.26. The p_i parameters will then depend on

Figure 2.25: The fraction of deposited energy in each tower of the PbSc for a 10 GeV electron with an impact point of (0,0)cm and no impact angle ($\theta = 0$). Each cell corresponds to one tower. The upper number in each cell represents the fraction (%) of the total deposited energy and the lower number represents the fluctuations (Eq. 2.22). The core region used for the E_{core} calculation is shown in the red and orange boxes (with $> 2\%$ of the total energy deposit). Figure taken from [101].

both the impact angle θ and the energy of the incoming particle (related to the shower depth). Such a dependence is parameterized in the following way:

$$p_{i=1\sim 3} = a_i + (b_i + c_i \ln E_{all}^{meas}) \times \sin^2 \theta \quad (2.20)$$

$$p_4 = a_4 \quad (2.21)$$

a_i, b_i, c_i are obtained from a multi-dimensional fit using the test beam data with energies ranging from 0.3 - 20 GeV and impact angles 0° - 20° .

The deviation of the deposited energy in the i th tower from E_i^{pred} is characterized by the covariance σ_i , and a similar approach is used to parameterize σ_i :

$$\sigma_i^2 = C \cdot E_i^{pred} \cdot (1 + f(E_{all}^{meas}, \theta)) \left(1 - \frac{E_i^{pred}}{E_{all}^{meas}} \right) + q \quad (2.22)$$

where $f(E_{all}^{meas}, \theta) = k \cdot E_{all}^{meas} \cdot \sin^4 \theta$. q accounts for electronics noise and C sets the scale of energy fluctuation in the shower which is measured to be 0.03 GeV using the test beam data.

Figure 2.26: Energy distribution in PbSc towers as a function of the distance between the tower center and shower center of gravity. The space between adjacent contour lines corresponds to a 10% change in value. Left is for a 0° impact angle and right is for a 20° impact angle. Figure taken from [79, 100].

Energy measurement In principle, the energy measurement in the test beam will consist of simply summing the energy deposit in all the fired towers. In practice, a few corrections need to be made from that point on. One needs to correct for the light attenuation as the scintillation light is transferred via wavelength-shifting fiber to the photomultipliers. This correction is described by [79]:

$$E_{\text{corr}} = E_{\text{meas}} / (E_{\text{meas}})^{X_0 / \lambda_{\text{att}}} \quad (2.23)$$

where λ_{att} is the effective attenuation length (~ 120 cm) and X_0 is the radiation length (2.1 cm).

The longitudinal energy leakage also needs to be corrected for and is more important for higher energy photons (longer shower depth). The correction is about 1% for 10 GeV photons and about 4% for 100 GeV photons.

Position measurement The impact point of incoming particle on the calorimeter surface can be measured from the center of gravity of the electromagnetic shower [102]:

$$(x, y)_{\text{CG}} = \frac{\sum_{\text{shower}} (x_i, y_i) E_i}{\sum_{\text{shower}} E_i} \quad (2.24)$$

$$(x, y)_{\text{CG}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sinh([(x, y)_{\text{imp}} + \Delta - \delta] / b)}{\sinh(1/2b)} + \delta, \quad |(x, y)_{\text{imp}} + \Delta + \delta| \leq \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.25)$$

where $(x, y)_{\text{imp}}$ is the impact point of the particle. (b, Δ, δ) are the parameters extracted from the test beam data. They are all functions of impact angle θ and incident particle energy E .

One can then invert Eq. 2.25 to obtain the impact parameter (hit position) from the simple $(x, y)_{\text{CG}}$ measurement:

$$(x, y)_{\text{imp}} = b \cdot \sinh^{-1} [2((x, y)_{\text{CG}} - \delta) \sinh(1/2b)] - \Delta + \delta, \quad |(x, y)_{\text{CG}} - \delta| \leq \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.26)$$

Δ is the mean displacement of the calculated shower center-of-gravity from the impact point $(x, y)_{\text{imp}}$, and it is given by:

$$\Delta = L_{\text{eff}} \sin(\theta) \quad (2.27)$$

b is the shower cross-sectional width, and it can be described by:

$$b = b_0 + b_1(E) \sin^2 \theta \quad (2.28)$$

Figure 2.27: Projected shower shape in EMCAL exposed to 1 GeV/c electrons for different angles of incidence. Insert: EMCAL position resolution. Figure taken from [99].

Fig. 2.27 illustrates the impact angle effect on both Δ and b . The effect on Δ is seen as an increasing shift of the mean value of the projected shower shape with increasing impact angle. The effect on b corresponds to the broadening of the projected shower shape with increasing impact angle, which is mainly

related to longitudinal shower fluctuations contributing to the width of the projected shower.

δ is the phase shift related to the skewed shape of the shower projection. As shown in the left panel of Fig. 2.28, there is a “S-shape oscillation” of the measured position $(x, y)_{CG}$ around the true impact position $(x, y)_{imp}$. This term is related to the finite signal-to-noise ratio, comparable size of the shower size and the tower size in the transverse plane (x–y plane in local coordinate of the calorimeter) and the fact that shower energy is highly concentrated in one tower so that the $(x, y)_{CG}$ is always pulled towards the center of the tower which has the largest energy deposit. δ corresponds to the phase of the “oscillation” and such a correction gives a better linear response for the measured hit position.

We have discussed the “S-shape oscillation” when using the center of gravity $(x, y)_{CG}$ as a measurement of $(x, y)_{imp}$. One needs to introduce the energy and impact angle correction, δ , to retrieve a linear response. There is actually an alternative way [103] (not used in PHENIX) of measuring the hit position using $\ln E$ rather than E as the weight:

$$(x, y)_{new} = \frac{\sum_{\text{cluster}} (x_i, y_i) w_i}{\sum_{\text{cluster}} w_i}, \quad \text{where } w_i = \max\left(0, w_0 + \ln\left(\frac{E_i}{\sum E_i}\right)\right), \quad (2.29)$$

where w_i represents the new weight. w_0 sets a threshold for the fraction of the total shower energy deposited in the tower, so that channels close to the noise level will not contribute. The comparison of x_{CG} and x_{new} from GEANT simulations is illustrated in Fig. 2.28.

2.2.4.6 Shower Reconstruction / Clustering Algorithm

In central heavy ion collision events, the occupancy of the EMCal detector is much higher as compared to the test beam events due to the extreme particle multiplicity. Fig. 2.29 shows an event display of the deposited energy in the EMCal from central to peripheral events. The challenge is to identify and reconstruct the single electromagnetic showers when they are overlapping with each other. We call the algorithm dealing with the shower identification and reconstruction “clustering”. The procedures used by the clustering algorithm are described below [25, 79]:

- A noise threshold of 10 MeV is applied for every tower.
- Neighboring towers which share the same edges are combined into an isolated cluster.

Figure 2.28: Position measurement of electrons in the EMCal using Eq. 2.24 in the left panels and Eq. 2.29 in the right panels. The upper panels are the calculated positions as a function of the impact (incident) position on an event-by-event basis. The lower panels show the average of the difference of the calculated position from the incident position as a function of the incident position. Figure taken from [103].

- The local maximum in an isolated cluster is identified. A local maximum is a module above the peak threshold (80 MeV) with the maximum amplitude in the 3×3 towers region surrounding it.
- If there is only one local maximum, the cluster is saved.
- If there is more than one local maximum, the cluster is split and new clusters are formed around each local maximum. The energy of the shared towers are assigned to the split clusters according to the amplitude and positions of the maxima using the parameterized shower profile.
- The shower shape of the split clusters is evaluated and a χ^2 value is assigned for shower identification purposes.
- The split clusters are then saved.

In the end, the reconstructed clusters correspond to individual showers. The cluster then becomes the basic object for the position and energy reconstruction. The position reconstruction is the same as what is used for the test beam (described in Sec. 2.2.4.5). However, the energy reconstruction is slightly more

complicated as compared to the test beam environment due to possible shower overlaps. To cope with this, a “core energy” algorithm is used, as described in the following section.

Figure 2.29: Event display of the deposited energy in an EMCAL sector (West0) for each centrality condition. “ix” and “iy” in the figures are the tower id (“ix” corresponds to along the beam line). Figure taken from [25].

Core energy An incoming particle usually deposits energy in more than one tower. For example, with an energy threshold of 3 MeV, the cluster size of a 0.5 GeV (4 GeV) incoming photon is on average 7 (19) towers in the PbSc calorimeter [79]. In principle, one would want to sum over all the towers to get the measured energy equal to the total energy deposited. However, in central heavy ion collisions, there are overlapping showers due to the high occupancy and that affects the energy measurement (i.e. it worsens the energy resolution

and shifts the measured energy systematically higher). The larger the cluster size, the more likely to have overlapping showers in each cluster. Therefore we reduce the energy summation region to only 4 ~ 5 towers by requiring each tower have at least 2% of the total energy in the 5×5 “peak area”:

$$\frac{E_i^{\text{pred}}}{E_{\text{all}}^{\text{meas}}} > 0.02 \quad (2.30)$$

where E_i^{pred} is the predicted energy deposit from the shower profile (described in Sec. 2.2.4.5), and $E_{\text{all}}^{\text{meas}}$ is the total energy in the peak area. These towers form the so-called shower “core”.

$$E_{\text{core}} = \sum_i^{\text{core}} E_i^{\text{meas}} \quad (2.31)$$

E_{core} only contains 92% of the total shower energy, dropping to 90% for a 20° impact angle. To correct for the energy loss in the tail not included in the core region, the total energy fraction relative to the expected total energy is estimated via a Monte Carlo simulation study input using the test beam shower profile. The parameterization is given as follows [25]:

$$\frac{E_{\text{core}}}{E_{\text{core}}^{\text{corr}}} = a_1 \cdot (1 - a_2 \sin^4 \theta (1 - a_3 \cdot \ln E_{\text{core}})) \quad (2.32)$$

where $a_1 = 0.918$, $a_2 = 1.35$, and $a_3 = 0.003$.

Since we use $E_{\text{core}}^{\text{corr}}$ in the analysis, for simplicity, we will denote $E_{\text{core}}^{\text{corr}}$ as E_{core} from this point on.

2.2.4.7 Photon Identification

In addition to the energy and impact position measurements, the EMCal in PHENIX also plays an important role in discriminating electrons and photons from hadrons. To select photons, one can apply an energy threshold cut, use the shower-shape analysis, and/or use the time of flight information. To select electrons/positrons, one can use the same criteria as for photon selection. Since e^\pm are charged particles, one can also combine the tracking information (p) with the calorimeter information (E) and discriminate e^\pm from charged hadrons based on the energy over momentum ratio E/p . We will focus on identification using only the calorimeter information here, and more information about the E/p cut can be found in Sec. 2.2.5.1.

Using the energy response (energy threshold) The EMCal is designed to be deep enough to catch all of the electromagnetic shower initiated by an incoming γ and e^\pm in most of the cases (there can be longitudinal leakage for very energetic particles). On the contrary, most hadrons punch through the EMCal with only partial energy loss. The hadrons either do not shower (just undergo ionization) or only deposit part of their total energy in the calorimeter since its thickness is only about one hadronic interaction length [104]. PbGl further suppresses the energy deposition of hadrons because it only observes Cherenkov light and the momentum threshold for charged hadrons to start Cherenkov radiation is higher than for γ/e^\pm . The Cherenkov threshold momenta for muons, pions and protons are 81, 106 and 715 MeV/c, respectively [93]. Below this threshold hadrons will not emit Cherenkov light, and hence the signal will be reduced. Fig. 2.30 - Fig. 2.31 show the energy response of the EMCal to electrons (as a proxy for photons in terms of energy deposition), pions and protons in two cases: the test beam and real data for peripheral Au + Au collisions. As we can see, electrons always deposit most of their energy so that the energy measured with the EMCal (E_{EMC}) is always around the particle's true energy. On the contrary, most of the pions and protons deposit ~ 0.27 GeV and ~ 0.56 GeV respectively via minimum ionization independent of the particle true energy. The hadrons can also develop a hadronic shower in the EMCal which gives the broader energy spread (gaussian like shape) under the minimum ionization peak in the plots. Therefore, by applying an energy threshold cut above the minimum ionization peak, one can already reject part of the hadrons.

Using the shower shape To discriminate photons from hadrons for a given momentum, one can use the shower shape of the clusters and check if the shape is more like an electromagnetic shower. This is quantified by the χ^2 between the known electromagnetic shower profile based on the test beam study and the measured shower shape:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_i \frac{\left(E_i^{\text{meas}} - E_i^{\text{pred}}\right)^2}{\sigma_i^2} \quad (2.33)$$

where E_i^{meas} is the measured energy deposit in the i th tower and E_i^{pred} is the predicted energy in the same tower based on Eq. 2.19, with the measured total energy $E_{\text{total}} = \sum_i E_i^{\text{meas}}$. σ_i is the predicted energy fluctuation of the electromagnetic shower given by Eq. 2.22. Fig. 2.32 shows the χ^2 distribution for electrons and pions at $p = 2$ GeV/c. As can be seen from Fig. 2.32, a standard $\chi^2 < 3$ cut is $\sim 90\%$ efficient for electrons and photons but only

Figure 2.30: The energy spectra measured in the PHENIX EMCal with the test beam at BNL when exposed to electrons, pions and protons of $p = 0.5, 1.0$ and 2.0 GeV/ c . Figure taken from [104].

$\sim 30\%$ efficient for pions, hence further enhancing the purity of the photon sample. The χ^2 cut has more discriminating power at higher energy, while on the lower-energy side < 2 GeV there is still a significant amount of misidentified hadrons surviving the χ^2 cut.

One can use a “stochastic” cut [25] defined by Eq. 2.34 to reject more hadrons as compared to the χ^2 cut, but it suffers from a lower photon efficiency as shown in Fig. 2.33.

$$\text{stoch}_2 = (0.3 + 4 \exp(-E_{\text{all}}/E_{\text{cent}})) \cdot (1.9 - 0.67\chi^2) > 1.4 \quad (2.34)$$

Using time of flight The EMCal also provides time of flight (TOF) information for the measured particles (using the BBC to obtain the event start time). The timing resolution after the slewing corrections and flight path corrections based on the event vertex is often better than 700 ps for the PbSc calorimeters [79, 93]. Such resolution is much worse compared to that of the Time of Flight detector (TOF) which has about 100 ps resolution [105]. So the timing from the EMCal mainly helps with the $\gamma(e)/\pi$ separation in the very low momenta regime (< 0.8 GeV/ s). The advantage of the EMCal is its much wider coverage in ϕ , and the timing cuts complements the shower shape cut, which loses its effectiveness on the lower energy side.

Figure 2.31: Particle response in PHENIX EMCAL for real data, Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. The identified particles are electrons, pions and (anti)-protons in three wide momentum bins illustrated by the grey shade and quantified at the top of the panels: $0.45 < p < 0.55$; $0.85 < p < 1.15$ and $1.75 < p < 2.25$ GeV/ c . Identification of the particles was done with different detectors: pions and protons with the TOF and electrons with the RICH. Only clusters with $E \geq 0.2$ GeV are considered. Figure taken from [101].

2.2.5 Particle / Electron Identification

PHENIX has many subsystems for particle identification purposes as shown in the PID section of Tab. 2.1. The direct photon analysis presented in this thesis mainly deals with photons and electrons. We have already discussed photon identification in Sec. 2.2.4.7, and we will focus explicitly on electron identification in this section. More information on identifying hadrons can be found in [79, 105].

2.2.5.1 Energy over momentum ratio of charged particles

As shown in Sec. 2.2.4.7, electrons will deposit all their energy into the calorimeter, while hadrons mostly just lose energy via ionization and hence only a small amount of their energy is seen by the calorimeter. Therefore, for electrons, the momentum (p) measured by the tracking system (Sec. 2.2.3) should be similar to the energy (E) measured by the calorimeter, meaning $E/p \approx 1$. For hadrons, p will be most likely much larger than E , meaning $E/p \ll 1$.

Figure 2.32: χ^2 distribution for showers induced by $p = 2 \text{ GeV}/c$ electrons and pions in the PbSc. Figure taken from [93].

Figure 2.33: Cluster reconstruction efficiency as a function of deposited energy ($\varepsilon(E_{\text{EMC}}) = N_{\text{PID}}/N_{\text{noPID}}$) for different particles using different PID cuts, $\chi^2 < 3.0$ in the left panel and stoch_2 in the right panel. Figure taken from [101].

To combine the momentum (p) and energy (E) measurements, a straight line projection of the track is performed from the DC to the EMCal front surface. The cluster which falls into the nearest vicinity of the projection point is then associated to the corresponding track. An E/p ratio can then be constructed for the associated track and cluster.

2.2.5.2 Track-EMCal Matching Displacement

Once the association is done, another variable can be used to help discriminate the electrons from charged hadrons, which is the displacement between the track projection point and the associated cluster position. Such a displacement is expressed by $emcd\phi$ in the ϕ direction and $emcdz$ in the z direction:

$$\begin{aligned} emcd\phi &= \phi_{\text{cluster}} - \phi_{\text{track}}^{\text{proj}} \\ emcdz &= z_{\text{cluster}} - z_{\text{track}}^{\text{proj}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.35)$$

For particles with the same momentum, the EMCal has a better position resolution for electrons/photons as compared to hadrons. Fig. 2.34 shows the deviation of the measured positions from the true impact positions for electron and pion beams in the PbSc test beam study. Therefore, one can further reject the charged hadron tracks by selecting tracks with smaller δ_ϕ and δ_z .

Figure 2.34: The deviation of the measured positions ($X_{\text{EMC}}, Y_{\text{EMC}}$) from the true impact positions ($X_{\text{imp}}, Y_{\text{imp}}$) for (a) electrons (b) pions with 2 GeV/ c momentum. Figure taken from [104].

2.2.5.3 Ring Imaging Cherenkov Detector

The Ring Imaging Cherenkov detector (RICH) [106, 107] is the primary device for electron identification in PHENIX. It is a Cherenkov-type detector using CO_2 as the radiator (index of refraction $n = 1.00041$). The momentum threshold to produce Cherenkov radiation is 18 MeV/ c for e^\pm , 4.87 GeV/ c for π^\pm and much higher for heavier particles (see Fig. 2.37). Therefore the PHENIX RICH detector can be used to effectively identify electrons below 5 GeV/ c by checking if the charged particle emits Cherenkov photons or not.

Fig. 2.35 shows a cutaway view of the RICH vessel on one side of the central arm and how the signal (Cherenkov light) is collected by the detector. As can be seen in Fig. 2.35 (b), when an electron passes through the RICH gas volume, Cherenkov photons emitted from the electron are reflected by thin spherical mirrors and are focused into a ring shape on the focal plane where arrays of photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) are located to collect the light signal. Cherenkov light from electrons going at different ϕ and θ angles will focus on different rings on the PMT plane. The radius of the reflecting surface of the mirror is 4.03 m.

The PMT arrays are placed outside the PHENIX central magnet so that particles from the collision vertex do not directly hit the arrays. This arrangement keeps a small radiation length of 2.1% in the central arm acceptance and thus minimize the photon conversions and multiple scattering. A Winston cone with a 5 cm entrance diameter is mounted on each PMT to help collect Cherenkov light, and each PMT is housed in a magnetic shielding case to allow it to function well in the residual magnetic field (< 0.1 T). The PMTs are first assembled into 16×2 sub-arrays, called a super module. 40 super modules contain a 16×80 array of PMTs, which forms one side of the RICH detector. There are in total 5120 (2 (arm) $\times 2$ (side) $\times 16$ (θ) $\times 80$ (ϕ)) channels in the RICH system. The angular segmentation of the PMT array is approximately 1° by 1° in ϕ and θ . Such high granularity is necessary to cope with the high charged particle density (about 1000 charged particles per unit rapidity). The occupancy of the RICH is kept low, only about 3.4% even in the most central Au-Au collisions due to its high granularity.

Principles of operation When a particle in a medium travels faster than the speed of light in that medium, the particle will emit Cherenkov radiation. The condition for the emission of Cherenkov radiation and the angle of the emitted Cherenkov light θ_c is given by:

$$\beta > \frac{1}{n}, \quad \cos\theta_c = \frac{1}{n\beta} \quad (2.36)$$

where n is the refractive index of the medium, and β is the speed (relative to the speed of light in vacuum) of the charged particle. For a given momentum, electrons always have a larger β as compared to hadrons because of their small mass. With a small n , the momentum threshold for charged hadrons to generate Cherenkov radiation is higher, and hence such a Cherenkov radiator can be operated as a threshold detector to identify electrons in the low momentum range.

The number of produced Cherenkov photons is constant per unit length

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.35: (a) A cutaway view of one arm of the PHENIX RICH detector. (b) Schematic view of the RICH, with the beam direction corresponding to the horizontal direction in the figure.

and per unit wavelength. It depends on the charge (z) and velocity of the particle (β), the index of refraction of the radiator (n), and the wavelength of the Cherenkov photons. The Cherenkov radiation is a continuous spectra and can be expressed by:

$$\frac{d^2 N}{d\lambda dx} = \frac{2\pi\alpha z^2}{\lambda^2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n^2(\lambda)\beta^2}\right) \approx \frac{2\pi\alpha z^2}{\lambda^2} \sin^2\theta_c \quad (2.37)$$

The approximation comes from ignoring the dispersion factor that n is not exactly a constant but has a weak dependence on λ . For a particle with a certain momentum, less Cherenkov light will be emitted for a radiator with a smaller n . This is the reason why the RICH detector in PHENIX has a very large radiator volume (~ 1.5 m long in the radial direction) and employs an optical focusing technique (“ring imaging”) to increase the amount of Cherenkov light seen by the PMTs.

The parallel Cherenkov light (with the same ϕ and θ angle) is focused to one point on the focal plane. Using rotational symmetry, the Cherenkov light produced by a single track is focused into a ring shape on the focal plane. The track projection point, defined as the focal point of the light parallel to the track, is at the ring center. The radius of the ring r_c is determined by θ_c via the following expression:

$$r_c = f \cdot \theta_c \quad (2.38)$$

where $f = R_{\text{mirror}}/2 = 2$ m is the focal length. Fig. 2.36 illustrates how the Cherenkov radiation light from an electron track is focused into a ring around the track projection point and which PMTs fall into the expected radius range of the emitted light.

Figure 2.36: The ring formed by Cherenkov emissions around the associated track projection point on the PMT plane. Figure adapted from [108].

RICH electron identification variables After associating the Cherenkov ring to the corresponding charged track (the track projection points close to the ring center), the following variables can then be constructed to discriminate electron tracks from pion tracks using the RICH and track projection information.

- n_i : the number of fired PMTs.

- npe_i : the number of Cherenkov photo-electrons.
- χ^2 : the difference between the observed ring shape and the ideal ring shape (the RMS^2 of the positions of the hit PMTs weighted by the number of photo-electrons in the hit PMTs compared to the expected distribution from an electron track within a radius of 11 cm around the track projection).
- $disp$: the distance between the ring center and the track projection point.

For n_i and npe_i , i is an integer from 0 to 3 representing different ring areas [108]. $i = 0$ corresponds to the nominal ring area, which is the expected radius range of the Cherenkov light from electron tracks. It is an annulus around the track projection with an inner radius of 3.4 cm and an outer radius of 8.4 cm. The expected ring radius for different charged particles can be easily estimated with Eq. 2.36 and Eq. 2.38. The result as a function of particle momentum is shown in Fig. 2.37 (effects like detector resolutions and dispersion are not included in this calculation). The result is consistent with the nominal ring area we use for electron identification. One can also immediately notice that the PHENIX RICH can most effectively determine if the particles are electrons before the charged hadrons pass the Cherenkov radiation threshold, meaning below 5 GeV/ c . The resolution on r_c (or equivalently θ_c), given by the size of the PMTs, is not enough to tell electrons apart from pions in the high momentum regime (> 5 GeV/ c).

Background (hadron contamination) Given the nature of the elliptical mirror focusing, there is an inherent ambiguity in the track – ring association [106]. For parallel tracks, the track projection points will be the same on the PMT plane (focal plane). Therefore, if there happens to be some charged pions flying parallel to an electron (shown in the left panel of Fig. 2.38), such pions will be associated to the RICH ring generated by the electron Cherenkov radiation. This type of mis-association (random association) between the charged hadron tracks and the electron rings causes the background in the electron sample after the RICH electron identification selection. The right panel of Fig. 2.38 shows the effect of requiring RICH association and the remaining background. The majority of the charged track sample is charged hadrons, a clear MIP peak at $E/p \sim 0.3$ sitting on a broad distribution caused by hadronic interactions in the calorimeter. After requiring the RICH association, most of the hadrons are rejected and thus an electron peak ($E/p \sim 1$) becomes visible, although there is still some hadron contamination mainly due to the random association we just discussed. Such a background can be esti-

Figure 2.37: Expected Cherenkov ring radius r_c as a function of momentum p for e^\pm , π^\pm , K^\pm and p^\pm . Momentum thresholds for different charged particles are shown inside the parentheses. The right side of the plot shows the adjacent PMT coverage range for θ_c (the red star symbol corresponds to the track projection point $\theta_c = 0^\circ$, where this is a special case of the track projection located at the center of one PMT).

mated by swapping the north and south sides of the RICH and reconstructing the track – ring association once again [108, 109].

2.2.6 Detector Simulation

Due to the limited detector acceptance, efficiency and resolution, the physics observables we measure often has those detector effects folded in and correction are needed to obtain the “true” physics observable. For instance, the amount of particles we reconstruct with our detector (raw yield) is just part of the truly produced particles (true yield) in a event, and one needs to apply the acceptance and efficiency correction to retrieve the true yield. The primary tool we use to correct for detector effects is simulation, where a simulated detector with realistic geometry and response is provided so that one can study the detector effects in a controlled environment.

Figure 2.38: Left: Example of the ambiguities in the Cherenkov ring association – the pions fly nearly parallel to the electron (solid line). The dotted line represents the like-sign pion (same charge as the electron) and the dashed line represents the unlike-sign pion (opposite charge as the electron). Right: E/p ratio of all the charged tracks (dashed-dotted line), tracks associated with RICH hits (solid line), estimated background for tracks with a RICH hit (dotted line), and tracks associated with RICH hits after background subtraction (solid markers). The transverse momentum range is from 1.1 to 1.2 GeV/c. Figure taken from [105].

2.2.6.1 PHENIX Integrated Simulation Application

In PHENIX, the detector geometry, response and the magnetic field are implemented in the PHENIX Integrated Simulation Application (PISA) software [110]. PISA is a customized GEANT-3 package, where the passage of elementary particles through matter are described using Monte Carlo simulation [111]. As the particles traversing the simulated PHENIX detector in PISA, the interactions between particles and detector material dictated by GEANT (like ionization, pair creation, Bremsstrahlung, hadronic interaction, multiple scattering, etc) are partly converted into simulated detector signals and recorded in the same format as the raw data collected in the real data taking. Such setup ensures that the same PHENIX reconstruction software applied on the raw data can also be applied in the same manner on the PISA output. The key difference between the real detector and simulated detector is that the true information of the particles (e.g. the full ancestry and daughter history, true momentum) is available in simulation, and can be used to compare with the reconstructed information and extract the correction fac-

tors. PHENIX reconstruction software, reconstructed objects like tracks and clusters (true information preserved).

2.2.6.2 Simulation Framework

To study the detector effects, we usually start from generating events of interest and pass them through the simulated detector PISA. The PISA output is then treated as real data, and standard PHENIX reconstruction (tracks, clusters, etc.) are performed. At the end, we evaluate the observables of interest and compare to true information recorded in the simulation output. A general simulation framework is summarized below:

- **Event Generation:** single particle events (π^0 , γ , etc), multiple particles events, more sophisticated event generator like Pythia [112], HIJING, etc.
- **Detector Response Simulation:** PISA or parameterized detector response.
- **Reconstruction:** convert raw detector response to physics objects (tuned to real data), like charged track reconstruction, track-particle ID association, EMCAL cluster reconstruction, track-EMCAL cluster association.
- **Evaluation:** reconstruct observables of interest (raw counts, reconstructed momentum, reconstructed energy, etc) and compare to the true value (generated true yield, true momentum, true energy, etc).

In this analysis, we used several simulation setups for different purposes. We used single γ simulation and the photon conversion process $\gamma \rightarrow e^+ + e^-$ to develop and test the new conversion photon reconstruction algorithm (see Sec. 3.2). A special single γ simulation with no magnetic field is used to cross check the detector material budget (see Sec. 4.8.2.3). We used a high multiplicity π^0 simulation to test the purity level of the new conversion photon selection cuts (see Sec. 3.2.4.2) and the double ratio tagging method to measure direct photon (see Sec. 3.3.2). Embedded single π^0 simulation is used to obtain the acceptance and efficiency when using the double ratio tagging method (see Sec. 4.6.2).

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter will introduce a new algorithm to reconstruct the tracks of an e^+e^- pair from external photon conversions. Such e^+e^- pairs (conversion pairs) form the inclusive photon sample in this analysis. After that, the double ratio tagging method is described, which is the method we use to measure the direct photon signal from the total inclusive photon sample. The double ratio tagging method was tested with a high multiplicity π^0 simulation. This simulation serves as proof of principle that direct photons can be extracted with sufficient accuracy.

3.1 External Conversion Photon Method

In PHENIX, there are in general two ways to reconstruct photons. The most straightforward way is to reconstruct the photon directly from its energy deposit and impact position measured by the electromagnetic calorimeter [113]. Given the measured event vertex position, the momentum vectors of the photons produced at or close to the collision point can then be fully reconstructed. This method, referred to as the calorimeter method, gives a good resolution and purity for high p_T ($>\sim 4\text{GeV}/c$) photons. However, towards lower p_T , the resolution degrades according to Eq. 2.13 and the hadron contamination becomes more and more significant (see Sec. 2.2.4.7).

To reconstruct and identify photons reliably in the low p_T regime, photon conversions to lepton pairs can be used. Here, the e^+e^- pair results from one of the following two processes:

- virtual photons go to lepton pairs [114]: $\gamma^* \rightarrow e^+ + e^-$
- real photon pair production via interaction with the detector material [54]: $\gamma \rightarrow e^+ + e^-$

To reconstruct such photons, one first needs to reconstruct the momentum vectors of the daughter electron and positron at the conversion point via the tracking system, and then sum the vectors to determine the photon momentum vector. The main difference in terms of tracking between the two conversion processes is where the photons convert to electron-positron pairs. In the case of virtual photons, the e^+e^- pairs come from the event vertex; while the real photon conversions take place in the detector material away from the event vertex. The conversion probability is proportional to the thickness of the material, usually described in units of radiation length X_0 . Thereby the virtual photon reconstruction method is also denoted as the internal conversion method, and the real photon conversion reconstruction is referred to as the external conversion method. All three methods are illustrated in Fig. 3.1.

In this analysis, we used the external conversion method with the external conversions mainly coming from the Silicon Vertex Tracker (VTX), which was installed during 2011 to provide tracking near the interaction point. The total material budget of the VTX is about 13% X_0 , resulting in a good statistical sample of conversions.

3.1.1 Off-vertex Tracks with Standard PHENIX Track Reconstruction

As described in Sec. 2.2.3.5, the standard PHENIX track reconstruction assumes the origin of all tracks to be at the interaction point, but that is a wrong assumption for the external conversions. In this section, we will discuss how many variables are needed to fully reconstruct a charged track (e.g. why such an assumption is needed in the first place), and the effect of using a wrong assumption for off-vertex tracks coming from external conversions.

3.1.1.1 Track Properties: Degrees of Freedom

The force bending the trajectory of a charged track in the magnetic field is the Lorentz force. Once the magnetic field map is given, in general one needs 6 variables to fully reconstruct a track, for example one space point and the momentum vector at that point. The tracking system only provides 3 variables: bending angle α , azimuthal angle ϕ_{DC} and the z position z_{DC} where the track hits the DC. Hence the origin of the track must be assumed in the standard track reconstruction.

In this analysis, we focus on the e^+e^- pairs from photon conversions. These tracks share a unique property – their momentum vectors at the conversion location points radially away from the interaction vertex. Now that the direction of track momentum has to be radial, one space point and the magnitude

Figure 3.1: Three different photon reconstruction methods in PHENIX. The dashed line corresponds to the calorimeter method. The solid lines correspond to the conversion methods, where the tracks coming from the collision point represent the internal conversion (virtual photon) method.

of the momentum at that point is sufficient to determine the track. Therefore, we need 4 variables in total to determine the track and perform the reconstruction. For instance, these four variables can be chosen as the conversion radius and the 3 variables provided by the tracking system: α , ϕ_{DC} and z_{DC} .

3.1.1.2 Mis-reconstruction of the External Conversions

The standard track reconstruction works well when the tracks originate from (or very near) the event vertex, but this is not the case for tracks from external photon conversions. The false assumption in the standard reconstruction results in a mis-measurement of both the trajectory and kinematics, which in turn results in a mis-reconstruction of the conversion photons.

Artificial opening angle In previous analyses, external conversions in the Hadron Blind Detector (HBD) [115] readout plane were used [2, 54, 116]. The HBD readout plane is of a cylindrical shape, located at a well defined radial

position $r = 60$ cm, with a radiation length of about $2.5\% X_0$. For such conversions, the e^\pm tracks traverse through less magnetic field and are thus bent less as compared to tracks from the event vertex. If one assumes these e^\pm tracks originate from the event vertex, both the direction of the track at the vertex, ϕ_0 , and the magnitude of the momentum, p , will be larger than the values at the true conversion position, which results in an “artificial” opening angle between the e^\pm tracks at the event vertex. The difference between the true e^\pm trajectories and the reconstructed trajectories assuming an event vertex origin is illustrated in Fig. 3.2a.

Non-zero mass of reconstructed conversion photons If we ignore the recoil of the nuclei involved in the pair production, which is much smaller than the γ or e^\pm energy we care about, the mass of the conversion photon can be constructed from the momentum of the daughter e^\pm by:

$$\begin{aligned}
M^2 &= (E_+ + E_-, \mathbf{p}_+ + \mathbf{p}_-)^2 & (3.1) \\
&= (E_+ + E_-)^2 - |\mathbf{p}_+ + \mathbf{p}_-|^2 \\
&= E_+^2 + E_-^2 + 2E_+E_- - (\mathbf{p}_+^2 + \mathbf{p}_-^2 + 2\mathbf{p}_+ \cdot \mathbf{p}_-) \\
&\approx |\mathbf{p}_+|^2 + |\mathbf{p}_-|^2 + 2|\mathbf{p}_+||\mathbf{p}_-| - |\mathbf{p}_+|^2 - |\mathbf{p}_-|^2 - 2|\mathbf{p}_+||\mathbf{p}_-|\cos\theta \\
&= 2|\mathbf{p}_+||\mathbf{p}_-|(1 - \cos\theta) & (3.2)
\end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{p}_\pm is the three momentum vector of the e^\pm , and θ is the opening angle between the e^+ and the e^- . The approximation made from line 3 to line 4 is neglecting the e^\pm mass (very small compared to the momentum range of this study).

In the pair production process, e^+ and e^- are emitted in nearly the same direction hence $M \approx 0$. However, if one uses the momentum from the standard track reconstruction, the artificial opening angle, namely $\phi_0^+ - \phi_0^-$, will lead to a finite reconstructed photon mass (e^+e^- pair mass):

$$M_{\text{vtx}}^2 = 2p_{\text{vtx}}^+ p_{\text{vtx}}^- (1 - \cos(\phi_0^+ - \phi_0^-)) \quad (3.3)$$

where p_{vtx}^\pm is the magnitude of the e^\pm momentum and ϕ_0^\pm is the direction of e^\pm tracks at the event vertex determined via the standard PHENIX track reconstruction. For the conversions at the HBD readout plane, $M_{\text{vtx}} \approx 12$ MeV/ c^2 .

Alternate Track Model (ATM) To have the momentum and mass of the conversion photon measured correctly, the e^\pm tracks need to be reconstructed to their true conversion position. From the discussion in Sec. 3.1.1.1, we

know the tracks from external conversions can be fully reconstructed once the conversion radius is given. In this case its simply 60 cm (the radial position of the HBD readout plane). The new reconstruction using the HBD readout plane radius as the track origin is called the Alternate Track Model (ATM) [2], and a new photon mass M_{HBD} can be calculated:

$$M_{\text{HBD}}^2 = 2p_{\text{HBD}}^+ p_{\text{HBD}}^- (1 - \cos(\phi_{\text{HBD}}^+ - \phi_{\text{HBD}}^-)) \quad (3.4)$$

M_{HBD} is nearly zero because now the e^\pm are reconstructed to the correct conversion radius. Fig. 3.2 shows the 2D histogram of e^+e^- pairs, where the x axis is M_{vtx} and the y axis is M_{HBD} . The main blob highlighted by the surrounding red dashed box corresponds to the HBD conversions and the other blob near the y axis corresponds to the Dalitz decay $\pi^0 \rightarrow e^+ + e^- + \gamma$. For the Dalitz decay, the e^+e^- comes from the event vertex, and hence their M_{HBD} is about 12 MeV/c^2 and M_{vtx} is about zero. Selecting ($M_{\text{vtx}}, M_{\text{HBD}}$) within the red box gives a very pure sample of HBD conversions.

Figure 3.2: Left: A cartoon illustrating the mis-reconstruction of external photon conversions when using the standard reconstruction. The red lines represent the real track trajectory of the e^+e^- pair from a photon conversion at the HBD readout plane, while the yellow ones represent the reconstructed trajectories using the standard reconstruction. Right: Invariant mass of conversions/ e^+e^- pairs using the tracks reconstructed to the HBD readout plane (red lines) M_{HBD} versus using the tracks reconstructed to the event vertex (yellow lines) M_{vtx} .

3.1.1.3 Conversions at the VTX detector

Although the ATM reconstructs the conversions from the HBD readout plane correctly, it is not applicable for the data sets taken after 2010. In 2011, the HBD was removed and the Silicon Vertex Tracker (VTX) [117, 118] installed. The material of the VTX detector is not located at a fixed radial position and has a rather complicated geometry, see insert in Fig. 3.3. There are 4 individual layers arranged around the beam pipe at nominal radii of $r = 2.6$ cm, 5.1 cm, 11.8 cm and 16.7 cm. The two inner layers, B0 and B1, were constructed using silicon-pixel technology [119] and the two outer layers, B2 and B3, were constructed using a novel silicon-stripixel technology [120]. Each layer consists of a series of ladders staggered next to each other. The material budget for the B0 to B3 layers are 1.28%, 1.28%, 5.43% and 5.43% X_0 , respectively.

Fig. 3.3 shows the mass distribution of photons converted at the beam pipe and the VTX using the standard track reconstruction in the Monte Carlo simulation. In contrast to conversions at the HBD readout plane, there are multiple peaks in the mass distribution. From low to high mass, each peak corresponds to conversions from low to high conversion radius, and the integral of counts under each peak is proportional to the material thickness. The two major peaks (green and blue) are conversions from the silicon-stripixel layers B2 and B3, and our main focus is to reconstruct and identify the conversions in that region.

3.2 New Conversion Reconstruction Algorithm

To reconstruct and identify conversions at different VTX layers, we developed a new track reconstruction algorithm [121]. The new algorithm uses a pair of e^+e^- tracks to first find the actual conversion position and then determines the correct momentum of the e^\pm based on the reconstructed conversion radius information. This section introduces the principle of the new algorithm using a simplified magnetic field map in Mathematica, its implementation in the PHENIX reconstruction framework, the performance test in Monte Carlo simulation, and the conversion photon selection criteria with the new algorithm.

3.2.1 Single track trajectory

Theoretically, given detailed knowledge of the magnetic field and the initial position and momentum of a charged particle, we can solve for its position at any arbitrary time, and there should be one and only one solution.

Figure 3.3: Different colors represent different conversion regions, as shown in the legend (the number after each line is the total number of conversions in the corresponding region). The structure of the VTX is displayed in the inset on the right.

3.2.1.1 Lorentz Force and Equation of Motion

The magnetic field in PHENIX is generated by the central magnet and is mostly along the z direction (see Sec. 2.2.3.1). The strength of the magnetic field varies little along z and the azimuthal direction, and thus we approximate the field as $\mathbf{B} = B_z(r)$ (i.e. azimuthally symmetric, with no radial component). The force exerted on a charged particle is the Lorentz force (\mathbf{F}), which in cylindrical coordinates can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{F} = q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} = q \begin{vmatrix} \hat{r} & \hat{\phi} & \hat{z} \\ v_r & v_\phi & v_z \\ 0 & 0 & B_z \end{vmatrix} \quad (3.5)$$

where q is the charge of the particle, \mathbf{v} is the velocity of the particle and \mathbf{B} is the magnetic field. The equation of motion is:

$$\gamma m \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{F} \quad (3.6)$$

where γ is the Lorentz factor, m is the mass of the particle and \mathbf{a} is its acceleration. In cylindrical coordinates $(\hat{r}, \hat{\phi}, \hat{z})$, we obtain the following equations

of motion:

$$\gamma m(\ddot{r} - r\dot{\phi}^2) = qB_z r\dot{\phi} \quad (3.7)$$

$$\gamma m(r\ddot{\phi} + 2\dot{r}\dot{\phi}) = -qB_z \dot{r} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\gamma m\ddot{z} = 0 \quad (3.9)$$

The motion in the r - ϕ (x - y) plane is completely separate from that in the z direction. If given the initial condition (the initial position and velocity of the particle), we can solve for $r(t)$ and $\phi(t)$ from Eq. 3.7 and Eq. 3.8.

3.2.1.2 Initial and Final Conditions

Since we do not know the initial conditions, but only the trajectory of the particle in the DC/PC1, we extrapolate backwards to find the conversion point by reversing time. In this scenario the particle starts from the DC detector, then travels back to its conversion point, thus the initial conditions (at $t = 0$) would be

$$\begin{cases} r(0) = r_{DC} \\ \phi(0) = \phi_{DC} \\ v_r(0) = \dot{r}(0) = -v_{DC}\cos(\alpha) \\ v_\phi(0) = r(0)\dot{\phi}(0) = v_{DC}\sin(\alpha) \end{cases} \quad (3.10)$$

where $r_{DC} = 220$ cm is the reference radius of the DC detector, ϕ_{DC} and α are measured (see Fig. 2.20), and v_{DC} is the velocity of the particle at that location. With the assumption that the magnetic field is independent of $\hat{\phi}$, the equation of motion will remain the same under rotation in $\hat{\phi}$. That means we can rotate our frame L (the lab frame) by ϕ_{DC} to a new frame L', where $\phi_{DC} = 0$ (see Fig. 3.4).

In the L' frame, the initial conditions become:

$$\begin{cases} r(0) = r_{DC} \\ \phi(0) = 0 \\ v_r(0) = \dot{r}(0) = -v_{DC}\cos(\alpha) \\ v_\phi(0) = r(0)\dot{\phi}(0) = v_{DC}\sin(\alpha) \end{cases} \quad (3.11)$$

In the L' frame, the initial conditions depend only on the momentum of the particle, p_{DC} , and the bending angle α at the DC. Using the known magnetic field, we can solve $r(t)$ and $\phi(t)$ for fixed $\{p_{DC}, \alpha\}$. In addition, in our approximation for the magnetic field, p_{DC} does not change with time and thus can be replaced by the p_T of the track.

Figure 3.4: The trajectory in frame L and L': the blue line with the arrow indicates the motion of the photon, and the orange line represents the converted e^\pm track.

In order to find the conversion point, we use the fact that all photons are emitted in the radial direction from the event vertex, which means the direction of the velocity (momentum) of both the e^+ and e^- tracks should also be along the radial direction. Therefore, at $t = t_f$ when the particle is at its conversion point, the following condition holds:

$$v_\phi(t_f) = r(t_f)\Delta\dot{\phi}(t_f) = 0 \quad (3.12)$$

For external conversions the conversion point is not at the vertex, $r(t_f) \neq 0$, thus Eq. 3.12 can be simplified to

$$\Delta\dot{\phi}(t_f) = 0 \quad (3.13)$$

By finding the root of Eq. 3.13, we obtain t_f . Then, with full initial con-

ditions $\{\alpha, \phi_{DC}, p_T\}$, the conversion point can be determined:

$$\begin{cases} r_{conv} = r(t_f) \\ \phi_{conv} = \Delta\phi_{conv} + \phi_{DC} = \Delta\phi(t_f) + \phi_{DC} \end{cases} \quad (3.14)$$

which can be simplified to the following form in the L' frame:

$$\begin{cases} r_{conv} = r(t_f) \\ \phi_{conv} = \Delta\phi(t_f) \end{cases} \quad (3.15)$$

3.2.2 Proof of Principle using Mathematica

In this section, we will solve the equation of motion for single tracks and extract the correlations between the DC information and conversion point information using the Mathematica package. After obtaining the analytical/numerical form of such correlations, r_{conv} can be solved using a pair of e^+e^- tracks by requiring the two tracks share the same conversion point; p_T can be calculated once r_{conv} is determined. At the end, we will check the reconstruction resolution by comparing the true and reconstructed conversion position in Monte Carlo simulation.

3.2.2.1 Look-up table for $\{\alpha, p_T, r_{conv}, \Delta\phi_{conv}\}$

Following the prescription described in Sec. 3.2.1.2, we notice that for given values of $\{\alpha, p_T\}$, the conversion point $\{r_{conv}, \Delta\phi_{conv}\}$ can be calculated. In order to find the correlations between those quantities, the first step is to create a look-up table for those four values. To create the look-up table, we input the initial conditions and magnetic field map into Mathematica and solve the equations of motion for conversion tracks.

B field The B field was taken from the central arm field map with the “++” configuration (see Sec. 2.2.3.1). Since B_ϕ and B_r are much smaller than B_z , and B_z mainly depends on r , our previous assumption that the B field can be denoted as $B_z(r)$ holds. We extract the B field for $z = 0$ and $\phi = 0$ and interpolate between the points using Mathematica. The interpolation function gives us the explicit form of $B_z(r)$. The original B field points and the interpolation function are shown in Fig. 3.5.

Calculation details and calculation range for $\{\alpha, p_T\}$ In order to create the look-up table, we set $\{\alpha, p_T\}$ to arbitrary values, then solve the differential

Figure 3.5: The red dash lines are the field strength from the “++” magnetic field map, and the blue curve is the interpolation function.

equations of Eq. 3.7 and Eq. 3.8. We set the range of flight time between 0-20 ns. With the solutions for $r(t)$ and $\phi(t)$, we calculate t_f by finding the root of Eq. 3.13. In order to simplify the root-finding procedure, we only consider conversions falling in the first quadrant. Plugging t_f back into $r(t)$ and $\phi(t)$, we obtain r_{conv} and $\Delta\phi_{conv}$.

We further limit the p_T values for fixed α values to ensure that there is a root for Eq. 3.13, and hence a $\{r_{conv}, \Delta\phi_{conv}\}$ solution exists. The p_T range is also constrained by the r_{conv} range. In this thesis, we only consider conversions between a radius of 0 to 25 cm (the outer shell/gas enclosure of the VTX detector). This range was limited as most of the material budget between the event vertex and the DC detector is located in this region, and it sets both upper and lower limits on p_T as shown in Fig. 3.6. Besides the p_T range, we also set the α range to be between 0 and 0.6 rad to shorten the calculation time.

Creating the lookup table To create the lookup table for $\{\alpha, p_T, r_{conv}, \Delta\phi_{conv}\}$, we step through α values from 0 to 0.6 with step size of 0.01. For each α , we calculate the p_T range (see in Fig. 3.7), and then loop over p_T in that range.

After establishing the p_T range, we choose 20 different p_T points that are equidistant from each other in $\frac{1}{p_T}$ phase space. Then for every combination of α and p_T we calculate the corresponding r_{conv} and ϕ_{conv} , thus creating our look-up table. Fig. 3.8 shows a small fraction of the look-up table. For an individual track with a given α , there is no unique solution for r_{conv} , but only

Figure 3.6: Illustration of the p_T range for a certain α : the blue curve corresponds to a track with p_T larger than the upper limit, for which there is no solution for the conversion point; the red curve corresponds to a track with p_T smaller than the lower limit, for which the conversion point falls outside the outer shell of the VTX.

a possible range.

3.2.2.2 A Pair of Tracks and the Conversion Point

In order to reconstruct the conversion point we use two tracks, one e^+ track and one e^- track. Once the conversion point is determined, we calculate the p_T for both tracks. The key is that the two tracks must intersect each other at the conversion point.

Parameterization of $\Delta\phi_{conv}$ and p_T as a function of (α, r_{conv}) To solve for the conversion point, we first need to parameterize $\Delta\phi_{conv}$ and p_T as a function of α and r_{conv} . This can be done by either interpolating between the points in the look-up table or by fitting them with a function. For the interpolation, the resolution should be no worse than that of the $\Delta\phi_{conv}(\alpha, r_{conv})$ grids from the look-up table, which is around 0.01 rad. We can also fit it with

Figure 3.7: p_T range for different α : $pl(\alpha)$ stands for the lower limit for p_T , and $pu(\alpha)$ stands for the upper limit for p_T .

a rational function like:

$$\Delta\phi_{conv} = \frac{-0.000563615 + 1.98033\alpha + 0.00722406r - 0.947033\alpha r - 0.770467\alpha^2 - 0.0128542r^2}{1 - 0.377809\alpha + 0.913216r - 0.848801\alpha r - 0.142\alpha^2 + 0.140344r^2} \quad (3.16)$$

where all the coefficients are determined by fitting in Mathematica.

Fig. 3.9 shows the interpolation, the fitting and the difference between them, from which we can see the fitting function is at most 0.0004 rad off from the interpolation result. Although there can be an offset up to 0.0004 rad (~ 0.02 degree), this offset is small compared with the multiple scattering effect. Since it is much easier to use a fitting function, we choose Eq. 3.16 as the parameterization of $\Delta\phi_{conv}$ for the later analysis.

In addition, p_T is also parameterized as a function of (α, r_{conv}) . If we figure out r_{conv} for the conversion, then $p_T(\alpha, r_{conv})$ will be the reconstructed momentum under the new reconstruction algorithm. The fitting function for p_T is:

$$p_T = \frac{159827 - 17737.8\alpha + 28681.6r + 3088.24\alpha r + 26132.8\alpha^2 - 96682r^2}{1 + 1542424.242\alpha - 17.7326r + 276875\alpha r - 170012\alpha^2 + 58.7012r^2} \quad (3.17)$$

Solving for r_{conv} and ϕ_{conv} With this parameterization, the trick we play to solve for r_{conv} is to assign the $e^+ - e^-$ tracks an assumed conversion radius r , and reconstruct them to that radius. The two tracks must intersect each other at the real conversion point. That means, to solve for the true conversion

```

{0.3, 0.350595, 0.0108278, 0.591457}
{0.3, 0.349945, 0.0571723, 0.557344}
{0.3, 0.349297, 0.0800786, 0.541148}
{0.3, 0.348652, 0.0977134, 0.528962}
{0.3, 0.348009, 0.112591, 0.518873}
{0.3, 0.347369, 0.125702, 0.510129}
{0.3, 0.346731, 0.137551, 0.502345}
{0.3, 0.346095, 0.148444, 0.495285}

```

Figure 3.8: A small fraction of the lookup table for $\{\alpha, p_T, r_{conv}, \Delta\phi_{conv}\}$: the first column is α in units of rad, the second column is p_T in units of GeV, the third column is r_{conv} in units of meter, and the last column is $\Delta\phi_{conv}$ in units of rad.

Figure 3.9: The left plot shows the interpolation of $\phi_{conv}(\alpha, r_{conv})$, the middle shows the fitting function of $\phi_{conv}(\alpha, r_{conv})$, the right shows the difference between the two.

radius, we only need to find at which radius the two tracks overlap each other, and that overlapping point is the true conversion point.

More specifically, we first assume the e^+ and e^- tracks originate from the same radius r and reconstruct them back with that assumption. The azimuthal angle difference between the two tracks at that radius would be (as shown in Fig. 3.10):

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta\phi &= \phi_{conv}(\alpha^{e^+}, \phi_{DC}^{e^+}, r) - \phi_{conv}(\alpha^{e^-}, \phi_{DC}^{e^-}, r) \\
&= (\Delta\phi_{conv}(\alpha^{e^+}, r) + \phi_{DC}^{e^+}) - (\Delta\phi_{conv}(\alpha^{e^-}, r) + \phi_{DC}^{e^-})
\end{aligned} \tag{3.18}$$

If r is the true conversion radius, then $\delta\phi$ should be 0 because the two tracks should intersect each other. That means the root of the following equation should be the true conversion radius, r_{conv} , if it exists.

$$\delta\phi(\alpha^{e^+}, \phi_{DC}^{e^+}, \alpha^{e^-}, \phi_{DC}^{e^-}, r) = 0 \tag{3.19}$$

Plugging r_{conv} back into the expression for $\phi_{conv}(\alpha^{e^+}, \phi_{DC}^{e^+}, r)$ or $\phi_{conv}(\alpha^{e^-}, \phi_{DC}^{e^-}, r)$,

Figure 3.10: Two tracks are reconstructed to the same radius r and $\delta\phi$ is the azimuthal angle difference between the two. $\delta\phi$ is zero at the conversion point.

we obtain the conversion angle ϕ_{conv} . Fig. 3.11 gives an example of solving for r_{conv} and ϕ_{conv} with this method. In Fig. 3.11, the reconstructed conversion radius r_{conv} is less than 2 cm off from the true conversion radius.

Figure 3.11: The left plot shows a e^+e^- pair generated in PISA, where the true conversion radius is $r_{conv} = 17$ cm. The right plot is the root finding process in Mathematica, where the reconstructed conversion radius is $r_{conv} = 18.85$ cm.

3.2.2.3 z direction

So far, we have only discussed the motion and reconstruction of e^+e^- pairs in the $x - y$ plane. Let us now look at the z direction. As we have discussed in Sec. 3.2.1.1, the charged particle will move uniformly in the z direction, if we assume B_ϕ and B_r are negligible. The projection of both tracks on the $r - z$ plane would look like Fig. 3.12.

From Fig. 3.12 we conclude that if the e^+ and e^- tracks are from the same photon conversion, their z_{DC} position at the DC should be equal, meaning:

$$dz_{DC} = z_{DC}^{e^+} - z_{DC}^{e^-} \approx 0 \quad (3.20)$$

3.2.2.4 Resolution of Reconstructed Conversion Points

To test the new reconstruction algorithm, we compare the reconstructed conversion position to the true conversion position in the Monte Carlo simulation. We generate single photon events and feed them through PISA. We select the events with photon conversions, calculate the conversion position using the parameterization from Mathematica and Eq. 3.19, and then compare the reconstructed conversion position with the true conversion position in the transverse plane and z direction, respectively.

Figure 3.12: Tracks from photon conversion in the $r - z$ plane.

Transverse plane Single photon events are generated uniformly in $\frac{1}{p_T}$ from 200 MeV/c to 5 GeV/c. The pseudorapidity η is set to 0 so that particles will be confined to the $x - y$ plane. The e^+e^- pairs from any photon conversion are recorded. The difference between the true and reconstructed conversion point is shown in Fig. 3.13, where we can see that ϕ_{conv} is reconstructed with a resolution of 3.9 mrad and that r_{conv} is reconstructed with a resolution of 1.94 cm

Figure 3.13: The difference between the reconstructed conversion position and true conversion position.

z direction To determine how well our new reconstruction algorithm works in the z direction, we again simulate single photon events uniformly in $\frac{1}{p_T}$ from 200 MeV/ c to 5 GeV/ c , but with an extended η range of $[-0.35, 0.35]$. The z difference at the DC is shown in Fig. 3.14. From Fig. 3.14 we can see that

Figure 3.14: The difference between the z positions of the e^\pm at the DC.

indeed z_{DC}^+ is close to z_{DC}^- within an RMS of about 6 cm. The relatively wide spread of the dz_{DC} distribution results from multiple scattering and the non-vanishing radial magnetic field component that deflects the charged particles in the z direction. The z -match between the two tracks can be considerably improved by taking the z -deflection into account, which will be implemented in the next section using the full 3D magnetic map.

3.2.3 Implementation in the PHENIX Reconstruction Framework

To demonstrate the feasibility of the new conversion reconstruction algorithm, several assumptions and approximations are made to simplify the problem. For example:

- The magnetic field is simplified to be $B_z(r)$ so that the motion in the transverse plane is separated from the z direction.
- The lookup table is generated with a relatively coarse grid compared to the detector resolution (the step size for α is 0.01 rad, with only 20 p_T

points for each α).

- The interpolation of $\Delta\phi_{conv}(\alpha, r_{conv})$ is done by fitting globally with a second order rational function, since the resolution fluctuates a lot at different (α, r_{conv}) points.

Such limitations can be overcome by generating a fine-grid 3D lookup table using the PISA simulation software and performing a local non-linear grid interpolation to obtain $\phi_{conv}(\alpha, r_{conv})$. The procedures for producing the new 3D lookup table and performing a local interpolation are described in the coming sections, followed by a performance test after the implementing the above improvements into the PHENIX reconstruction framework.

3.2.3.1 3D Lookup Table for $\{r_{conv}, \theta_{conv}, p, \alpha, \Delta\phi_{conv}, \Delta z_{DC}\}$

To create the new look-up table we generate conversion e^- s at different momentum p from different conversion positions $(r_{conv}, \phi_{conv}, \theta_{conv})$, and then swim them through the full magnetic field map until they get registered in the DC/PC1. This way, the full information about the magnetic field is used. In this simulation setup, the multiple scattering and bremsstrahlung are turned off, so the particles will only interact with the magnetic field and the tracking detectors.

Since the z direction motion is now correlated with the transverse plane motion, we need more variables to describe a single track in the look-up table. For the input, we first need to choose a z_{vertex} position to settle the reference frame. Because the initial direction of the charged tracks is radial, in addition to the z_{vertex} there are only four input variables $\{r_{conv}, \phi_{conv}, \theta_{conv}, p\}$. As for the output, only one extra variable is added, which is z_{DC} . Putting together the input and output, there will be eight columns in the lookup table $\{z_{vertex}, r_{conv}, \phi_{conv}, \theta_{conv}, p, \alpha, \phi_{DC}, z_{DC}\}$. This large look-up table is both time and space consuming.

Fortunately, like in the simplified 2D case, the number of variables can be reduced based on the symmetries of the system. By assuming ϕ symmetry, ϕ_{conv} and ϕ_{DC} can be replaced by $\Delta\phi_{conv} = \phi_{conv} - \phi_{DC}$. Similarly, by assuming z_{vertex} symmetry, z_{vertex} and z_{DC} can be replaced by $\Delta z_{DC} = z_{DC} - z_{vertex}$. With these assumptions, there are only six columns left in the lookup table $\{r_{conv}, \theta_{conv}, p, \alpha, \Delta\phi_{conv}, \Delta z_{DC}\}$.

3.2.3.2 Local fit of $\Delta\phi_{conv}, \theta_{conv}, p$ as a function of $(\alpha, \Delta z_{DC}, r_{conv})$

Analogous to the procedures described in Sec. 3.2.2.2 to search for r_{conv} using the lookup table, we need to interpolate $\Delta\phi_{conv}$ as a function of $(\alpha, \Delta z_{DC}, r_{conv})$

and solve the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\phi &= \phi_{conv}(\alpha^{e^+}, \phi_{DC}^{e^+}, \Delta z_{DC}^{e^+}, r) - \phi_{conv}(\alpha^{e^-}, \phi_{DC}^{e^-}, \Delta z_{DC}^{e^-}, r) \\ 0 &= (\Delta\phi_{conv}(\alpha^{e^+}, \Delta z_{DC}^{e^+}, r) + \phi_{DC}^{e^+}) - (\Delta\phi_{conv}(\alpha^{e^-}, \Delta z_{DC}^{e^-}, r) + \phi_{DC}^{e^-}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.21)$$

If the e^+e^- pair originates from the same pair production process, the root of Eq. 3.21 will be real and be equal to the true (reconstructed) conversion radius r_{conv} .

In the Mathematica approach, we used a global fitting function on the whole lookup table to interpolate. In the new setup, we choose a local fit to have better control over fluctuations of the fit result. Another advantage of the local fit is that it is no longer necessary to guess an appropriate functional form for the fitting function. Rather than fitting the whole lookup table, we only fit the entries in phase space $(\alpha \pm \delta\alpha, r_{conv} \pm \delta r_{conv}, z_{DC} \pm \delta z_{DC})$ with second order polynomials. In principle, $\delta\alpha$ and δr_{conv} should be small to ensure the quality of the second order polynomial fit, yet they cannot be too small because we need enough grid points to perform the fitting. In addition, they need to be larger than the resolution. Taking all these aspects into consideration, $\delta\alpha$ is set to 0.01 rad, δr_{conv} is set to 2 cm, and δz_{DC} is set to 4 cm.

Similar interpolations are done on p and θ_{conv} . By plugging $(\alpha, \Delta z_{DC}, r_{conv})$ into the interpolation functions, we can obtain the 3D conversion position and momentum p of the e^\pm tracks.

3.2.3.3 Test Result with PISA

After integrating the new 3D lookup table, local fit and r_{conv} searching procedures into the PHENIX reconstruction framework, we did another performance test using the Monte Carlo simulation, as described in Sec. 3.2.2.4. The reconstruction resolutions of the new implementation are shown in the following sections.

$p_T^{e^\pm}$ reconstruction To test if this new implementation improves the reconstructed $p_T^{e^\pm}$, we compare $p_T^{e^\pm}$ from different reconstruction schemes with the true $p_T^{e^\pm}$. We use a single photon simulation. All e^\pm s from photon conversions are with fixed $p_T = 0.8$ GeV, and convert at a fixed azimuthal angle $\phi = 0.5$ rad. The particles are confined to the XY plane. Different conversion radii are set to check the r_{conv} dependence on p_T .

The result is shown in Fig. 3.15. One important feature of Fig. 3.15 is the mean of the peaks shift to the positive side when using the standard reconstruction when the conversion radius increases, while the mean stays around 0 when using the new reconstruction. The significant shift in the

Figure 3.15: The plots show the difference between the reconstructed p_T and true p_T under three reconstruction schemes. Different plot represent different conversion radii.

standard reconstruction is due to the fact that the conversion radius is always assumed to be 0 there. This means the reconstructed trajectory travels longer in the magnetic field in the standard reconstruction, and to ensure the same bending angle α , p_T is reconstructed higher than the true p_T . The larger the true conversion radius is, the larger this difference will be. Another feature is that the peak widths are similar, which is because the spread of the peaks is mainly due to detector resolution (especially in the α measurement), multiple scattering and bremsstrahlung, which are not related to the reconstruction procedure we choose.

Fig. 3.16 shows the difference between the reconstructed and true p_T as a function of conversion radius for the various reconstruction procedures, as well as the result if using the Mathematica implementation. As can be seen from the plots, when using the new 2D lookup table generated by GEANT, the p_T is reconstructed closer to true p_T .

3.2.4 Conversion Selection Cuts

Now that we have established a new algorithm to reconstruct photon conversions, we need to ask what purity can be achieved – in other words, how well can we distinguish the true external photon conversions (signal) from other sources (background). We consider the combinatorial background as the ma-

Figure 3.16: In the left plot, the new reconstruction is done using the 2D lookup table generated by GEANT. In the right plot, the new reconstruction is done using the 2D lookup table generated by Mathematica. The central points represent the mean value of the relative difference from the true p_T , with the error bar indicating the peak width.

major source that contaminates our photon sample, where a conversion point is accidentally reconstructed for two tracks not from the same photon conversion. We will study how and to what degree the new reconstruction algorithm can suppress that background.

3.2.4.1 Pair Cut Candidates

In previous PHENIX analyses, a common method to select (or reject) photon conversions was to use the orientation of the opening angle with respect to the magnetic field. The standard tracking algorithm assumes all the tracks originate from the event vertex. Pairs from external photon conversions will be reconstructed with an artificial opening angle. This opening angle will always be in the plane perpendicular to the axial magnetic field (radial component negligible), while combinatorial e^+e^- pairs will be oriented randomly with respect to the magnetic field. Therefore, the orientation of the opening angle can be used for the background suppression. To quantify the orientation of

the opening angle, we use ϕ_V described in [114, 122]:

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{\mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{p}_2}{|\mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{p}_2|}, \quad \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{p}_1 \times \mathbf{p}_2 \quad (3.22)$$

$$\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{v}, \quad \mathbf{u}_a = \frac{\mathbf{u} \times \hat{z}}{|\mathbf{u} \times \hat{z}|} \quad (3.23)$$

$$\phi_V = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{u}_a}{|\mathbf{w}| |\mathbf{u}_a|} \right) \quad (3.24)$$

where \mathbf{p}_1 and \mathbf{p}_2 are the three momentum vectors of the electron and positron. The conversion pairs have ϕ_V either near 0° or 180° , while the random e^+e^- pairs and e^+e^- pairs from hadron decays around the event vertex have a random ϕ_V distribution.

Besides the ϕ_V cut, the new reconstruction algorithm offers some new possible cuts to suppress background in the conversion sample. In the transverse plane, if the e^+e^- pair is from a photon conversion, there should be a solution for r_{conv} and ϕ_{conv} , and the reconstructed conversion point should be located where the material is. On the contrary, if the e^+ and e^- are not from the same photon conversion, we expect no solution for r_{conv} and ϕ_{conv} or a solution that is not correlated with where the material is located in the experiment. That means we can cut on r_{conv} and ϕ_{conv} to eliminate random e^+e^- pairs.

As for the z direction, we know that for e^+ and e^- tracks from the same photon conversion, the difference in their z position at the DC, dz_{DC} , will be close to 0 for the signal, while dz_{DC} should be some random value for the background.

3.2.4.2 Determining Cut Values

To find out where we should cut quantitatively, we can compare the distributions of ϕ_V , r_{conv} , etc. of the foreground (all the e^+e^- pairs) and background (random e^+e^- combinations) when no cuts are applied. To simulate the foreground and background, we create events containing 280 π^0 s and pass them through the simulated PHENIX detector system using the PISA software. The input π^0 p_T distribution is extracted from fitting the measured charged and neutral pion spectrum in the most central (0-10%) Au + Au collisions at 200 GeV [25, 123, 124] using a modified Hagedorn function [125]:

$$E \frac{d^3N}{d^3p} = \frac{c}{(\exp(-ap_T - bp_T^2) + p_T/p_0)^n} \quad (3.25)$$

The extracted parameters are shown in the first five columns of Tab. 3.1. The last column is the integrated π^0 yield calculated from the parameterization.

c [[GeV/c ⁻²]]	a [[GeV/c ⁻¹]]	b [[GeV/c ⁻²]]	p_0 [[GeV/c]]	n	dN_{π^0}/dy
1331.0	0.5654	0.1945	0.7429	8.274	280.9

Table 3.1: Fit parameters of the measured pion p_T spectrum in 0-10% Au + Au collisions at 200 GeV [109].

We applied the electron identification cuts used in the real data analysis to select candidate single e^+/e^- tracks. The details of the cuts can be found in Sec. 4.2.2. The distribution of pair selection variables for the foreground (FG) and background (BG) is shown in Fig. 3.17 when no pair cuts are applied. We want to cut out the region where BG/FG is large.

Figure 3.17: Distribution of ϕ_V , r_{conv} , ϕ_{conv} , dz_{DC} , $\frac{p_T^+ t_f^+}{p_T^- t_f^-}$, $\frac{|p_T^+ - p_T^-|}{p_T^+ + p_T^-}$ with no cuts; in each plot, the blue line represents the foreground, and the red line represents the background.

Based on Fig. 3.17, we choose the following cuts:

- $0 < \phi_V < 0.05$
- $8cm < r_{conv} < 25cm$
- $|dz_{DC}| < 5cm$

- $-0.4 < \phi < 0.6$ or $2.4 < \phi < 3.5$

To test these new cuts, we plot the m_{vtx} distribution with/without cuts and calculate the background/foreground (BG/FG) ratio for every case. The mass distributions are shown in Fig. 3.18 for two mass ranges: 0 to 1 GeV and 40 to 160 MeV, which correspond to the range we expect for the photon conversions from the silicon-stripixel layers. The sub-panels correspond to different cut combinations that are given in Table 3.2. The last column of the table gives the BG/FG ratio in the region of interest 40-160 MeV. Integrated over all the generated p_T , the purity (defined as $1-\text{BG/FG}$) of the conversion sample is larger than 99% after all cuts are applied.

$\phi_V \in [0, 0.5]$	$r_{conv} \in [8, 25]cm$	$dz_{DC} \in [-5, 5]cm$	$\phi_{conv} \in [-0.4, 0.6]$ or $[2.4, 3.5]$	BG/FG
				%71.1
✓				%26.0
	✓			%37.8
		✓		%23.4
			✓	%18.9
✓	✓	✓	✓	%0.6

Table 3.2: BG/FG ratio under different cuts. BG/FG is calculated from 40-160 MeV mass window.

The cuts described above give a conversion sample with very good purity but suffer from large efficiency loss. In the real data analysis, we can afford some background in the conversion sample because it can be subtracted statistically via the event mixing technique (see Sec. 3.3.2.1). However, too much background can induce some additional systematic uncertainty. To choose an optimized set of cuts which balance the statistical and systematic uncertainties of the direct photon measurement, we keep different sets of conversion selection cuts to obtain conversion samples with varying statistics and purity levels and compare the results at the end. The details of each set of pair cuts are listed below (from low to high purity):

loose cut

- e^+e^- tracks fall into the same arm of the DC
- there is a solution for r_{conv} and ϕ_{conv} when searching for the conversion position for the e^+e^- pair

Figure 3.18: In each plot, the blue line is the FG and red line is the BG. Plots (a)-(c) show the full-scale $m_{V\text{TX}}$ distribution, while plots (d)-(f) zoom in from 0 to 160 MeV.

dzed cut

- loose cut
- $|dz_{DC}| < 4 \text{ cm}$

default cut

- loose cut

- $|dz_{DC}| < 4$ cm
- $\phi_V < 0.1$ rad
- 9 cm $< r_{conv} < 23$ cm
- $|\theta^{e^+} - \theta^{e^-}| < 0.01$ rad (at the conversion point)

tight cut

- loose cut
- $|dz_{DC}| < 2$ cm
- $\phi_V < 0.1$ rad
- 10 cm $< r_{conv} < 20$ cm
- $|\theta^{e^+} - \theta^{e^-}| < 0.006$ rad (at the conversion point)

3.3 Direct Photon Signal R_γ

One of the most important observables to measure the direct photon signal is R_γ , which is defined as follows:

$$R_\gamma = \frac{\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}} \quad (3.26)$$

where γ^{incl} is the yield of all the photons emitted from collisions, and γ^{hadron} is yield of photons from hadronic decays. $R_\gamma > 1$ indicates there are direct photons produced, and the direct photon yield γ^{direct} can be constructed from R_γ and γ^{hadron} :

$$\gamma^{\text{direct}} = (R_\gamma - 1)\gamma^{\text{hadron}} \quad (3.27)$$

A R_γ measurement usually exhibits much smaller experimental uncertainties compared to a direct photon yield γ^{direct} measurement, because the common uncertainties for γ^{incl} and γ^{hadron} cancel out in the ratio.

3.3.1 Double Ratio Tagging Method

Because more than 80% of hadronic decay photons are from the $\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma + \gamma$ decay and π^0 can be well reconstructed with the highly segmented EMCal in PHENIX, it is preferable to measure $\left(\frac{\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}}\right)_{\text{Data}}$ from the real data and replace the single ratio form by a double ratio form in the R_γ measurement:

$$R_\gamma = \frac{\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}} = \frac{\left(\frac{\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}}\right)_{\text{Data}}}{\left(\frac{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}}\right)_{\text{Sim}}} \quad (3.28)$$

where the denominator $\left(\frac{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}}\right)_{\text{Sim}}$ is estimated from simulation in order to account for other decay photon sources (mainly the η decay contribution). Such a simulation contains a ‘‘cocktail’’ of hadronic photon sources (π^0 , η , ω , η' etc); hence it is often referred to as the cocktail simulation, and the obtained $\left(\frac{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}}\right)_{\text{Sim}}$ is called the cocktail ratio.

The numerator $\left(\frac{\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}}\right)_{\text{Data}}$ corresponds to the π^0 decay photon contribution in the total inclusive photon yield. In this analysis, we use a tagging method to determine the $\left(\frac{\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}}\right)_{\text{Data}}$ term, which is illustrated by Fig. 3.19. We first measure a subset of inclusive photons, in our case the reconstructed conversions

at the VTX detector, and calculate the raw yield* of the inclusive photon (conversion) sample N_γ^{incl} . The measurement of N_γ^{incl} is shown in Fig. 3.19a. The relationship between the raw counts of the conversion sample N_γ^{incl} and the yield of all photons γ^{incl} is expressed by:

$$N_\gamma^{\text{incl}} = \gamma^{\text{incl}} \cdot p_{\text{conv}} \cdot a_{e^+e^-} \cdot \epsilon_{e^+e^-} \quad (3.29)$$

where p_{conv} is the probability for a photon to convert to an e^+e^- pair, $a_{e^+e^-}$ is the acceptance for the e^+e^- pairs to fall into the tracking system, and $\epsilon_{e^+e^-}$ is efficiency of reconstructing the accepted e^+e^- pairs.

The majority of N_γ^{incl} are π^0 decay photons. To quantify this contribution, the conversions are paired with a second photon measured by the calorimeter and those forming an invariant mass near the π^0 mass are tagged as π^0 decay photons, denoted as $N_\gamma^{\pi^0, \text{tag}}$. The measurement of $N_\gamma^{\pi^0, \text{tag}}$ is shown in Fig. 3.19b. The relationship between the raw counts of the tagged photon sample $N_\gamma^{\pi^0, \text{tag}}$ and the yield of all π^0 decay photons γ^{π^0} is expressed as:

$$N_\gamma^{\pi^0, \text{tag}} = \gamma^{\pi^0} \cdot p_{\text{conv}} \cdot a_{e^+e^-} \cdot \epsilon_{e^+e^-} \cdot \langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle \quad (3.30)$$

where $p_{\text{conv}} \cdot a_{e^+e^-} \cdot \epsilon_{e^+e^-}$ corresponds to the probability of one of the decay photons ($\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma + \gamma$) converting and being measured by the tracking system (like Eq. 3.29), and $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$ corresponds to the probability of the second decay photon from the π^0 decay falling into the EMCal acceptance f and being successfully reconstructed with efficiency ϵ_γ . Note that $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$ is a conditional acceptance and efficiency correction which requires one photon from the π^0 decay to be reconstructed as a conversion pair in the first place. $\langle \rangle$ means averaging over the distribution of the second decay photon.

Combining Eq. 3.29 and Eq. 3.30, we obtain:

$$\left(\frac{N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{N_\gamma^{\pi^0, \text{tag}}} \right)_{\text{Data}} = \frac{\gamma^{\text{incl}} \cdot \cancel{p_{\text{conv}}} \cdot \cancel{a_{e^+e^-}} \cdot \cancel{\epsilon_{e^+e^-}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0} \cdot \cancel{p_{\text{conv}}} \cdot \cancel{a_{e^+e^-}} \cdot \cancel{\epsilon_{e^+e^-}} \cdot \langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle} = \frac{\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0} \cdot \langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle} \quad (3.31)$$

As a result, R_γ can be rewritten as:

$$R_\gamma = \frac{\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}} = \frac{\left(\frac{\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}} \right)_{\text{Data}}}{\left(\frac{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}} \right)_{\text{Sim}}} = \frac{\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle \left(\frac{N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{N_\gamma^{\pi^0, \text{tag}}} \right)_{\text{Data}}}{\left(\frac{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}} \right)_{\text{Sim}}} \quad (3.32)$$

*Raw yield means the observed raw counts of certain particles uncorrected for effects like luminosity, detector acceptance, efficiency etc...

Figure 3.19: Schematic view of (a) the raw inclusive photon (i.e. conversions at the VTX, see figure insert) measurement and (b) the conversions tagged as coming from a π^0 decay.

The R_γ measurement is now decomposed into the following three ingredients, and their contributions are illustrated in Fig. 3.20.

- **Raw yield ratio from data:** $\frac{N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{N_{\gamma^{\pi^0, \text{tag}}}}$
- **Conditional acceptance and efficiency:** $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$
- **Cocktail ratio:** $\frac{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}}$

3.3.2 Proof of Principle with Pseudo-data

In this section we will describe the detailed procedures for measuring N_γ^{incl} and $N_{\gamma^{\pi^0, \text{tag}}}$ using the 280 π^0 simulation introduced in Sec. 3.2.4.2, which is referred to as pseudo-data in the following section. The $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ setup and calculation is discussed afterwards using the embedded single π^0 simulation. At the end, we calculate R_γ of the pseudo-data:

$$R_\gamma^{\text{pseudo}} = \frac{N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{N_{\gamma^{\pi^0, \text{tag}}}} \times \langle \epsilon f \rangle \quad (3.33)$$

Since there are no direct photons in the pseudo-data, R_γ^{pseudo} should be equal to 1 by construction. Therefore if the calculated $R_\gamma^{\text{pseudo}} = 1$, it will validate the principle and details of the double ratio tagging method.

Figure 3.20: Cartoon illustration of different components in the conversion photon sample.

3.3.2.1 Raw Yield N_γ^{incl}

To obtain the raw yield of N_γ^{incl} , we first pair an e^+ with an e^- and apply the conversion selection cuts. The conversion candidates form the so-called foreground sample (FG). As shown by Fig. 3.21, the FG contains both the signal (SG) we want to measure – real conversions – and some background (BG) contamination – “fake” conversions.

- **FG:** all the e^+e^- pairs passing the conversion selection cuts (all the conversion candidates).
- **BG:** random e^+e^- pairs (fake conversions).
- **SG:** e^+e^- pairs from real conversions (real conversions).

As discussed in Sec. 3.2.4, these “fake” conversions come from random combinations of e^+ and e^- pairs from different photon conversions. Such a background is often referred to as combinatorial background, and increases drastically with multiplicity. Although a large amount of the random combinations are removed after applying the conversion selection cuts, there is still some background left in the conversion sample. We need to evaluate and subtract this background before extracting N_γ^{incl} .

Figure 3.21: Cartoon illustration of FG, BG and SG conversion pairs.

With the true information available in the simulation framework, we can easily identify if a conversion candidate is a real conversion or not by looking at the particle ancestry. The invariant mass distribution of the FG, BG and SG pairs are shown in the left panel of Fig. 3.22 to Fig. 3.23, where the pair mass m_{ee} is constructed by Eq. 3.3. In this analysis, we choose the m_{ee} window 40-120 MeV as the signal counting window. Therefore N_{γ}^{incl} is defined as the number of real conversions in $40 < m_{ee} < 120$ MeV, which can be calculated using $N_{\text{SG}} = N_{\text{FG}} - N_{\text{BG}}$.

However, in the real data analysis, we do not have the true information of the detected particles to identify signal from background. Instead, an event mixing technique is adopted to estimate the combinatorial background contribution. The BG obtained using event mixing is shown in the middle panel of Fig. 3.22 to Fig. 3.23, and we will discuss in detail how the event mixing is

constructed and normalized in the next paragraph.

Background estimation via event mixing technique The event mixing technique is a method of combining particles from different events to estimate the combinatorial/uncorrelated background [126–128]. To construct the background in the conversion sample using event mixing, we pick an electron (positron) from event 1 and pair it with a positron (electron) from event 2. The basic idea is that by making pairs from different events, the correlations (in this analysis, the pair properties from the same photon conversion) between the e^+e^- pairs will be broken, while the effect of the detector acceptance and event topology (bulk/statistical, momentum distribution, angular distribution) properties will be preserved. After applying the same conversion selection cuts as the foreground, we can get the distribution of the mixed e^+e^- pairs. The event mixing technique can provide a very high statistical accuracy if one uses a large number of mixed events. However, it only gives the shape of the background distribution and needs to be properly normalized to the background level in the foreground sample.

To normalize the event mixing background, we utilize the “side band” method. With this method, one first picks a range of the m_{ee} distribution where there is no signal in the foreground sample (a “side band” outside the signal range) and then normalizes the event mixing background so that the event mixing background distribution overlaps with the foreground distribution in that side band ranges. Here we use the higher m_{ee} range ($>\sim 0.2$ GeV) as the normalization side band. The normalization is obtained by requiring the integral of pairs to be the same for the FG and BG in the side band. Such a side band is only prominent in the conversion sample after the loose cut selection, and the normalization for the other cut cases is assumed to be the same as for the loose cut. This assumption proven to hold by comparing the true info to the normalized event mixing result for the other cut cases, as shown in Fig. 3.24. Fig. 3.24 shows the comparison of the extracted N_γ^{incl} as a function of conversion photon p_T using both the event mixing technique and the true information. We observe an $\sim 1\%$ discrepancy above 2 GeV in the loose cut case, while the event mixing gives very consistent results with the true information in all other tighter cut cases. This proves the correctness of the background subtraction method for the N_γ^{incl} extraction.

Figure 3.22: Invariant mass distributions of e^+e^- pairs (low p_T example).

Figure 3.23: Invariant mass distributions of e^+e^- pairs (high p_T example)

Figure 3.24: Extracted N_{γ}^{incl} as a function of conversion photon p_T using the true information (red) and event mixing technique (blue). The bottom panel shows the ratio of the event mixing result over the true information result.

3.3.2.2 Raw Yield N_γ^{tag}

Similar to the N_γ^{incl} extraction, to obtain the raw yield of N_γ^{tag} , we first pair all the conversion candidates with all the EMCal photons in the same event to get the foreground $m_{e^+e^-\gamma}$ distribution (FG) and then construct the background distribution (BG) using the event mixing technique. $m_{e^+e^-\gamma}$ is expressed by:

$$m_{ee\gamma} = 2|\mathbf{p}_\gamma^{\text{conv}}||\mathbf{p}_\gamma^{\text{EMCal}}|(1 - \cos\theta) \quad (3.34)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_\gamma^{\text{conv}}$ is the reconstructed conversion photon momentum using the new algorithm, $\mathbf{p}_\gamma^{\text{EMCal}}$ is the EMCal photon momentum, and θ is the opening angle between the two photons.

We choose $90 < m_{ee\gamma} < 190$ MeV as the signal counting window, and N_γ^{tag} is the number of π^0 s inside this window.

Background sources The background sources are slightly more complicated in the $e^+e^-\gamma$ sample as listed below and illustrated in Fig. 3.25.

- **FG:** all the $e^+e^-\gamma$ pairs (π^0 candidates).
- **BG_{uncorr}:** conversions paired with EMCal photons from other π^0 decays.
- **BG_{corr}:** fake conversions paired with EMCal photons from the same π^0 decay as one of the constituent e^\pm of the fake conversion (fake π^0 s).
- **SG:** conversions paired with EMCal photons from the same π^0 decay (real π^0 s).

We see in Fig. 3.26 that in addition to a smooth-shaped background, BG_{uncorr}, there is another type of background exhibiting a peak structure around the π^0 mass, denoted as BG_{corr}. BG_{corr} increases monotonically as a function of the background level in the conversion sample (fake conversions), and hence is the most significant in the loose cut case and lower p_T range.

Event mixing for the correlated background To estimate BG_{corr}, two event mixing setups are used. To preserve the correlation between the constituent e^\pm and decay γ from the same π^0 decay, we perform the event mixing in the following way: pick one electron track from event 1, one positron track from event 2 and pair with EMCal photons from both event 1 and 2. Such combinations contain not only the fake conversion \times correlated EMCal photon pairs (the EMCal photon from the same π^0 decay as one of the constituent e^\pm of the fake conversion), but also random combinations of fake conversion \times uncorrelated EMCal photon pairs (the EMCal photon from a different π^0

Figure 3.25: Cartoon illustration of FG, BG_{uncorr} , BG_{corr} and SG conversion-EMCal cluster pairs.

decay than the constituent e^\pm of the fake conversion), as shown in Fig. 3.27 and denoted as $BG_{\text{corr}} + BG_{\text{comb}}$. The key to obtaining the correct amount of BG_{corr} is to normalize $BG_{\text{corr}} + BG_{\text{comb}}$ correctly and subtract the corresponding BG_{comb} component. The normalization factor is calculated using:

$$\frac{BG_{ee}}{FG_{ee}} \text{ in the inclusive photon sample} = \frac{BG_{ee}}{FG_{ee}} \text{ in the tagged photon sample} \quad (3.35)$$

To estimate the combinatorial contribution BG_{comb} , we mix three events as follows: pick one electron track from event 1, one positron track from event 2, and pair them with EMCal photons from event 3. A side band method is used to normalize BG_{comb} with respect to $BG_{\text{corr}} + BG_{\text{comb}}$. The normalization mass range is chosen to be 0.65 to 1.0 GeV, and the normalization factor is

Figure 3.26: Invariant mass distributions of $e^+e^-\gamma$ pairs.

calculated using the integral ratio of $BG_{\text{corr}} + BG_{\text{comb}}$ to BG_{comb} in the chosen side band.

Event mixing for the uncorrelated background The event mixing for the BG_{uncorr} is more straightforward compared to the BG_{corr} . We simply pick a conversion e^+e^- pair from event 1 and pair with ECal photons from event 2. The event mixing result for BG_{uncorr} is shown by the red histograms in Fig. 3.27.

Because of the large BG_{uncorr}/SG ratio, we use a more careful normalization scheme for BG_{uncorr} to account for a possible mismatch between the true background shape and the event mixing shape:

1. Calculate a mass-independent normalization using the integral ratio in the side band $[0.25, 0.45]$ GeV and scale BG_{uncorr} accordingly.
2. Fit the $(FG - BG_{\text{corr}})/BG_{\text{uncorr}}$ ratio with a second order polynomial $f(m_{ee\gamma})$ excluding all the peak regions. The fit result is shown by the yellow lines

in the bottom panels of Fig. 3.27.

3. Normalize BG_{uncorr} again with the mass-dependent normalization factor $f(m_{ee\gamma})$

The new BG_{uncorr} after the two-step normalization is shown by the red filled histogram in the right panel of Fig. 3.26.

Figure 3.27: Invariant mass distributions of $e^+e^-\gamma$ pairs from the same event (FG) and different event mixing setups.

To check how well the background subtraction works using the event mixing described above, a direct comparison of the $FG-BG_{\text{uncorr}}$, BG_{corr} and $SG=FG-BG_{\text{total}}$ distributions obtained via using the true information and event mixing is shown in Fig. 3.28 and Fig. 3.29. In the end, the extracted N_{γ}^{tag} using the event mixing technique agrees mostly within 2% with the result using the true information, as shown in Fig. 3.30.

Figure 3.28: Invariant mass distributions of $e^+e^-\gamma$ pairs (low p_T example).

Figure 3.29: Invariant mass distributions of $e^+e^-\gamma$ pairs (high p_T example).

Figure 3.30: Extracted N_{γ}^{tag} as a function of conversion photon p_T using the true information (red) and event mixing technique (blue). The bottom panel shows the ratio of the event mixing result over the true information result.

3.3.2.3 Conditional Acceptance and Efficiency $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$

As discussed in Sec. 3.3.1, $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$ is the detector effect correction factor used to account for the fact that only part of the conversions from π^0 decays can be tagged due to the limited acceptance and efficiency of the second decay photon being reconstructed by the EMCal. $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$ can be extracted from the single π^0 simulation – meaning one π^0 per event – with the PISA software (see Sec. 2.2.6.1). PISA handles the decay of the π^0 and particle interactions with the detector material, such as pair creation (external photon conversion), multiple scattering, Bremsstrahlung, etc... After the PHENIX reconstruction chain, the events of interest are ones with at least one conversion e^+e^- pair in them. To get the value of $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$, we just need to measure the raw yield of N_γ^{incl} and N_γ^{tag} . $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$ is expressed by:

$$\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle = \frac{N_\gamma^{\text{tag}}}{N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}} \quad (3.36)$$

Embedded single π^0 In the single π^0 simulation setup, since the multiplicity is so low (only one π^0 per event), there is no background in both the conversion e^+e^- pairs and the $e^+e^-\gamma$ pairs. However, this multiplicity difference between the pseudo-data (280 π^0 per event) and the single π^0 event needs to be accounted for before calculating $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$ because the photon reconstruction efficiency is different when the occupancy in the detector is high (more in Sec. 4.6.2). To include the occupancy effect in the single π^0 simulation setup, we embed the single π^0 event into the pseudo-data event and calculate $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$ with this embedding setup.

$\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ calculation N_γ^{incl} can be directly extracted by counting the foreground pairs inside the signal counting window, $N_{\text{SG}} = N_{\text{FG}}$, as shown in Fig. 3.31. N_γ^{tag} is extracted using $N_{\text{SG}} = N_{\text{FG}} - N_{\text{residual}}$, as shown in Fig. 3.32. The residual background corresponds to a second order polynomial function used to describe the small tail far from the π^0 counting window. More details about the source of this residual background and the subtraction procedure are given in Sec. 4.6.5. The extracted $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ as a function of the conversion photon p_T is shown in Fig. 3.33.

3.3.2.4 R_γ of Pseudo-data

With both $\frac{N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}}{N_\gamma^{\pi^0, \text{tag}}}$ from the pseudo-data and $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ from the embedded single π^0 simulation in hand, we can now measure the direct photon signal of the

Figure 3.31: m_{ee} distribution using different conversion selection cuts in the embedded single π^0 simulation. Different colors correspond to the conversions from different r_{conv} ranges.

pseudo-data using Eq. 3.33. The results are shown in Fig. 3.34. We see that $R_{\gamma}^{\text{pseudo}}$ is within 2% of unity, which indicates the procedures we use to extract $\frac{N_{\gamma}^{\text{incl}}}{N_{\gamma^0, \text{tag}}}$ and $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ are reliable. In the next chapter we will use the same method to measure the direct photon signal in the real data.

(a) loose cut

(b) dzed cut

(c) default cut

(d) tight cut

Figure 3.32: $m_{ee\gamma}$ distribution using different conversion selection cuts in the embedded single π^0 simulation.

Figure 3.33: $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$ as a function of conversion photon p_T for loose, dzed, default, and tight cut cases.

Figure 3.34: R_γ^{pseudo} as a function of conversion photon p_T for loose, dzed, default, and tight cut cases. The red band represents $\pm 2\%$ from 1.

Chapter 4

Data Analysis

4.1 Data Sample and Trigger Condition

The data set we use consists of Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV taken in 2014 from March 15 to June 16 (first to last physics runs). With the long data taking period and high luminosity delivered by the collider, we collected very high statistics in this data set.

As introduced in Sec. 2.2.2.3, one of the key components of the minimum bias trigger is the BBC coincidence (signals from both North and South BBC), which is referred to as BBCLL1 (BBC Local Level-1 trigger) in the PHENIX experiment. For the Au+Au at 200 GeV data set taken in 2014, the BBCLL1 trigger is generated by requiring more than one tube to fire on either the south or north side of the BBC and an online z vertex[†] within ± 30 cm from the nominal interaction point. About 3.5 billion events are recorded with the BBCLL1 trigger. The Minimum Bias (MB) events can be selected using the BBCLL1 trigger and ZDC coincidence:

- BBC coincidence: BBCLL1 (>1 tube), $|z_{\text{BBC}}^{\text{online}}| < 30$ cm
- ZDC coincidence: energy deposit in ZDCN and ZDCS larger than zero, valid timing from ZDC
- $|z_{\text{BBC}}|^\ddagger < 30$ cm

The centrality is defined with the MB events by charged particle multiplicity measured by the BBC, $N_{\text{ch}}^{\text{BBC}}$, as shown in Fig. 4.1 and Fig. 4.2a by the blue histogram. The centrality distribution for events selected with such a trigger configuration is displayed in Fig. 4.2b by the blue histogram.

[†] z vertex calculated using BBC during data taking for trigger decision

[‡]Event z vertex calculated using BBC after data taking and full reconstruction of de-

Figure 4.1: Centrality definition N_{ch}^{BBC} distribution of MB events.

The majority of the events in this data set (about 19 billion events) are recorded with BBCLL1 narrowvtx trigger, which is the same as the BBCLL1 trigger described but with a narrower z vertex requirement, $|z_{BBC}^{online}| < 10$ cm (or 12 cm for part of the data). The events selected by the BBCLL1 narrowvtx trigger and ZDC coincidence are denoted as narrow vertex events. The centrality distribution for the narrow vertex events is not as flat as the MB events due to a trigger efficiency drop towards peripheral collisions, as shown in Fig. 4.2b.

Figure 4.2: Comparison of N_{ch}^{BBC} distribution and centrality distribution of MB events and narrow vertex events.

tector variables

Fig. 4.3 shows the z vertex distribution for MB events and narrow vertex events, and it can be observed that more events with z vertex around 10 cm are lost towards the peripheral collisions using the BBCLL1 narrow trigger, which is related to the worse $z_{\text{BBC}}^{\text{online}}$ resolution in low multiplicity events.

Figure 4.3: z_{BBC} distribution for MB events and narrow vertex events.

4.2 Quality Assurance

Before analyzing the data, we first performed checks to assure that the selected data sample was taken with good beam conditions and properly functioning detector subsystems. For the two main detector parts relevant in this analysis, DC and EMCal, we identified the unstable/broken channels and created a fiducial map to mask them out. In addition, calibrations are done to correct for the detector misalignment, the momentum scale from tracking systems, and the energy scale of the EMCal.

4.2.1 Global variables

In PHENIX, data is taken in units of runs. Each run corresponds to about 1 hour of data taking to ensure a manageable output file size and each run has its own run number. Larger run numbers correspond to later runs. There are different types of runs suiting different purposes: calibration runs, zero-field runs (magnetic field turned off), physics runs, etc... In this analysis, we mainly used the physics runs (405839 – 414988). Zero-field runs are important for the detector alignment check, more details can be found in Sec. 4.2.2.2.

When analyzing the physics runs, we want to avoid the bad/problematic runs where there are some issues with the detector subsystems, with the data acquisition system (DAQ) or with the beam itself. To flag such runs, we looked at a few global variables, for example number of events per run as a function of run number shown in Fig. 4.4a. Runs with $N_{\text{evt}} < 3 \times 10^5$ are marked as bad runs (a run which is too short usually had some issue during it – like unexpected beam dump, detector malfunction, etc. – and the run was terminated earlier than expected). Fig. 4.4b shows the width of the z_{BBC} distribution per run as a function of run number. One can see a drop at run 407157, which is due to a change in online narrow vertex selection from 12 cm to 10 cm.

Runs with an abnormal centrality distribution (resulting from a problematic BBC charge distribution) are also marked as bad runs, as shown by the outliers in Fig. 4.5.

Figure 4.4: (a) Number of recorded events per run as a function of run number. The red line corresponds to $N_{\text{evt}} = 3 \times 10^5$. (b) Width of z_{BBC} distribution per run as a function of run number.

Figure 4.5: MB events fraction in 0-5%, 5-40%, 40-80% and 80-93% per run as a function of run number (figure taken from [129]).

4.2.2 Tracking and Electron Identification

In this section we look more closely into the tracking and electron identification detectors to ensure the e^\pm tracks we use to reconstruct conversions are of good quality.

4.2.2.1 DC Deadmap

Detector performance can change during the data taking period, and such a change can occur for multiple reasons like loss of active areas in detectors (noisy/cold channels), unstable DAQ, high voltage change (gain change,) etc... The changes in the tracking detectors (DC and PC) and electron identification detectors (RICH and EMCal) usually lead to a change in the number of reconstructed electrons (positrons) per event, which is plotted in Fig. 4.6. The different average N_{e^\pm} corresponds to different active area/efficiency. For instance the drop in the runs marked with orange color is due to the loss of the whole south east side of RICH (high voltage issue) which gets repaired after run 413250. The runs with too low N_{e^\pm} , below 0.24, are discarded because that indicates the loss of too much of the active area of the detectors. The outliers indicate a problem in any of those detectors, like broken wires in DC, high voltage issues and so on. After cross-checking with the record of the corresponding run log, some of them are marked as bad runs and discarded.

Figure 4.6: Electrons (positrons) per event as function of run numbers. Different colors correspond to different run groups.

Run groups To avoid extra corrections and systematic uncertainties due to the acceptance and efficiency fluctuations, we looked at a 2D track rate map of tracks in α versus wire net number (board) and applied a fiducial mask to exclude tracks hitting the unstable (noisy/inefficient/dead) detector regions. Such a fiducial mask is often referred to as the DC dead map. We grouped the runs of similar conditions together and created a dead map for each run group. There are in total 8 run groups identified for the whole data set. The runs with too big of a dead area or an additional unstable area which cannot be masked out by the main run groups are considered as bad runs and thrown away. After masking out the bad regions, the 2D track rate maps for different run groups are shown in Fig. 4.7.

4.2.2.2 DC Alignment

The tracks are reconstructed in the PHENIX global coordinate system. To convert the local hits on the DC to global coordinates, one needs to know the detector position precisely. The DC position can change due to central carriage movements during the data taking period. The movements are done to allow access to the central arm detector and perform maintenance. After each carriage move, we take some data with no magnetic field, called zero-field runs, to check the detector alignment. In the zero field environment, if there is no offset between the beam and DC, the α for charged tracks will be zero independent of ϕ_{DC} . Therefore one can look at the 2D profiles of α versus ϕ_{DC} , as shown in Fig. 4.8. A clear dependence of α on ϕ_{DC} is observed and is fitted with Eq. 4.1. Plugging the extracted dx and dy into Eq. 4.1, one can get a $\Delta\alpha$ correction for regular physics runs with full magnetic field on. Without the misalignment correction, the bending angle measured in the DC will be slightly off and hence affect the momentum reconstruction especially at high p_T where α is small.

$$\alpha = \frac{dx}{R_{DC}} \sin\phi + \frac{dy}{R_{DC}} \cos\phi \quad (4.1)$$

Fig. 4.9 summarizes each carriage movement during the data taking and the correction factors obtained from the zero-filed runs.

4.2.2.3 Momentum Scale Recalibration

During the quality assurance check, we found the momentum scale of the reconstructed tracks are about 3% higher than the true momentum by checking the proton/anti-proton mass. The proton/antiproton mass is measured by

Figure 4.7: DC hits map (α versus board number) after fiducial cuts for different run groups. In each subfigure, the top(bottom) panels correspond to the south(north) side of DC and the left(right) panels correspond to the east(west) arm of DC.

Figure 4.8: Left and middle: α versus ϕ_{DC} of charged tracks in a zero field run before DC offset correction. Right: α versus ϕ_{DC} of charged tracks in a zero field run after DC offset correction

the Time of Flight (TOF) East detector and the tracking system using $m = p/(\beta\gamma)$. As shown in Fig. 4.10, the proton and antiproton mass are 3% higher than the Particle Data Book (PDG) value, which means the overall momentum scale is 3% higher. This overall momentum scale offset indicates that the magnetic field map used in the track reconstruction is about 3% higher than the actual magnetic field in the central arm detector. To correct the momentum scale offset, we apply a 97% scale factor to the momentum scale.

East Carriage Move	Zero Field Runs	dx	dy	West Carriage Move	Zero Field Runs	dx	dy	
Mar. 15: 200 GeV Au+Au starts	405835	-0.201886	-0.0206449	Mar. 15: 200 GeV Au+Au starts	405835	0.126119	0.0747311	
	405836	-0.201983	-0.0204607		405836	0.123926	0.0785087	
	406541	-0.210042	-0.0144324		Mar. 19	406541	0.1265	0.0801124
Apr. 02	408185	-0.180873	-0.016651	Apr. 02	408185	0.142374	0.0755642	
	408327	-0.187947	-0.0141503		408327	0.151071	0.0726968	
	409446	-0.204596	-0.0194973		Apr. 16	409446	0.134759	0.0746321
Apr. 04	410113	-0.246138	0.00136171	Apr. 25	410113	0.170582	0.0852463	
	410660, 410661				Apr. 30	410660, 410661		
	410925	-0.174612	-0.00315327		410925	0.127019	0.0889756	
May 12	411562	-0.18176	-0.00586957	May 05	411562	0.100596	0.081746	
	411653	-0.175022	-0.00245628		411653	0.103775	0.0836175	
	411654	-0.174739	-0.00564955		411654	0.106026	0.0865344	
	411655	-0.176099	-0.0041496		411655	0.106377	0.0878755	
May 14	411768	-0.183436	-0.00298656	411768	0.109922	0.0906062		
May 28	413442	-0.170063	-0.0110999	413442	0.161432	0.0809223		
June 10	414435	-0.194111	-0.00394989	May 28	414435	0.219101	0.0867466	
	414436	-0.195692	-0.00397217		414436	0.220524	0.0847161	

Figure 4.9: Carriage moves during the 2014 Au+Au at 200 GeV data taking period

Figure 4.10: Identified charged hadron mass squared as a function of momentum (figure taken from [130]).

4.2.3 EMCAL

Similar to the checks and re-calibrations we did for the tracking system, in this section we will look at the EMCAL dead map, detector alignment and the sector-by-sector energy scale re-calibration.

4.2.3.1 Dead map

The EMCAL was relatively stable across the whole data taking period as compared to the DC, hence only one EMCAL dead map is created for the whole data set. We used a 2D cluster rate map in tower index along the ϕ and z directions to identify the hot (noisy) or cold (inefficient) towers. One can obtain the number of hits per tower distribution from the 2D cluster rate map. The distribution is of gaussian-like shape, and towers with cluster rate 7σ away from the mean value are marked as hot/cold towers and added to the dead map.

To remove the remaining hot towers, we check the $m_{\gamma\gamma}$ distribution in different pair p_T bins:

$$m_{\gamma\gamma} = \sqrt{2E_{\gamma_1}E_{\gamma_2}(1 - \cos\theta)} \quad (4.2)$$

where $E_{\gamma_{1,2}}$ corresponds to the energy of each photon in the pair and θ is the opening angle of the photon pair. The combination of two hot towers will create an artificial peak structure and such peaks will move from bin to bin while the real particle correlations, such as π^0 , η decay, will stay at a fixed mass range. We identify the towers from these “fake” peaks and further mark them as bad channels and include them in the dead map. Fig. 4.11 shows the 2D cluster rate map after applying the EMCAL dead map.

4.2.3.2 EMCAL Alignment

For each PbSc sector, there are 72 towers along x in the local coordinate system, which is along z (beam) in the global coordinate system, and 36 towers along y in the local coordinates, which is along ϕ in the global coordinates. For each PbGl sector, since the tower size is slightly smaller, there are 96 towers along x in and 48 along y . When a photon hits a certain tower and creates a signal, we need to convert the tower index (ix, iy) to global PHENIX coordinates (x, y, z) to be consistent with other detector subsystems and to extract physics quantities of the detected particle, like momentum. Such a mapping between the local coordinate (tower index) and the global coordinate (cluster position) is what we refer to as the EMCAL geometry in this analysis,

Figure 4.11: 2D cluster rate map of each EMCAL sector after masking out the bad channels (towers).

which basically describes where towers are located inside a sector and where sectors are located in the central arm.

The EMCAL geometry setting can be categorized into the following 3 classes:

- Radial position and rotational angle for individual sectors (sector center along ϕ)
- Number and size of the towers within a sector
- Extra translational offset for a whole sector

We use the track projection position as a reference and look at the displacement between the track projection position and the reconstructed cluster

position, $emcd\phi$ and $emcdz$ (see Sec. 2.2.5.2), to judge if the EMCal geometry used in the reconstruction is off or not with respect to the tracking system. In particular, one can choose zero-field runs to avoid the bending of the track so that tracks will be straight-going and can serve as a good reference no matter whether they are of low p_T or high p_T . The plots on the left in Fig. 4.12 show the displacement between the track projection point and reconstructed cluster position as a function of ϕ or θ within each sector using zero-field runs. Firstly, it can be seen that the sector center is off in both the ϕ and z directions, and that is why the spread of $emcd\phi$ and $emcdz$ for each sector is not centered around zero. Secondly, there is a dependence of $emcd\phi$ on ϕ within one sector, and a similar behavior is also observed for $emcdz$. That indicates the radial position or the tower sizes used in the reconstruction are not matching the real detector case.

To fix the mismatch between the real EMCal geometry and the geometry used in reconstruction, we tuned the radial position and translational offset of the geometry setting used in the reconstruction for both the PbSc and PbGl sectors. In addition, the tower size tuning along x (local coordinate) is adjusted slightly for PbGl sectors. The previous and new setting can be found in Fig. 4.13. With the new setting, the displacement between the track projection point and reconstructed cluster position is shown in Fig. 4.12 by the plots on the right. After the correction, the sector centers are sitting at the correct place, although there seem to be still some mismatch either in radial position or tower size. However, the residual difference is rather small and the effect should be much smaller compares to other systematics of our analysis.

4.2.3.3 Sector by Sector Energy Recalibration

The energy scale of each sector changes during the runs due to EMCal gain change. To ensure the EMCal energy scale is stable and consistent between sectors, we use the π^0 mass reconstructed from two EMCal photons (see Eq. 4.2) to recalibrate the energy scale of each sector to the expected π^0 peak position using the single π^0 simulation generated with a realistic p_T spectrum. We increase (decrease) the energy scale if the π^0 peak is lower (higher) than the expected value. Such an adjustment is performed for each run and each sector and is referred to as the sector by sector energy re-calibration. Fig. 4.14 shows the expected π^0 peak position for each sector as a function of run number before and after the energy scale re-calibration.

Figure 4.12: The top plots show the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point along ϕ as a function of ϕ for each sector. The bottom plots show the displacement between the reconstructed cluster position and true impact point along θ as a function of θ for each sector (here the θ are manually moved along the x axis to avoid overlap of the sectors). The left column is before the alignment correction and the right is after the alignment correction.

Previous Setting

Data	Sector W0	Sector W1	Sector W2	Sector W3	Sector E3	Sector E2	Sector E1	Sector E0
Rot angle (°)	22.151	-0.302	-22.784	-45.390	-45.341	-22.899	-0.154	22.139
Trans y (cm)	-0.451	-0.172	0.009	-0.322	-0.810	-0.085	1.776	0.138
Trans z (cm)	1.114	0.899	1.200	1.393	0.890	-0.128	1.195	1.049
Tsize x (cm)	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	4.092	4.092
Tsize y (cm)	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	4.106	4.106
R pos (cm)	506.991	507.197	507.124	507.360	507.982	507.489	540.115	539.057

New Setting

Data	Sector W0	Sector W1	Sector W2	Sector W3	Sector E3	Sector E2	Sector E1	Sector E0
Rot angle (°)	22.151	-0.302	-22.784	-45.390	-45.341	-22.899	-0.154	22.139
Trans y (cm)	1.249	1.128	1.109	-0.222	1.290	0.715	2.576	0.338
Trans z (cm)	-0.486	-0.901	-0.400	-0.407	1.290	0.722	1.595	1.849
Tsize x (cm)	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	4.116	4.116
Tsize y (cm)	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	4.106	4.106
R pos (cm)	508.991	509.197	509.124	509.360	509.982	508.489	536.115	536.057

Figure 4.13: The previous and new geometry settings.

Figure 4.14: Extracted π^0 mass $m_{\gamma\gamma}$ peak mean value as a function of run number. Black and red points correspond to before and after energy re-calibration.

4.3 Event Sample

After the quality assurance check, we identified 1085 good runs out of 1140 runs in total. We analyze the events in good runs and apply the following event selection criteria:

- Narrow vertex events (BBCLL1 narrowvtx trigger + ZDC coincidence)
- $|z_{vtx}| < 10\text{cm}$

There are 1.16×10^{10} events in total after the above event selection cuts.

4.4 Inclusive Photon Sample

In this section, we construct the inclusive photon sample – external photon conversions – from identified e^\pm tracks and extract the raw yield, N_γ^{incl} , as described in Sec. 3.3.2.1.

4.4.1 Electron (Positron) Track Selection

To reconstruct conversion photons via the new algorithm, we first need to select out the e^\pm tracks from the charged hadron tracks. The electron identification cuts we used in this analysis are listed below:

- **Single track cuts**
 - Fiducial cut: DC dead map, $|z_{DC}| < 75\text{ cm}$
 - Track quality cut: DC quality $Q_{\text{track}} = 31 \parallel 51 \parallel 63$
 - Momentum threshold cut: $p_T > 200\text{ MeV}$
- **RICH electron ID cuts**
 - Number of fired PMTs cut: $n_0 \geq 2$
 - Displacement cut: $disp < 5\text{ cm}$
 - Ring shape cut: $\chi^2/npe0 < 10$
 - RICH ghost cut
- **EMCal electron ID cuts**
 - E/p cut: $-2 < dep < 5$
 - Electron track matching cut: $|emcsd\phi_e| < 5, |emcsdz_e| < 5$
 - Associated cluster shower shape cut: $prob > 0.01$

These cuts can be categorized into three classes: 1) single track cuts to select a sample of well reconstructed charged tracks with stable acceptance and efficiency; 2) electron identification cuts using the RICH detector; 3) electron identification cuts using the track-EMCal association. We will describe them in more detail in the following paragraphs.

4.4.1.1 Single Track Cuts

We first apply the run group dependent DC dead map (see Sec. 4.2.2.1) on the track selection and constrain tracks to be from $z_{DC} < 75$ cm to avoid edge effects. The tracks are required to be of good quality, $Q_{track} = 31 \parallel 51 \parallel 63$ (see Sec. 2.2.3.4), to ensure a good momentum resolution. Because of the strong magnetic field, the tracks with very low momentum ($< \sim 170$ MeV) will curl back before reaching the DC. To avoid edge effects due to the curling back of the charged particles, we apply a low momentum threshold of $p_T > 200$ MeV on the charged tracks.

4.4.1.2 RICH Electron ID Cuts

The RICH variables are used to identify e^\pm from charged hadrons. For tracks with momentum below 4 GeV/c, only e^\pm will emit Cherenkov light which will form a ring shape on the PMT plane. We require on at least 2 tubes fired in the nominal ring area – an annulus around the track projection point from 3.4 to 8.4 cm (see Sec. 2.2.5.3). To ensure a good track–ring association, a displacement cut is used to limit the track projection points to within 5 cm from the reconstructed ring center. We also cut on the ratio of the ring shape χ^2 over the number of fired Cherenkov photo-electrons in the nominal ring area to ensure the goodness of the ring shape.

RICH ghost cut As shown in Fig. 2.38, if a charged hadron goes parallel to an e^\pm track, it will be associated to the RICH ring generated by the e^\pm Cherenkov radiation and hence will be misidentified as an e^\pm by the RICH. These mis-associated tracks are often referred to as the RICH ghost tracks. The tracks sharing the same ring will have a very similar distance between the track projection point and the associated ring center, as shown in Fig. 4.15. One can then pair every two tracks and cut away the ring sharing tracks to remove some of the RICH ghost tracks. The cutting value is indicated by the dashed circle in Fig. 4.15.

Figure 4.15: Distance between track projection point and associated ring center along the z and ϕ directions.

4.4.1.3 EMCal electron ID cuts

EMCal variables are then used to further remove the charged hadrons in the e^\pm track sample.

E/p cut One of the most efficient ways of identifying e^\pm other than the RICH n_0 cut is the energy over momentum ratio (E/p) cut combining tracking and EMCal information (see Sec. 2.2.5.1). Fig. 4.16 shows the E/p distribution of charged particles after applying all other e^\pm selection cuts except the E/p cut itself. e^\pm and charged hadrons dominate at different regions of the E/p distribution.

The e^\pm s, due to their negligible mass and full energy deposit into the EMCal, show as a clear e^\pm peak at $E/p \sim 1$ in Fig. 4.16. There can be deviations when the energy or momentum of the e^\pm is mis-reconstructed. For example, if an electron cluster happens to overlap with clusters from other particles, the energy will be reconstructed higher, and hence $E/p > 1$. Or if an electron originates from somewhere far from the interaction point, often referred to as an off-vertex track, its momentum will be reconstructed higher, leading to $E/p < 1$. The conversions we are interested in for this analysis generate off-vertex e^\pm . However, because these conversions take place at the VTX, which is still close to the event vertex, the standard reconstructed momentum is just slightly off, and hence $E/p \sim 1$. It is a different story for conversions further away, such as conversions in the HBD support material, which is around 80 cm away from the interaction point. The e^\pm from such conversions will have

a much smaller E/p , shown as the peak at $E/p \sim 0.6$ in Fig. 4.16. The HBD support structure is at the upper side of the central arm ($y > 0$), and hence the conversion electrons can only reach sector W3 and positrons can only reach sector E3.

There are remaining charged hadrons after applying the RICH electron ID cut, which come from the mis-association of the RICH ring and charged track. Charged hadrons can deposit part of their energy via minimal ionization, and hence exhibit $E/p \ll 1$ (see Sec. 2.2.4.7), shown as a peak at $E/p \sim 0.3$ in Fig. 4.16.

Figure 4.16: E/p distribution of charged tracks after applying the RICH electron ID cuts.

Before determining where to select the E/p peak of e^\pm , we first studied its p_T dependence. The E/p peak mean value, $\langle E/p \rangle$, and sigma, σ are extracted via a fit function constructed by a Gaussian added to a low order polynomial, which is illustrated by the solid lines in Fig. 4.16. Fig. 4.17 shows the E/p versus p_T distribution for e^\pm after RICH electron ID cuts. The central value of the black points correspond to $\langle E/p \rangle$ and the error bar corresponds to σ . Both $\langle E/p \rangle$ and σ exhibit a moderate p_T dependence. $\langle E/p \rangle$ decreases towards high p_T because e^\pm s lose more energy when going through material at lower p_T . Also the low p_T tracks have a large inclination angle when impacting the EMCAL, which causes a wider spatial spread of the shower, and hence the reconstructed E tends to be smaller than the true E . σ increases towards low p_T mainly due to the worse energy resolution of the EMCAL at lower energy (it takes over the better momentum resolution at lower p_T).

Figure 4.17: E/p versus p_T distribution.

Reduced E/p variable – dep To make it easier when cutting on the E/p value in units of σ around the mean value $\langle E/p \rangle$, we convert E/p to a reduced variable dep using Eq. 4.3 so that the mean value of dep will be 0 and σ of dep will be 1, like a standard normal distribution. The smooth functions used to describe $\langle E/p \rangle(p_T)$, expressed by Eq. 4.4, and $\sigma(p_T)$, expressed by Eq. 4.5, are illustrated by the dashed lines in Fig. 4.17.

$$dep = \frac{E/p - \langle E/p \rangle}{\sigma} \quad (4.3)$$

$$\text{where } \langle E/p \rangle = \frac{p_0}{1 + e^{(p_1 - p_T)/p_2}} \quad (4.4)$$

$$\sigma = p'_0 \cdot \sqrt{p'_1/p_T + p'_2 \cdot p_T + p'_3} \quad \text{for PbSc} \quad (4.5)$$

$$\text{and } \langle E/p \rangle = \frac{p_0 + p_1 \cdot p_T + p_2 \cdot p_T^2}{1 + p_3 \cdot p_T + p_4 \cdot p_T^2} \quad (4.6)$$

$$\sigma = \frac{p'_0 + p'_1 \cdot p_T + p'_2 \cdot p_T^2}{1 + p'_3 \cdot p_T + p'_4 \cdot p_T^2} \quad \text{for PbGl} \quad (4.7)$$

In this analysis, we keep a tighter cut on the lower bound $dep > -2$ and a looser cut on the higher bound $dep < 5$. Because we use the tracking system to reconstruct conversion photons, we can keep electrons with slightly mis-measured energy but not momentum.

Electron track matching cut As discussed in Sec. 2.2.5.2, the displacement between the track projection point at the EMCal and the associated cluster position can also be used to identify e^\pm from charged hadrons. The track-EMCal matching variables are expressed in Eq. 2.36.

Reduced electron track matching variable – $emcsd\phi_e$ and $emcsdz_e$ Similar to the reduced variable dep (discussed in Sec. 4.4.1.3), the reduced variables $emcd\phi$ and $emcdz$ are constructed for the electron track matching. Fig. 4.18 shows the $emcd\phi$ distribution for tracks from different z vertex ranges. The smooth functions to describe $\langle emcsd\phi \rangle(p_T, zed)$, expressed by Eq. 4.9 and Eq. 4.10, and $\sigma_\phi(zed, p_T)$, expressed by Eq. 4.11 and Eq. 4.12, are illustrated by the dashed lines in Fig. 4.18. We select tracks within 5σ from the mean value. Similar information for the $emcdz$ variable is shown in Fig. 4.19.

$$emcsd\phi_e = \frac{emcd\phi - \langle emcd\phi \rangle}{\sigma_\phi(p_T, zed)}; \quad (4.8)$$

$$\text{where } \langle emcsd\phi \rangle = p_0(p_T) + p_1(p_T) \cdot zed + p_2(p_T) \cdot zed^2 \quad (4.9)$$

$$p_i(p_T) = c_0^i + c_1^i/p_T + c_2^i/p_T^2 + c_3^i/p_T^3, i = 0, 1, 2; \quad (4.10)$$

$$\text{and } \sigma_\phi(zed, p_T) = p'_0(p_T) + p'_1(p_T) \cdot zed^2 \quad (4.11)$$

$$p'_i(p_T) = c_0^{i'} + c_1^{i'}/p_T + c_2^{i'}/p_T^2 + c_3^{i'}/p_T^3, i = 0, 1; \quad (4.12)$$

$$emcsdz_e = \frac{emcdz - \langle emcdz \rangle}{\sigma_z(p_T, \theta)}; \quad (4.13)$$

$$\text{where } \langle emcsdz \rangle = p_0(p_T) + p_1(p_T) \cdot \theta + p_2(p_T) \cdot \theta^3 \quad (4.14)$$

$$p_i(p_T) = c_0^i + c_1^i/p_T + c_2^i/p_T^2 + c_3^i/p_T^3, i = 0, 1, 2; \quad (4.15)$$

$$\text{and } \sigma_\phi(zed, p_T) = p'_0(p_T) + p'_1(p_T) \cdot \theta^2 \quad (4.16)$$

$$p'_i(p_T) = c_0^{i'} + c_1^{i'}/p_T + c_2^{i'}/p_T^2 + c_3^{i'}/p_T^3, i = 0, 1; \quad (4.17)$$

4.4.2 Pair Selection

After applying the electron identification cuts, we pair the identified e^+e^- tracks together and check if they are produced from the same photon conversion process. Different conversion selection cuts – loose, dzed, default and tight cut – are used as described in Sec. 3.2.4.2.

Figure 4.18: $emcd\phi$ versus z_{DC} distribution for low p_T and high p_T bins.

Figure 4.19: $emcdz$ versus θ distribution for low p_T and high p_T bins.

4.4.3 N_{γ}^{incl} extraction

The e^+e^- pairs passing the conversion selection cuts may contain random pairs of e^+e^- from different processes, which is the main background in the conversion photon sample. The event mixing technique is used to estimate this background before extracting N_{γ}^{incl} . More details are discussed in Sec. 3.3.2.1. In short, we pair an e^+ from event A in our event sample with an e^- from another event B to produce the random e^+e^- pair sample. To make sure the events A and B have similar topological characteristics, we require them to be:

- from the same 10% centrality bin.
- from the same 2.5 cm z vertex bin.
- from the same event plane angle $\pi/6$ bin.

Because of the combinatorial nature of the background, one can see from Fig. 4.20 that the background to signal ratio decreases dramatic towards more peripheral centrality (lower multiplicity). Different conversion selection cuts give different purity (see Sec. 3.2.4.2 and Sec. 3.3.2.1). The purity is the worst in the loose cut case and best in the tight cut case as shown in Fig. 4.20.

4.5 Tagged π^0 Sample

In this section, we construct the tagged π^0 sample by pairing conversion photons with photons measured by the EMCAL and extract the raw yield N_{γ}^{tag} as described in Sec. 3.3.2.2.

4.5.1 EMCAL Photon Selection

To select photon clusters using the EMCAL, the following cuts are used:

- EMCAL dead map
- $E_{\text{core}} > 500$ MeV
- $\chi^2 < 3$
- conversion e^{\pm} veto cut

Similar to e^{\pm} track selection, firstly a fiducial cut on the EMCAL is applied to avoid edge effects and additional systematics from an unstable response of inefficient and noisy channels. We exclude clusters which centers at the sector

Figure 4.20: m_{ee} distribution using different conversion selection cuts (loose, dzed, default, tight) in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality classes.

edges. To ensure the cluster energy is reconstructed correctly, we also require the clusters not to center at the 3×3 tower region around the bad channels marked in the EMCal dead map (see Sec. 4.2.3.1).

An energy threshold cut and shower shape cut are then applied to select photon clusters. The energy threshold cut $E_{\text{core}} > 500$ MeV can remove the minimal ionizing hadrons (deposit about 300 MeV in the EMCal, see Sec. 2.2.4.7). The shower shape cut $\chi^2 < 3$ can remove the clusters with a shower shape unlike the electromagnetic shower profile obtained from the test beam study (see Sec. 2.2.4.7). Since we pair the photon cluster with the conversion photon to identify if the conversion photon is from the decay π^0 by checking the pair mass $m_{ee\gamma}$, we use relatively loose cuts when selecting pho-

ton clusters to ensure a high photon selection efficiency as well as a reasonable signal to background ratio when extracting N_γ^{tag} .

Some of the clusters are from the conversion e^\pm and will form a self-correlation peak around 300 MeV in the $m_{ee\gamma}$ distribution. The self-correlation peak will affect the normalization of the event mixing background, and hence we apply a veto cut to exclude clusters from the conversion e^\pm .

$$\sqrt{\frac{\Delta\phi^2}{\sigma_\phi^2} + \frac{\Delta z^2}{\sigma_z^2}} > 8 \quad (4.18)$$

where σ_ϕ is from Eq. 4.11 and σ_z is from Eq. 4.16.

4.5.2 N_γ^{tag} Extraction

The method of N_γ^{tag} extraction is discussed in Sec. 3.3.2.2. The mixed events requirement is the same as the ones used for the background estimation in N_γ^{incl} . We use the procedures described in Sec. 3.3.2.2 to obtain the shape and normalization of BG_{corr} and $\text{BG}_{\text{uncorr}}$. The one difference is we use a slightly different fitting range to normalize $\text{BG}_{\text{uncorr}}$ to avoid the η peak range in real data. The fitting range is illustrated by the solid orange curve in the bottom panel of Fig. 4.21, which is 0.05 to 1 GeV/ c^2 excluding 0.08 to 0.23 GeV/ c^2 and 0.45 to 0.65 GeV/ c^2 mass ranges.

Additional residual background subtraction Because of the more complicated particle correlations (flow, jets, feed down etc.) present in the real Au + Au collision events, the $m_{ee\gamma}$ dependent re-scaling function $f(m_{ee\gamma})$ gives a stronger correction for $\text{BG}_{\text{uncorr}}$ (see Sec. 3.3.2.2). There still is background (side band histograms not fluctuating around 0) after subtracting the correlated and uncorrelated background using event mixing. We apply an additional low-order polynomial function $\text{Res}(m_{ee\gamma})$ to subtract the residual background, shown by the red lines in Fig. 4.24.

Figure 4.21: $m_{ee\gamma}$ distribution in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality classes.

Figure 4.22: $m_{ee\gamma}$ distribution in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality classes. The conversion selection cut used here is the default cut and the conversion p_T bin is 0.8 to 1 GeV/c.

Figure 4.23: $m_{ee\gamma}$ distribution in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality classes. The conversion selection cut used here is the default cut and the conversion p_T bin is 2.5 to 3.5 GeV/c.

Figure 4.24: $m_{ee\gamma}$ distribution (after subtraction the correlated and uncorrelated background estimated from event mixing) in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality classes. The conversion selection cut used here is the default cut and the conversion p_T bin is 0.8 to 1 GeV/c.

4.6 Conditional Acceptance and Efficiency $\langle \epsilon_\gamma f \rangle$

To ensure the efficiency and acceptance correction calculated from simulation is good, one needs to make sure the simulation setup depicts the real data-taking environment. The major detector parts involved are the track reconstruction system (DC and PC1), electron identification system (RICH) and calorimetry system (EMCal). The former two parts are mainly used in the conversion photon identification and reconstruction, the third is mainly used for the second photon reconstruction.

Because the conversion photon acceptance and efficiency largely cancel out in $N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}/N_\gamma^{\text{tag}}$, the efficiency and acceptance correction in our analysis, $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$, is mostly determined by the acceptance and efficiency of the second photon. That means $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ will be more sensitive to the EMCal response rather than the DC or RICH response. Therefore a careful check was done to make sure the EMCal energy response in the simulation is to the same level of the energy response in the real detector, as discussed in the following section.

4.6.1 EMCal energy response

To tune the EMCal energy response in simulation, we used the π^0 peak reconstructed from cluster pairs in the EMCal following a similar idea as described in Sec. 4.2.3.3. A higher π^0 peak position corresponds to a higher energy scale, and a wider peak width corresponds to a worse energy resolution. The goal is to tune the energy scale and resolution in the simulation setup until the π^0 peak sits at the same position and has the same width as real data.

During the π^0 peak reconstruction, we applied a tight energy asymmetry cut $\alpha < 0.2^*$ so that we can look at the π^0 peak position as a function of photon energy, which can be approximated by the average cluster energy $(E_{\gamma_1} + E_{\gamma_2})/2$. We first tuned the energy scale in simulation sector by sector to have the π^0 peak mean value sitting at the same place for simulation and real data. After a few iterations of energy scale tuning, we achieved the following comparison shown in Fig. 4.25. One can see that the π^0 peak position agrees reasonably well at higher photon energy but there is a discrepancy at the lower photon energy side especially for PbGl. We think that is due to the fact that the nonlinearity effect[†] is implemented and corrected in different ways for simulation and real data. To quantify the difference of the nonlinearity effect between simulation and data, we fit the ratio of the peak position from data to simulation using the functional form shown in the bottom panel of Fig. 4.25.

*Energy asymmetry is defined as $|E_{\gamma_1} - E_{\gamma_2}|/(E_{\gamma_1} + E_{\gamma_2})$

†The nonlinear energy response of the EMCal can come from energy leakage at the front face, light attenuation in the fibers etc. [25].

We then just apply the fitting result as a multiplicative correction factor on

Figure 4.25: Reconstructed π^0 mass peak position via $\gamma\gamma$ channel as a function of average cluster energy for the single π^0 simulation and real data.

the energy of each cluster in simulation to ensure the same nonlinearity effect as real data. After such a correction, the new comparison is shown in Fig. 4.26. One can see now the energy scale in simulation and real data agree better from low to high cluster energy.

Another aspect of the energy response check is the energy resolution comparison. To make sure the simulation has a similar energy resolution as the data, we tuned the smearing factor c_1 in simulation and in addition introduced a new energy dependent smearing term c_2 as shown below:

$$\frac{\sigma_E}{E} = c_1 \oplus \frac{c_2}{\sqrt{E}} \quad (4.19)$$

Fig. 4.27 shows the π^0 peak width comparison between simulation and real data before and after introducing the c_2 term.

Tab. 4.1 summarizes the tuning constants for the EMCAL energy response. The comparisons of the reconstructed π^0 mass peak for each sector between simulation and data are displayed in Fig. 4.28 and Fig. 4.29.

4.6.2 Simulation/Embedding setup

To obtain the conditional acceptance and efficiency of the tagging process, we started from single π^0 events and then processed them through the simulated

Figure 4.26: Reconstructed π^0 mass peak position via $\gamma\gamma$ channel as a function of average cluster energy for the single π^0 simulation and real data.

Sector	0 (W0)	1 (W1)	2 (W2)	3 (W3)	4 (E3)	5 (E2)	6 (E1)	7 (E0)
Scale	0.988	0.990	0.985	0.981	0.980	0.985	1.025	1.023
Smear c_1	0.055	0.066	0.055	0.059	0.057	0.056	0.072	0.072
Smear c_2	0.011	0.017	0.011	0.013	0.012	0.012	0.063	0.062

Table 4.1: Table of tuning constants for each EMCal sector in simulation.

PHENIX detector in PISA software (see Sec. 2.2.6.1). The events with at least one decay γ converting to e^+e^- are the events of our analysis interest. We generated π^0 with flat p_T distribution, and a weight is applied during the analysis to incorporate a realistic momentum distribution. The weight is the Hagedorn function with parameters listed in Tab. 4.3, which is from Tab. 4.1 of [109]. To resemble more a realistic collision, a realistic z vertex distribution obtained from data and a wide Gaussian ($\sigma=10$) pseudo rapidity distribution from -0.5 to 0.5 are implemented in the event generation step.

After processing through PISA, the PHENIX reconstruction software is applied (pisaToDST) to generate an output file (simulated DST file), which is of the same format as the real data output. In this step, the z vertex position of the simulated π^0 events are smeared to match the BBC z vertex resolution in real data. We have four different z vertex smearing – 0.3 cm, 0.5 cm, 0.95 cm, 1.9 cm. They correspond to the different BBC z vertex resolutions in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality classes. The BBC z vertex resolution

Figure 4.27: Reconstructed π^0 mass peak width via $\gamma\gamma$ channel as a function of average cluster energy for the single π^0 simulation and real data.

Figure 4.28: Reconstructed π^0 mass peak position via $\gamma\gamma$ channel as a function of average cluster energy for the single π^0 simulation and real data.

Figure 4.29: Reconstructed π^0 mass peak width via $\gamma\gamma$ channel as a function of average cluster energy for the single π^0 simulation and real data.

from real data is estimated via comparing the z vertex measured by the BBC and VTX, which is shown in Fig. 4.30.

Figure 4.30: Difference between the z vertex reconstructed from the BBC and VTX in each 10% centrality class.

In the next step, we embed the simulated DST file with a certain z vertex smearing into the real data events of the corresponding centrality class to account for the occupancy effects in high multiplicity Au+Au collisions. The occupancy effects relevant to the $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ calculation are mainly the following two:

- the underlying energy due to the overlapping clusters in the EMCAL
- the distortion of the shower profile of individual clusters due to the overlapping clusters in the EMCAL

Since these two effects happen in the EMCAL, the embedding procedure is done only for the EMCAL detector. Such a procedure involves having an algorithm to un-cluster the clusters from the data (realDST.root) and the simulated files (simDST.root), merge the energy depositions from the two files, and then run the clusterization again. The full embedding simulation takes into account the realistic photon efficiency and occupancy effects in the EMCAL. After embedding, we run the analysis module (RDAnalyzer) and save events with conversion candidates into *ROOT*Trees and then reconstruct the conversions

and π^0 s from conversion- γ pairs, just like in the real data case. We then use the following formula to calculate $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$:

$$\langle \epsilon f \rangle = \frac{N_{\gamma}^{\text{tag}}}{N_{\gamma}^{\text{incl}}} \quad (4.20)$$

Fig. 4.31 summarizes the two kinds of simulation chains we used in this analysis. One is without embedding, shown in the left branch, and the other is with embedding, shown in the right branch. The former we will refer to as pure simulation/single $\pi^0/e^+e^-\gamma$ simulation, which runs relatively fast and is useful when checking the tracking system variables. The later we will refer to as embedding – this setup runs much slower compared to the pure simulation, but is necessary when calculating $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ and when checking the EMCal cluster properties such as shower shape and energy.

Figure 4.31: Schematic graph of the simulation chain to calculate $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$.

After embedding, one expects more underlying energy in the reconstructed clusters towards central collisions. To verify that, we look at the π^0 peak from cluster pairs again and compare the embedding results with the real data results in each of the centrality classes shown in Fig. 4.32 - 4.33. It can be seen

that the π^0 mass peak position increases towards central collisions because of the increasing underlying energy, and such an increase is quantitatively described by the embedding to $\sim 1\%$ level.

Figure 4.32: Reconstructed π^0 mass peak position via $\gamma\gamma$ channel as a function of average cluster energy for the single π^0 simulation, embedding and real data in PbSc sectors.

Figure 4.33: Reconstructed π^0 mass peak position via $\gamma\gamma$ channel as a function of average cluster energy for the single π^0 simulation, embedding and real data in PbPb sectors.

4.6.3 Simulation and Real Data Crosscheck

After tuning the energy response of the EMCal, we also compared several other reconstructed variables between simulation and data in order to make sure the simulated detector response depicts the reality. We have some tolerance in the differences for the conversion photons since their acceptance and efficiency cancel out in the $N_{\gamma}^{\text{incl}}/N_{\gamma}^{\text{tag}}$ ratio (see Eq. 3.31), but extra caution needs to be taken when differences show up for the EMCal photons. Systematic uncertainties of $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ will be discussed in Sec. 4.8.

4.6.3.1 Electron (Positron) Tracks

We first compared the RICH electron identification variables, as shown in the top panels of Fig. 4.34. We then checked the acceptance of the tracking system in terms of ϕ_{DC} , as shown by the bottom left plot in Fig. 4.34. ϕ_{conv} and ϕ_{second} are also looked at to cross-check that the generated π^0 distribution agrees with the real data and the decay kinematics is handled properly in simulation.

Fig. 4.35 shows the comparison of the E/p distribution. The observed consistency indicates a good match of measured momentum and energy between simulation and data.

4.6.3.2 Photon Clusters

A comparison of shower shape, the χ^2 distribution, is shown in Fig. 4.36. To have a cleaner look at the electromagnetic shower shape in the real data, we select clusters of conversion e^{\pm} . Although the simulation exhibits a slightly narrower shape, the χ^2 distribution looks very consistent between simulation and data and the systematics arising from such a difference will be estimated later in Sec. 4.8.2.2. One can see the embedding/occupancy effect from the wider χ^2 distribution towards more central events. Such an effect comes from the overlapping clusters. As the multiplicity increases, there is a larger chance of having the overlapping clusters and hence the shower shape will be more distorted. This means the photon identification efficiency of the χ^2 cut will drop towards the central collisions, as shown in Fig. 4.37. In the figure, the PbGl sectors have a smaller efficiency drop as compared to the PbSc sectors because of their finer granularity, and thereby a lower chance of having overlapping clusters.

4.6.4 N_{γ}^{incl} Extraction

N_{γ}^{incl} extraction in simulation is simpler compared to real data because of the very low multiplicity (one π^0 per event). After the single track and pair

Figure 4.34: Distribution of single track variables in simulation (black curve) and real data (red curve).

Figure 4.35: Mean value and sigma of E/p distribution in simulation (right column) and real data (left column).

Figure 4.36: χ^2 distribution for conversion e^\pm in real data (top panel) and embedded simulation (bottom panel). The two columns on the left correspond to clusters from a PbSc sector (sector W0), while the two columns on the right correspond to clusters from a PbGl sector (sector E0)

Figure 4.37: Photon identification efficiency of the $\chi^2 < 3$ cut in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality classes from the embedded simulation.

selections, there is no background in the conversion pairs, so one can directly count the number of conversions in the counting window without background estimation and subtraction.

Figure 4.38: m_{ee} distribution in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality classes of embedded simulation. The conversion selection cut used here is the dzed cut and the conversion p_T bin is 0.8 to 1 GeV/c.

4.6.4.1 m_{ee} Comparison

The comparison of the m_{ee} distribution between simulation and real data is shown in Fig. 4.39. The conversion peaks look shaper in the simulation, which indicate the momentum resolution of charged tracks is slightly better in the simulation. To confirm that, we smeared the reconstructed momentum with two smearing constants c_1 and c_2 described below:

$$\frac{\sigma_p}{p} = c_1 \oplus \frac{c_2}{\sqrt{p}} \quad (4.21)$$

Fig. 4.40 shows the m_{ee} comparison after the momentum smearing with

Figure 4.39: $m_{e^+e^-}$ distribution with no additional momentum smearing.

$c_1 = 2\%$ and $c_2 = 2\%$ [‡]. We can see the m_{ee} distribution agrees much better between simulation and real data after the momentum smearing. However, the momentum smearing does not affect the $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ result; hence we still use the no smearing setup for simplicity.

4.6.5 N_γ^{tag} Extraction

N_γ^{tag} extraction in simulation is also simpler compared to real data because we can use the particle ancestry information to pair conversion photons with EMCAL clusters deposited by particles originating from the same π^0 as the conversions. After such a requirement, the combinatorial background will be eliminated in the reconstructed π^0 sample ($e^+e^-\gamma$ pairs), as shown in Fig. 4.41. Therefore, we only subtract the residual background using a low order polynomial function to make sure the side band of the $m_{ee\gamma}$ histogram is fluctuating around 0.

[‡]These smearing factors correspond to the additional smearing we applied on the reconstructed track momentum (in addition to the intrinsic momentum resolution implemented in simulation).

Figure 4.40: $m_{e^+e^-}$ distribution with momentum smearing, where smearing constants $c_1 = 2\%$ and $c_2 = 2\%$.

4.6.5.1 $m_{ee\gamma}$ Comparison

During the N_γ^{tag} extraction, we use a fixed π^0 counting window for simulation and data. To ensure the same counting efficiency, we compared the $m_{ee\gamma}$ distribution between simulation and data in different centrality classes which is shown in Fig. 4.42. One can see that while the single π^0 simulation shows a pretty good description in the most peripheral centrality case, it missed the higher mass tail developed in the more central collisions. The higher mass tail is caused by the overlapping clusters and thus most prominent in the most central collisions. The embedded simulation manages to catch this tail feature very well. The good agreement of the $m_{ee\gamma}$ distribution also implies the momentum and energy responses are described well in the embedded simulation.

4.6.5.2 Different Components in the π^0 Mass Window

When we pair conversion e^+e^- with EMCAL clusters in the embedded π^0 events, there are different components in the π^0 mass window. The three main contributions ($> 1\%$ of the total signal) are listed below:

- conversions paired with second decay photons

Figure 4.41: $m_{ee\gamma}$ distribution in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality classes of embedded simulation. The conversion selection cut used here is the dzed cut and the conversion p_T bin is 0.8 to 1 GeV/c.

- conversions paired with second conversions

Figure 4.42: $m_{ee\gamma}$ distribution (after background subtraction) in single π^0 simulation (black histogram), embedded single π^0 simulation (blue histogram) and real data (red histogram).

- conversions paired with the Bremsstrahlung photon generated during the second conversion process

From Fig. 4.43, one can see there is more than a 10% chance that the second decay photon converts to an e^+e^- before reaching the EMCal. The probability for a second conversion to happen is proportional to the material budget. Whether or not the second conversion can be used to tag the first ($m_{ee\gamma}$ near π^0 mass), depends largely on where the second conversion takes place.

Late conversions Not all the second conversion clusters can form a peak around the π^0 mass. If the conversion happens early, meaning inside the strong

Figure 4.43: $m_{e^+e^-\gamma}$ distribution when pairing e^+e^- with different types of EMCAL clusters.

magnetic field, the conversion e^+e^- tracks will be opened up by the magnetic field and shower at different spots at the EMCal. In this case, each cluster only carries part of the decay photon energy and the clusters are deflected as compared to the photon going direction, and hence the pair mass of the first conversion and photon cluster will be most likely off the π^0 mass. However, there is a special case – the conversions take place late, meaning outside of the strong magnetic field. For these “late” second conversions, the bent of the conversion e^+ or e^- track is small and hence their showers merge in the EMCal. This merged shower resembles a single photon cluster and will form a pair with the π^0 mass. We will refer to these late second conversions as late conversions in the later discussion, and a cartoon illustrating a comparison between an “early” second conversion and a “late” second conversion is shown in Fig. 4.44.

Figure 4.44: Cartoon illustration of “early” and “late” conversions.

4.6.6 Acceptance and Efficiency Break Down

By keeping track of the whole history for the partner photon of the conversion photon from the same π^0 decay, or say the second decay photon, we can break the $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ term into different acceptance and efficiency components and check them individually.

The first step is to separate the cases where the second decay photon stays intact or not while traversing detector material before hitting the EMCal, if the second photon hits a live area as a photon and passes all the photon ID cuts. The conditional acceptance and efficiency for this process is denoted as $\langle \epsilon f \rangle_{\text{second } \gamma}$. Another branch is the second photon converts to e^+e^- before reaching the EMCal, but the conversion happens outside the strong magnetic field. In this case, the e^+e^- develop a merged shower in the EMCal and can be treated as one photon cluster. We call this type of process late (second) conversion (see Sec. 4.6.5.2). If the merged shower can pass all the photon ID cuts, the conditional acceptance and efficiency for this process is denoted as $\langle \epsilon f \rangle_{\text{late } e^+e^-}$.

The total $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ can then be expressed by the following formulas:

$$\langle \epsilon f \rangle \approx \langle \epsilon f \rangle_{\text{second } \gamma} + \langle \epsilon f \rangle_{\text{late } e^+e^-} \quad (4.22)$$

$$\langle \epsilon f \rangle_{\text{second } \gamma} = f_{\text{geo}} \cdot (1 - p_{\text{conv}}) \cdot f_{\text{fiducial}} \cdot \epsilon_{E_{\text{thrd}}} \cdot \epsilon_{\chi^2} \cdot \epsilon_{\text{veto}} \quad (4.23)$$

$$\langle \epsilon f \rangle_{\text{late } e^+e^-} = f_{\text{geo}} \cdot p_{\text{conv}} \cdot f_{\text{fiducial}} \cdot \epsilon'_{E_{\text{thrd}}} \cdot \epsilon'_{\chi^2} \cdot \epsilon_{\text{veto}} \quad (4.24)$$

where f_{geo} is the probability of the second photon flying within the EMCal geometric acceptance. p_{conv} is the probability that the second photon converts to e^+e^- before reaching the EMCal. f_{fiducial} is the probability that the second photon or late conversion showers at a live area of the EMCal (not centered at the edge of each sector or around a bad channel). $\epsilon_{E_{\text{thrd}}}$ ($\epsilon'_{E_{\text{thrd}}}$) correspond to the probability of the second photon (late conversion) passing the energy threshold cut. ϵ_{χ^2} (ϵ'_{χ^2}) correspond to the probability of the second photon (late conversion) passing the shower shape cut. ϵ_{veto} is the probability that the second photon or late conversion does not fall into the veto area of the first conversion (inclusive photons). All the variables are averaged over the conversion photon distribution and are functions of conversion photon p_T .

One can then combine the two cases and perform another acceptance and efficiency break down in terms of effective conversion probability (the probability that the second conversion takes place and develops an individual shower at the EMCal), p_{conv}^* , and combined photon identification efficiencies, $\epsilon_{E_{\text{thrd}}}^*$ and $\epsilon_{\chi^2}^*$, like the following:

$$\langle \epsilon f \rangle \approx f_{\text{geo}} \cdot (1 - p_{\text{conv}}^*) \cdot f_{\text{fiducial}} \cdot \epsilon_{E_{\text{thrd}}}^* \cdot \epsilon_{\chi^2}^* \cdot \epsilon_{\text{veto}} \quad (4.25)$$

Fig. 4.45 shows the individual components expressed in Eq. 4.25.

Figure 4.45: A break down of $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ into different acceptance and efficiency components[§]. The energy threshold cut here is $E_{\text{core}} > 500$ MeV and the shower shape cut is $\chi^2 < 5$.

4.6.7 $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ Result

After demonstrating the validity of the embedded simulation, $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ is simply the ratio of N_{γ}^{tag} over N_{γ}^{incl} (see Eq. 3.36). The result is shown in Fig. 4.46. The increasing trend of $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ with increasing conversion photon p_T is partly due to the decrease of the opening angle between the conversion photon and the second photon so that the second photon is more likely to fall into the

[§]The drop of the last p_T point in Fig. 4.45 (d) and Fig. 4.61 is an edge effect because the π^0 s in the simulation are generated only up to $p_T = 10$ GeV/ c . To determine the final values of $\langle \epsilon f \rangle(p_T)$, we used π^0 s generated up to $p_T = 15$ GeV/ c to avoid such edge effect.

acceptance of the EMCal, as illustrated in Fig. 4.45 (a). Another important factor is that the average energy of the second photon increases with increasing conversion photon p_T , and hence the efficiency of the energy threshold cut increases towards higher p_T , as illustrated in Fig. 4.45 (d). The difference in $\langle\epsilon f\rangle$ between different centrality classes is mainly related to the shower shape (χ^2) selection because the shower shape is more distorted in central Au+Au collisions, as illustrated in Fig. 4.45 (e).

Figure 4.46: $\langle\epsilon f\rangle$ as a function of p_T in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality classes of the embedded simulation. The conversion selection cut used here is the dzed cut.

4.7 Cocktail Ratio

Now that we have obtained N_γ^{incl} , N_γ^{tag} from real data and $\langle\epsilon f\rangle$ from the embedded π^0 simulation, the last ingredient to construct R_γ is the denominator of Eq. 3.32, $\frac{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}}$ or *cocktail ratio*. Cocktail ratio is the ratio of photons from hadronic decays over photons from π^0 decays (see Sec. 3.3.1). To calculate it, we simulated a mix of hadrons that decay to photons according to their cross section and decay them through different decay channels according to

the branching ratios. The detector efficiency of reconstructing photons from different hadron decays is supposed to be the same, meaning it will cancel out in the ratio form and only the detector acceptance needs to be included in the cocktail simulation. In this work, the cocktail simulation uses the PHENIX internal single particle generator – *EXODUS*, which takes the parent particle species, p_T spectrum, and decay channels as input, generates the decay products and outputs the particles falling into the PHENIX detector acceptance.

The main contributing sources of decay photons are listed in Tab. 4.2. Decays that only produce π^0 s, for example $\eta \rightarrow \pi^0 + \pi^0 + \pi^0$, are not included to avoid double counting.

Parent particle	Decay products	Branching ratio
π^0	$\gamma + \gamma$	98.8%
η	$\gamma + \gamma$	39.3%
η	$\pi^+ + \pi^- + \gamma$	4.6%
η'	$\gamma + \gamma$	2.1%
η'	$\pi^+ + \pi^- + \gamma$	23.0%
η'	$\omega + \gamma$	2.8%
ω	$\pi^0 + \gamma$	8.3%

Table 4.2: Photon production channels in the cocktail simulation.

4.7.1 Neutral Pions

There are comprehensive measurements of pions from PHENIX. Hence the input π^0 spectrum is extracted by fitting the measured invariant yield of π^0 and π^\pm (to reach to lower p_T) with a modified Hagedorn function:

$$E \frac{d^3 N}{d^3 p} = \frac{c}{(\exp(-ap_T - bp_T^2) + p_T/p_0)^n} \quad (4.26)$$

An example of the fitting procedure and data to fit ratio is shown in Fig. 4.47. The extracted fit parameters for different centrality bins are summarized in Tab. 4.3.

4.7.2 η meson

Among decay photon production channels other than π^0 decay in the cocktail simulation, only η has a significant contribution, and hence extra care is taken when extracting the η yield as a function of p_T .

Figure 4.47: Left: Invariant yield of minimum bias charged pions (blue symbols), neutral pions using 2002 data (green symbol) and neutral pions using 2004 data (red symbols) as a function of pion p_T . Right: Data to fit ratio as a function of pion p_T . Figure taken from [109].

Centrality	c [[GeV/c ⁻²]]	a [[GeV/c ⁻¹]]	b [[GeV/c ⁻²]]	p_0 [[GeV/c]]	n	dN_{π^0}/dy
0-10%	1331.0	0.5654	0.1945	0.7429	8.274	280.9
10-20%	1001.0	0.5260	0.1628	0.7511	8.348	200.6
20-30%	750.7	0.4900	0.1506	0.7478	8.299	140.5
30-40%	535.3	0.4534	0.1325	0.7525	8.333	93.8
40-50%	364.5	0.4333	0.1221	0.7385	8.261	59.2
50-60%	231.2	0.4220	0.1027	0.7258	8.220	35.0
60-70%	118.1	0.4416	0.0559	0.7230	8.163	17.9
70-80%	69.2	0.2850	0.0347	0.7787	8.532	8.8
80-92%	51.1	0.2470	0.0619	0.7101	8.453	5.0
Min. Bias	8.453	0.5169	0.1626	0.7366	8.274	95.7

Table 4.3: Fit parameters of the measured pion p_T spectrum in different centrality classes for Au + Au collisions at 200 GeV. Table taken from [109].

4.7.2.1 η/π^0 Ratio in p+p and p+A Collisions

To have a precise extraction of η yield as function of p_T , a global fit on the world data of the η/π^0 ratio in p+p and p+A collisions is performed using a modified m_T scaling function Eq. 4.27. The fitting result is shown in Fig. 4.48. More details can be found in [131].

$$R^{\eta/\pi^0}(p_T) = A \left(\frac{e^{-am_T - bm_T^2} + \frac{R^\infty - \frac{1}{n} m_T}{A} \frac{m_T}{p_0}}{e^{-ap_T - bp_T^2} + \frac{p_T}{p_0}} \right)^{-n} \quad (4.27)$$

where $m_T = \sqrt{m_\eta^2 - m_{\pi^0}^2 + p_T^2}$.

Figure 4.48: World data of η/π^0 ratio as function of p_T and fit result using Eq. 4.27 (blue band). Figure taken from [131].

4.7.2.2 η/π^0 Ratio in A+A Collisions

As we have observed in Fig. 4.48, the η/π^0 ratio exhibits a universal p_T dependence in different small collision systems and different beam energies. The same universality also holds for larger collision systems in the higher p_T regime ($p_T > 2$ GeV/c), which is illustrated in Fig. 4.49.

There is currently no η measurement below 2 GeV/c for Au+Au collisions at 200 GeV, but the low p_T result from central Pb+Pb collisions at 2.76 TeV shows a higher η/π^0 ratio compared to the p+p result [132, 133]. This

Figure 4.49: η/π^0 ratio as a function of p_T for d+Au, Cu+Au, Au+Au and Pb+Pb collision systems. Solid curve is the fit result from Fig. 4.48. Figure taken from [131].

enhanced η/π^0 in central heavy ion collisions is attributed to the radial expansion of QGP. To estimate this radial flow effect, the low p_T kaon to pion ratio is used:

$$R_{\text{flow}} := \frac{\left(\frac{K^\pm}{\pi^\pm}\right)_{C_i}}{\left(\frac{K^\pm}{\pi^\pm}\right)_{p+p}} = \frac{\left(R_{AA}^{K^\pm}\right)_{C_i}}{\left(R_{AA}^{\pi^\pm}\right)_{p+p}} \quad (4.28)$$

where C_i correspond to certain centrality class. Assuming the radial flow effect is the same for η and K^\pm because of their similar mass[¶], one can then use R_{flow} to calculate η/π^0 below 2 GeV/c in different centralities from the p+p result and corresponding radial flow effect:

$$\left(\frac{\eta}{\pi^0}\right)_{C_i} \approx \left(\frac{\eta}{\pi^0}\right)_{p+p} \times R_{\text{flow}} \quad (4.29)$$

η/π^0 calculated from Eq. 4.29 is denoted as “pseudo-data”. Combining the pseudo-data with the Au+Au data points available at higher p_T , we obtained the new fitting result shown in Fig. 4.50.

[¶]This assumption is supported by the observation that $R_{AA}^{K^\pm} \approx R_{AA}^\eta$ at low p_T , shown in Fig. 4 in [132] and figures in slide 9 of [133]

Figure 4.50: η/π^0 ratio as a function of p_T for Au+Au collisions in different centralities. Solid curve is the fit result fusing Gaussian Regression Process (GPR). Figure taken from [131].

More details about the estimation of the radial flow effect and η/π^0 in A+A collision systems can be found in [131]. The final η/π^0 result we use is a combined version: GRP result in Au+Au for the low p_T range (< 3 GeV/c) and the fit result in p+p/A for the high p_T range (> 3 GeV/c). The uncertainty of the fit and the radial flow effect is shown in Fig. 4.51, which is the maximal coverage of the different p+p fits [131] and the extreme cases (smallest and largest) of the radial flow effect.

Figure 4.51: Left: η/π^0 ratio calculated using Eq. 4.29 for most central (0-10%) and most peripheral (60-92%) of Au+Au collisions at 200 GeV beam energy. Right: Maximal cover of flow effect in Au+Au collisions and uncertainty of p+p/A fit. Figure taken from [131].

The final η/π^0 result is then folded in with the input π^0 spectrum (Hagedorn function described in Sec. 4.7.1) to obtain the η yield as a function of p_T and fed into *EXODUS*.

4.7.3 Other Mesons

Due to the limited measurements, the input p_T spectra of other hadrons listed in Tab. 4.2 are extrapolated using the input π^0 spectrum and m_T^{\parallel} scaling [114, 125]. The functional form is determined by the same parameterization as the π^0 case, just replacing $f(p_T)$ (see Eq. 4.26) by $f(\sqrt{p_T^2 + m_{\text{meson}}^2 - m_{\pi^0}^2})$. The overall normalization scale is anchored by experimental measurement at $p_T = 5$ GeV/c, as shown in Tab. 4.4.

^{||}Transverse mass $m_T = \sqrt{m^2 + p_T^2}$

Parent meson	Yield relative to π^0
π^0	1
η'	0.25 ± 0.075 [134–136]
ω	0.9 ± 0.06 [137]

Table 4.4: Meson yield relative to π^0 yield at $p_T = 5$ GeV/ c .

4.7.4 Decay Photons

The decay photon spectra obtained from the cocktail simulation is shown in Fig. 4.52, from which one can calculate $\frac{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}}{\gamma^{\pi^0}}$ easily.

Figure 4.52: Left: Decay photon spectra from different parent hadrons in 0-20% centrality. Right: Cocktail ratio as a function of p_T in 0-20% centrality.

4.8 Systematic uncertainties

In this section, we will discuss the systematic uncertainties in $N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}/N_\gamma^{\text{tag}}$, $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ and the cocktail ratio. Together they determine the systematic uncertainties on the R_γ measurement.

In PHENIX, the convention of categorizing systematic uncertainties according to the point-to-point correlation is summarized below:

- Type A: No (or unknown) correlation between data points – individual data points can fluctuate independently like statistical uncertainty. This type of systematic uncertainty is usually combined with statistical uncertainty in the final results.

- Type B: There is correlation between data points – the fluctuation of each data point can be determined by the fluctuation of the neighboring points.
- Type C: A special form of type B uncertainty – every data point fluctuates with the exact same fraction.

4.8.1 Systematic on $N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}/N_\gamma^{\text{tag}}$

4.8.1.1 π^0 Yield Extraction – Type A

One of the major systematic uncertainties in the R_γ measurement comes from the tagged photon extraction or equivalently π^0 yield extraction. This uncertainty is related to the fact that the event mixing background shape cannot describe the real background perfectly mainly due to the presence of correlated background in the foreground pairs. To further subtract the residual background which is not captured by the event mixing background, we re-scale the event mixing result with a $m_{ee\gamma}$ dependent function and in addition use a low order polynomial function to fit and estimate the remaining background after subtracting the re-scaled event mixing background. Depending on the fit range and functional form, one may over or under subtract the residual background. For example, if one fits just next to the π^0 peak, the fit function will be pushed higher because it will fit part of the signal range. Similarly, the second order polynomial functional form tends to give a systematically higher estimation of the residual background because it usually has a concave shape under it while the first order polynomial looks flatter like the case shown in Fig. 4.53.

After the residual background subtraction, there will be an additional uncertainty coming from the π^0 counting window. To ensure a good statistical uncertainty, we use a limited π^0 counting window $0.09 - 0.19 \text{ GeV}$ where the signal dominates. If we enlarge the counting window, we end up with more statistical fluctuations than signals. However, this limited π^0 counting window will cut part of the signal away especially in the central collisions when the underlying energy gives rise to a broadening of the π^0 mass distribution. If the signal shape is different in simulation as compared to the data after the residual background subtraction, the $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ obtained using the same π^0 counting window will be off from the correct value. An example is illustrated in Fig. 4.54. The left hand side plots show a direct comparison of the π^0 peak mass distributions between data and simulation. The peak shape looks in reasonable agreement, and one can see a larger tail structure at the higher end of the π^0 peak in the $0 - 20\%$ centrality bin shown on the top row when

Figure 4.53: Comparison between first order polynomial fit on the residual background (left) and second order polynomial fit (right) in the embedded simulation.

comparing with the most peripheral case shown on the bottom. To quantify the the effect, we calculated the fraction of π^0 s when varying the upper bound of the π^0 counting window (lower bound fixed at 0.09 GeV) over all the π^0 counts in between 0.09-0.5 GeV. The results are shown in the right hand side plots in Fig. 4.54. The y axis shows the fraction of π^0 s (labeled as efficiency) and the x axis shows the different upper bounds of the counting window. It can be seen that if we choose 0.19 GeV as the upper bound to count π^0 s in 0 – 20% centrality, we will get fewer π^0 s in the simulation and hence a smaller $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$. In contrast, the 60 – 93% does not have such an issue due to an almost 100% efficiency when using the 0.09-0.19 GeV counting window.

The total systematic uncertainty of the π^0 yield extraction is estimated by comparing $N_\gamma^{\text{tag}}/N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ using combinations of different fit ranges, functional forms for residual back subtraction and different π^0 counting windows in each conversion photon p_T bin and centrality bin. The results are shown in the top plots of Fig. 4.55 - 4.58. We then project all the points (except for the largest 4 π^0 counting windows where statistical fluctuation dominates) to the $N_\gamma^{\text{tag}}/N_\gamma^{\text{incl}}\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ axis and use the RMS to represent the systematic uncertainties, which are shown in the bottom plots of Fig. 4.55 - 4.58.

We then plot the RMS as a function of conversion photon p_T in Fig. 4.59 for different centrality bins. There are large fluctuations from point to point which mainly originate from the statistical fluctuation in the π^0 extraction step. A fit function is used to extrapolate a smooth trend along p_T and the

Figure 4.54: Comparison of π^0 peak mass distribution between data (red points and curve) and embedded simulation (blue points and curve). Top plots correspond to the 0 – 20% centrality bin, and the bottom plots correspond to the 60 – 93% centrality bin. The dashed black lines are the lower and upper bound of the π^0 counting window.

Figure 4.55: $N_{tag}/N_{incl}\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ as a function of different π^0 counting windows in the 0 – 20% centrality bin.

Figure 4.56: $N_{tag}/N_{incl}\langle\epsilon f\rangle$ as a function of different π^0 counting windows in the 20 – 40% centrality bin.

Figure 4.57: $N_{tag}/N_{incl}\langle\epsilon f\rangle$ as a function of different π^0 counting windows in the 40 – 60% centrality bin.

Figure 4.58: $N_{tag}/N_{incl}\langle\epsilon f\rangle$ as a function of different π^0 counting windows in the 60 – 93% centrality bin.

value from the fit function is used as the final systematic uncertainty. However, the lowest p_T point (0.6-0.8 GeV) is always systematically higher than the fit result, so we refer to the point value as the systematic uncertainty for the lowest p_T point. Considering that such an uncertainty should be larger for the most central collisions and smaller for the peripheral collisions, we use 3.5%, 3%, 2.5% and 2% as the systematic uncertainty for the lowest p_T point from central to peripheral centrality bins.

Figure 4.59: The systematic uncertainty of tagged photon extraction/ π^0 yield extraction as a function of conversion photon p_T in 0–20%, 20–40%, 40–60% and 60–93% centrality bins.

4.8.1.2 Conversion Sample Purity – Type B

Due to the high multiplicity in Au+Au collisions, we always end up with some background contamination in the conversion photon sample even after applying the tightest conversion selection cut. However we statistically subtracted the remaining background with the event mixing technique. Therefore, we expect consistent results using different conversion selection cuts, which is proved by Fig. 4.60. We observe no systematic trend in R_γ of the conversion sample with different purity levels except for the worst purity case – the conversion sample with low p_T from most central collision events after applying the loose cut. Therefore, we use the dzed cut to obtain the central value of the final results, which has the second best statistics as compared to the loose cut, and quote a $< 1\%$ uncertainty for this source.

Figure 4.60: R_γ obtained using different conversion selection cuts over R_γ obtained using dzed cut ratio as a function of purity level of the conversion sample.

4.8.2 Systematic on $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$

4.8.2.1 Energy Scale and Resolution – Type B

As mentioned in Sec. 4.6.1, it is important to make sure the energy scale and resolution are consistent between data and the simulation. For instance, if the energy scale is higher in the simulation, then there will be more clusters passing the fixed energy threshold cut, and hence we will end up with a higher $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ which directly propagates into the R_γ measurement. To evaluate the

systematic uncertainty from the potential energy scale, we tuned the energy scale constants in the simulation up and down by 2% and checked how $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ changes, as shown in Fig. 4.61. We choose the variation of the energy scale to be 2%, which is motivated by the observed difference in the π^0 peak position between embedding and real data in each sector and the systematic from the fitting procedure to get the π^0 peak mean value.

Figure 4.61: $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ as a function of conversion photon p_T using three different energy scale settings.

To evaluate the systematic uncertainty from the nonlinearity effect correction, we re-calculated the ratio of the π^0 peak position from data to simulation allowing each data point to move according to its statistical and systematic uncertainty. The statistical uncertainty is shown in the plot while a 2% system-

atic uncertainty is added on the lowest two energy bins because the Gaussian fit used to extract the π^0 peak mean is not as good due to the low statistics and a worse background subtraction towards lower energy in the real data. We then re-fit the ratio to get a different nonlinearity correction function. We repeated this procedure ten times, and chose three of the fitting results as the central value, upper bound and lower bound for the nonlinearity correction as shown in Fig. 4.62. We then re-calculated $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ using the central value, up-

Figure 4.62: Ten possible fits for the nonlinearity correction. The green line corresponds to the upper bound, the black corresponds to the central value and the blue corresponds to the lower bound.

per and lower bound of the nonlinearity correction. To show the effect of the nonlinearity correction, we also checked $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ without any nonlinearity correction. Fig. 4.63 shows the effect for PbSc and PbGl separately. From the ratio plot shown in the bottom panels, one can see that the nonlinearity makes a significant difference especially when using PbGl sectors only because of the stronger nonlinearity effect there. Fig. 4.64 shows $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ using different nonlinearity corrections after combining all the PbSc and PbGl sectors. There is a $\sim 0.5\%$ systematic difference between the upper bound and lower bound.

To evaluate the systematic uncertainty from the smearing effect, we tuned the smearing constants, c_1 and c_2 terms defined in Eq. 4.19, to a few different values and compared the $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$. For PbSc sectors, we tuned the c_1 term up and down by 10%, and the c_2 term up and down by 50%. For PbGl sectors, we tuned the c_1 term up and down by 10%, and the c_2 term up and down by 10%. Fig. 4.65 - 4.66 show how the π^0 mass peak comparison looks like when using different sets of smearing constants for PbSc and PbGl separately. A comparison of $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ using different smearing constants is shown in Fig. 4.67. There is no clear systematic variation ($< 0.5\%$) for different smearing constants, and

Figure 4.63: $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ as a function of p_T when using different nonlinearity corrections. The bottom panel is the ratio of certain a nonlinearity correction over the central value. The left plot is when using only PbSc sectors in the tagging process, and the right plot is using only PbGl sectors.

Figure 4.64: $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ as a function of conversion photon p_T when using different nonlinearity corrections. Bottom panel shows the ratio of different $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ over the central value.

Figure 4.65: Reconstructed π^0 mass peak position and width via $\gamma\gamma$ channel as a function of average cluster energy for the single π^0 simulation and real data for PbSc when using different smearing constants.

Figure 4.66: Reconstructed π^0 mass peak position and width via $\gamma\gamma$ channel as a function of average cluster energy for the single π^0 simulation and real data for PbGf when using different smearing constants.

hence we assign no systematic uncertainty from this source. In addition, we

Figure 4.67: $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ as a function of conversion photon p_T when using different smearing constants. Bottom panel shows the ratio of different $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ over the central value.

compared the case when there is no c_2 term added to the smearing process and when there is a tuned c_2 term to see if such a tuning is useful or not. And since the c_2 tuning is mainly needed for PbGl, we calculated $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ using PbGl sectors only, which is shown in Fig. 4.68. One can observe a $\sim 2\%$ difference in $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ with or without c_2 smearing for the PbGl sectors.

4.8.2.2 Photon Efficiency – Type B

In addition to the energy threshold cut, we also have a shower shape cut $\chi^2 < 5$ on the clusters to select the photon candidates. As already discussed in the previous section, the χ^2 distribution in the simulation is slightly narrower as compared to the real data. Such a difference will cause a different photon

Figure 4.68: Effect of using c_2 term in the EMCal energy smearing process. The left two plots show the reconstructed π^0 mass peak sigma comparison between simulation and real data with or without c_2 smearing. The right plot shows the corresponding $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$.

efficiency for a fixed χ^2 , and hence contribute to the systematic uncertainty in the $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ determination. To evaluate the systematic uncertainty of this source, we compared $\frac{N_{incl}}{N_{tag}} \langle \epsilon f \rangle$ when using $\chi^2 < 5$ and $\chi^2 < 3$ cuts. The result is shown in Fig. 4.69, and we fit the difference with a constant to quantify the systematic uncertainty. We fit the lower p_T and higher p_T ranges separately since the photon efficiency has a p_T dependence, which can be seen in Fig. 4.70. However the two range fitting only shows a difference in the 0 – 20% centrality bin, so we only keep the two range fitting for the central case and use a constant over the whole p_T range for all other centralities. We observe a 1.4% systematic uncertainty for 0 – 2 GeV in the 0 – 20% centrality bin and a 1% uncertainty for all other cases.

4.8.2.3 Conversion Photon Loss – Type C

As discussed in Sec. 4.6.5.2, we may not be able to tag the conversion photons from π^0 decay if the second decay photon converts in the strong magnetic field region (before the DC). The probability for this loss is directly related to the material budget of the central arm detectors and will decrease the tagging efficiency $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$. If the material budget implemented in the simulation is different from the real detector, $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ will be systematically off the truth.

The material budget in simulation is quantified by the conversion probabil-

Figure 4.69: $\frac{N_{incl}}{N_{tag}} \langle \epsilon f \rangle$ as a function of conversion photon p_T when using different χ^2 cuts. Bottom panel shows the ratio of different $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ over the central value ($\chi^2 < 5$).

Figure 4.70: Efficiency of χ^2 cut as a function of conversion photon p_T in different centrality bins.

ity extracted from single photon simulation, where we generate photons and pass them through the detector material. We can then map out the conversion probability by looking at where and how frequently conversions took place. In this simulation study, the magnetic field is turned off so that the e^\pm tracks from conversions will go straight into the following detectors.

The conversion probability for the real detector is calculated from the documented detector material budget X/X_0 using the following formula:

$$p_{conv} = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{7}{9}X/X_0\right) \quad (4.30)$$

The comparison of the conversion probability/material budget in simulation and reality for each detector system before the EMCal is shown in Fig. 4.72. Fig. 4.71 shows a zoomed-in version of the detectors in the strong magnetic field region, namely the beam pipe and the VTX detector.

The total conversion probability difference between the simulated and real detector is $\sim 5\%$, as shown in the second last row of text in Fig. 4.72. However, due to the fact that the second conversions which take place in the small magnetic field are very likely to merge into the same shower and behave like a single photon (see Sec. 4.8.2.3), the effective conversion loss is smaller than the expected value (especially for detectors after the DC). Taking that factor into account, the effective conversion loss difference is $\sim 3\%$ between simulation and real data, as shown by the last row of text in Fig. 4.72. Hence we assign 3% systematic uncertainty to $\langle\epsilon f\rangle$ due to the conversion photon loss.

4.8.2.4 Active Area and Geometry Acceptance – Type C

Following the above discussion of the systematic uncertainties on the efficiency side, we now look at the acceptance side. There are mainly two aspects which will affect the second photon acceptance – one is the dead map and the other is the EMCal geometry. The dead map includes a mask on dead and hot towers as well as a fiducial cut on an area of 3x3 towers around the dead/hot channel to avoid loss/distortion of the signal from a photon depositing part of its energy into a dead tower. Clusters with a center on these edge towers are rejected to avoid edge effects. A difference in the dead map can cause an acceptance difference, although Fig. 4.73 - 4.74 show that such a difference is negligible in our analysis (only 0.6% relative difference in sector E0).

To determine the systematic uncertainty on the acceptance due to the EMCal geometry mismatch, we first compare and check how different the geometry settings are between data and simulation, which is shown in 4.75. More details about how the numbers are obtained can be found in [138]. The

Figure 4.71: Conversion rate map within 30 cm of the interaction point. Numbers in parentheses represent the probability that the second conversion e^+e^- merge into the same shower. The \pm sign means whether there is more material in the simulation or more in the real detector, respectively.

Figure 4.72: Conversion rate map before the EMCal. Numbers in parentheses represent the probability that the second conversion e^+e^- merge into the same shower. The \pm sign means whether there is more material in the simulation or more in the real detector, respectively.

Figure 4.73: The comparison of the west arm EMCAL hit maps in simulation (left) and data (right). The fraction of the dead area over the whole sector is calculated by using the ratio of the number of dead towers over the total number of all towers as shown on the top of each plot.

Figure 4.74: The comparison of the east arm EMCAL hit maps in simulation (left) and data (right). The fraction of the dead area over the whole sector is calculated by using the ratio of the number of dead towers over the total number of all towers as shown on the top of each plot.

settings which will affect the geometry are mainly the tower size and radial position of each sector. Given the number of towers N_{tower} , tower size along a certain direction $size_{tower}$ and the radial position R , we can calculate the angular acceptance along ϕ and z for PbSc and PbGl sectors.

$$\text{angular acceptance} = \frac{N_{tower} \times size_{tower}}{R} \quad (4.31)$$

For PbSc, the angular acceptance difference between data and simulation is $\sim 0.1\%$ along ϕ and $\sim 0.3\%$ along z . For PbGl, the angular acceptance difference is $\sim 0.3\%$ along ϕ and $\sim 0.9\%$ along z . Since the majority of our statistics comes from the PbSc sectors, on average the difference should be closer to the PbSc result. Combining the dead map effect, we decide to use 1% as the systematic coming from the acceptance.

Sim	Sector W0	Sector W1	Sector W2	Sector W3	Sector E3	Sector E2	Sector E1	Sector E0
Rot angle (°)	22.152	-0.2354	-22.785	-45.392	-45.343	-22.9	0	22
Trans y (cm)	0.649	0.649	0.649	0.649	0.511	0.511	0	0
Trans z (cm)	0.816	0.816	0.816	0.816	0.742	0.742	0	0
Tsize x (cm)	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	4.104	4.104
Tsize y (cm)	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	5.58	4.104	4.104
R pos (cm)	511.2	511.2	511.2	511.2	511.2	511.2	541.2	541.2

Data	Sector W0	Sector W1	Sector W2	Sector W3	Sector E3	Sector E2	Sector E1	Sector E0
Rot angle (°)	22.151	-0.302	-22.784	-45.390	-45.341	-22.899	-0.154	22.139
Trans y (cm)	1.249	1.128	1.109	-0.222	1.290	0.715	2.576	0.338
Trans z (cm)	-0.486	-0.901	-0.400	-0.407	1.290	0.722	1.595	1.849
Tsize x (cm)	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	5.580	4.116	4.116
Tsize y (cm)	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	5.571	4.106	4.106
R pos (cm)	508.991	509.197	509.124	509.360	509.982	508.489	536.115	536.057

Figure 4.75: EMCAL geometry settings used in simulation (top) and real data (bottom).

4.8.3 Systematics on Cocktail Ratio

4.8.3.1 η/π^0 Ratio – Type B

To estimate the systematic uncertainty on the cocktail ratio due to the uncertainty on the η/π^0 ratio extraction, we move the η/π^0 ratio up and down ac-

according to the uncertainty shown in Fig. 4.48 and recalculate $\gamma^{hadron}/\gamma^{\pi^0}$. The deviation of $\gamma^{hadron}/\gamma^{\pi^0}$ after changing the η/π^0 ratio is independent of centrality. The result of the 0-10% centrality is shown as an example in Fig. 4.76, from which one can see the overall uncertainty is $< 2\%$ and increases towards higher p_T .

Figure 4.76: Cocktail ratio as a function of p_T using the upper bound, central value and lower bound of the η/π^0 ratio for Au+Au in 0-10%.

4.8.4 Summary of Systematic Uncertainties on R_γ

The individual systematic uncertainties from different sources and total systematic uncertainty of R_γ is summarized in Fig. 4.77.

Figure 4.77: Systematic uncertainties of R_γ as a function of conversion photon p_T in 0–20%, 20–40%, 40–60% and 60–93% centrality bins. The black curve corresponds to total uncertainty, and colored curves correspond to individual sources.

4.8.5 Systematic Uncertainties on γ^{direct}

Based on Eq. 3.27, the uncertainty of the invariant yield of direct photons γ^{direct} can be expressed by:

$$\frac{\Delta\gamma^{\text{direct}}}{\gamma^{\text{direct}}} = \frac{\Delta R_\gamma}{R_\gamma - 1} \oplus \frac{\Delta\gamma^{\text{hadron}}}{\gamma^{\text{hadron}}} \quad (4.32)$$

Therefore we need to include the systematic uncertainties on γ^{hadron} (see Sec. 4.7) to calculate the uncertainty of the invariant yield of direct photons.

4.8.5.1 Systematic Uncertainties on γ^{hadron}

The systematic uncertainties on γ^{hadron} have been studied in detail in [2]. The main sources are described in the following paragraphs.

Input pion spectrum shape The pion measurements have their own systematic uncertainties, and hence the extracted pion spectrum shape serving as input to calculate decay photons will also have uncertainties.

Run 2/Run 4 discrepancy Combined pion measurements were used when extracting the pion spectrum shape, which includes the charged pion measurements and the neutral pion measurements with Run 2 (data taken during 2002) and Run 4 (data taken during 2004) data sets. Although the results should be independent of the data taking year, there is a systematic difference between the 2002 and 2004 π^0 invariant yield results (see Fig. 4.47). This difference, denoted as the Run 2/ Run 4 discrepancy, is included in the systematic uncertainty estimation of γ^{hadron} .

Meson to pion ratio The uncertainty on the spectra of other mesons (η , η' , ω) also contributes to the uncertainty on γ^{hadron} , but is dominated by the uncertainty on the spectrum of η mesons, which is described in Sec. 4.8.3.1.

A summary of the systematic uncertainties on γ^{hadron} is shown in Fig. 4.78.

4.8.5.2 Uncertainty Propagation and MC Sampling Method

If $R_\gamma \geq 1$, we can simply use Eq. 4.32 to calculate the systematic uncertainty of the direct photon yield. However, if $R_\gamma < 1$, the direct photon yield will be negative, which is unphysical. Given that the direct photon yield cannot be

Figure 4.78: Systematic uncertainties of γ^{hadron} as a function of photon p_T .

negative a priori, to correctly evaluate the uncertainty of direct photon yield when R_γ or $R_\gamma - \sigma_{R_\gamma}$ is less than unity, we utilized the MC sampling method.

In the MC sampling method, we vary the ingredients of the direct photon yield calculation according to its statistical or systematic uncertainties and recalculate the yield each time (*a sample*). The variation, denoted as fluctuation δ , changes randomly from sample to sample. After repeating such a procedure many times, we end up with a distribution of direct photon yields, from which we can determine the central value and uncertainties. Depending on how big the mean value $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle$ and width σ of the distribution are, there are typically three cases (illustrated in Fig. 4.79):

- $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle \geq 0$ and $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle - \sigma \geq 0$: in this case, we use the mean value as the central value and quote $\pm \sigma$ as the uncertainty.
- $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle \geq 0$ and $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle - \sigma < 0$: in this case, we use the mean value as the central value. However, since the $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle - \sigma$ is in the unphysical region (negative yield), we quote 0 as the lower bound. The upper bound is determined by $\int_{\text{upper}}^{+\infty} / \int_0^{+\infty} = 10\%$.
- $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle < 0$ and $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle + \sigma \geq 0$: in this case, since the mean value is in the unphysical region (negative yield), there is no central value for this measurement. The lower bound is 0, and the upper bound is determined by $\int_{\text{upper}}^{+\infty} / \int_0^{+\infty} = 10\%$.

(a) $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle \geq 0$ and $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle - \sigma \geq 0$

(b) $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle \geq 0$ and $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle - \sigma < 0$

(c) $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle < 0$ and $\langle \gamma^{\text{dir}} \rangle + \sigma \geq 0$

Figure 4.79: Three typical cases of the uncertainty calculation for γ^{dir} . The blue histogram is the distribution of γ^{dir} when samples are generated with only statistical uncertainty. The red histogram is the distribution of γ^{dir} when samples are generated with only systematic uncertainty.

Correlated uncertainties During the sampling procedures, extra care is taken to account for the correlation between different p_T or centrality points to ensure a correct uncertainty estimation when we study the p_T (see Sec. 5.2.1) and centrality dependence (see Sec. 5.2.3) of the direct photon production.

For the statistical or type A systematic uncertainty, we just vary each individual point randomly for each sample using $\delta(p_T, \text{cent}) = \text{Gaussian}(0, \sigma(p_T, \text{cent}))^{**}$. The generated fluctuation maps for two example samples are shown in Fig. 4.80.

Figure 4.80: Generated fluctuation on $N_\gamma^{incl}/N_\gamma^{tag}$ according to the statistical uncertainty in two example samples. x axis is centrality bin (9 bins from 0 to 93%). y axis is p_T bin (13 bins from 0.8 to 10 GeV/c). Color represents the fluctuation assigned to each bin in unit of %.

For the type C uncertainty, we vary all the points by the same amount for each sample using $\delta(p_T, \text{cent}) = \text{Gaussian}(0, 1) \times \sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$, where $\text{Gaussian}(0, 1)$ generates one number per sample. The generated fluctuation maps for two example samples are illustrated in Fig. 4.81. A uniform 2D distribution is seen because the type C uncertainty does not depend on centrality or p_T .

For the type B uncertainty, the situation is more complicated because the functional form of the correlation is usually unknown and the correlation can differ for different systematic sources. For some sources, we assume there is a positive correlation between points, meaning the adjacent points will fluctuate to the same direction. In this case, we vary all the points by the same relative amount with respect to the uncertainty for each sample using $\delta(p_T, \text{cent}) =$

^{**} $\sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$ corresponds to the statistical/systematic uncertainty in a certain p_T and centrality bin. $\text{Gaussian}(0, \sigma(p_T, \text{cent}))$ corresponds to a random number generated from a Gaussian distribution with a mean value of 0 and a width of $\sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$.

Figure 4.81: Generated fluctuation on $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ according to the conversion photon loss systematic uncertainty (see Sec. 4.8.2.3) in two example samples. x axis is centrality bin (9 bins from 0 to 93%). y axis is p_T bin (13 bins from 0.8 to 10 GeV/ c). Color represents the fluctuation assigned to each bin in unit of %.

Gaussian(0, 1) \times $\sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$, where Gaussian(0, 1) generates one number per centrality per sample. For the input pion spectrum shape systematic uncertainty, we treated its correlation along p_T in this manner, as shown in Fig. 4.82. It can be seen that the fluctuation is always the same sign for all the p_T bins in a certain centrality bin, and the fluctuation is always larger at higher p_T because this systematic uncertainty increases with p_T (see Fig. 4.78).

So far we discussed one implementation of the type B systematic uncertainty along p_T in MC sampling. There are cases that the systematic uncertainty is also type B along centrality, which is the case for energy scale. Here we will briefly describe how the energy scale uncertainty is implemented in the MC sampling code, which is the largest type B uncertainty in this analysis.

1. Generate two random numbers using Gaussian(0, $\sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$) as the fluctuation for the lowest p_T point in the lowest centrality bin, denoted as $\delta(p_T^{\text{low}}, \text{cent}^{\text{low}})$, and the lowest p_T point in the highest centrality bin, denoted as $\delta(p_T^{\text{low}}, \text{cent}^{\text{high}})$.
2. Linearly interpolate $\delta(p_T^{\text{low}}, \text{cent}^{\text{low}})$ and $\delta(p_T^{\text{low}}, \text{cent}^{\text{high}})$ to obtain the fluctuation for any centrality bin $\delta(p_T^{\text{low}}, \text{cent})$.
3. For a certain centrality, generate a random number using Uniform(0, $0.5\delta(p_T^{\text{low}}, \text{cent})$) as the fluctuation for the highest p_T bin, denoted as $\delta(p_T^{\text{high}}, \text{cent})$.

Figure 4.82: Generated fluctuation on decay photon yield γ^{hadron} according to the input pion spectrum shape systematic uncertainty (see Sec. 4.8.5). x axis is centrality bin (9 bins from 0 to 93%). y axis is p_T bin (13 bins from 0.8 to 10 GeV/ c). Color represents the fluctuation assigned to each bin in unit of %.

4. Linearly interpolate $\delta(p_T^{\text{low}}, \text{cent})$ and $\delta(p_T^{\text{high}}, \text{cent})$ to obtain the fluctuation for any p_T bin, denoted as $\delta(p_T, \text{cent})$.

The steps 1 and 2 are the implementation of the correlation along centrality, which is motivated by Fig. 4.83. Step 3 is used for the implementation of the correlation along p_T , which ensures the higher p_T points always fluctuate less as compared to the lower p_T points because the lower p_T points are more sensitive to the energy scale uncertainty. Two examples of the generated fluctuation on $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ due to energy scale uncertainty are shown in Fig. 4.84.

4.8.5.3 Summary of Systematic Uncertainties on γ^{direct}

A summary of the MC sampling implementation of different systematic uncertainty sources on the direct photon R_γ and invariant yield measurements can be found in Tab. 4.5^{††}.

^{††}The sources with $< 1\%$ systematic uncertainty are ignored, e.g. conversion purity and the contribution of other mesons in γ^{hadron} .

Figure 4.83: Possible correlation between different centrality bins for energy scale systematic uncertainty. The top panel shows the energy scale as a function of charged particle multiplicity N_{ch} (equivalent to centrality), where the red line corresponds to the real data and the black lines are the possible cases in the embedding setup. The increasing energy scale with charged particle multiplicity is due to more and more underlying energy in more central collisions. The bottom panel shows the energy difference between data and embedding ΔE as a function of N_{ch} for case 2.

Source	Correlation along p_T	Correlation along centrality	Implementation of variation $\delta(p_T, \text{cent})$
Sources of systematic uncertainty on $N_{\text{incl}}^\gamma/N_{\text{tag}}^\gamma$			
N_{tag}^γ extraction	Type A	Type A	$\delta(p_T, \text{cent}) = \text{Gaussian}(0, 1) \times \sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$, where Gaussian(0, 1) generated for each p_T and centrality bin
Sources of systematic uncertainty on $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$			
Energy scale	Type B	Type B	described in Sec. 4.8.5.2
Conversion loss	Type C	Type C	$\delta(p_T, \text{cent}) = \text{Gaussian}(0, 1) \times \sigma$
γ efficiency	Type B	Type A	$\delta(p_T, \text{cent}) = \text{Gaussian}(0, 1) \times \sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$, where Gaussian(0, 1) generated for each centrality bin
Active area	Type C	Type C	$\delta(p_T, \text{cent}) = \text{Gaussian}(0, 1) \times \sigma$
Input π^0 p_T spectra	Type B	Type A	$\delta(p_T, \text{cent}) = \text{Gaussian}(0, 1) \times \sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$, where Gaussian(0, 1) generated for each centrality bin
Sources of systematic uncertainty on $\gamma^{\text{hadron}}/\gamma^{\pi^0}$			
η/π^0	Type B	Type C	$\delta(p_T, \text{cent}) = \text{Gaussian}(0, 1) \times \sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$
Sources of systematic uncertainty on inclusive γ^{hadron} yield			
η/π^0	same as the η/π^0 uncertainty for $\gamma^{\text{hadron}}/\gamma^{\pi^0}$		
Input pion spectrum shape and Run 2/Run 4 discrepancy	Type B	Type A	$\delta(p_T, \text{cent}) = \text{Gaussian}(0, 1) \times \sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$, where Gaussian(0, 1) generated for each centrality bin

Table 4.5: Summary of the implementation of systematic uncertainties in the MC sampling method. Type A/B/C represent different type of correlation between data points: type A means no or unknown correlations between data points; type B means there is a certain correlation between data points; type C means all data points fluctuate by the exact same fraction (more details in Sec. 4.8). $\delta(p_T, \text{cent})$ corresponds to the variation applied on each data point per MC sample. $\sigma(p_T, \text{cent})$ corresponds to the systematic uncertainty on each data point (the exact value for different source can be found in Sec. 4.8.4 and Sec. 4.8.5.1). Gaussian(0, 1) corresponds to a random number generated from a Gaussian distribution with a mean value of 0 and a width of 1.

Figure 4.84: Generated fluctuation on $\langle \epsilon f \rangle$ according to the energy scale systematic uncertainty (see Sec. 4.8.2.1). x axis is centrality bin (9 bins from 0 to 93%). y axis is p_T bin (13 bins from 0.8 to 10 GeV/ c). Color represents the fluctuation assigned to each bin in unit of %.

Chapter 5

Results and Discussion

5.1 Results

5.1.1 Direct Photon R_γ

R_γ is calculated from Eq. 3.32. Fig. 5.1 shows the R_γ results in the 0–20%, 20–40%, 40–60% and 60–80% centrality classes. The vertical error bar on each point corresponds to the statistical uncertainty, and the box around each point corresponds to the systematic uncertainty. The new results are compared with several published PHENIX results measured with different methods – the gray points use the external conversion method to measure photons which convert at the HBD detector [54], the blue points use internal conversion to measure virtual photons [139] and the green points use the calorimeter method of measuring photons [140], which deposit all their energy into the EMCal. Despite the differences of the method used in the various measurements and the correspondingly different systematic uncertainties, the results are consistent with each other. Benefiting from the larger statistics of the 2014 dataset, due to both increased luminosity and conversion material, the new result exhibits smaller statistical uncertainties. Furthermore, the new result provides a continuous measurement across a wide range of p_T , 0.8–10 GeV/ c , bridging the previous measurements which cover low the p_T and high p_T region separately. In Fig. 5.1, R_γ shows a small excess in the lower p_T end with a relatively flat shape. It then starts to rise and ends up with a much more significant excess at the higher p_T end.

Fig. 5.2 shows the new R_γ results in finer centrality classes, from 0-10% to 80-93%. The overall shape of R_γ as a function of p_T is similar to what we observed in Fig. 5.1, except for the most peripheral centrality 80-93%. A sudden drop of the R_γ values occur in the 80-93% centrality class. Below 5 GeV/ c , the data points show no significant excess above 1 and are very

Figure 5.1: R_γ as a function of conversion photon p_T in the 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality bins.

consistent with the direct photon result from p+p collisions (black points in the plot).

5.1.2 Direct Photon Invariant Yield

With R_γ and the decay photon yield obtained from Sec. 4.7.4, one can determine the invariant direct photon yield via $\gamma^{\text{direct}} = (R_\gamma - 1)\gamma^{\text{hadron}}$ (see Eq. 3.27). However, we need to apply a *bin-width correction* before presenting the final results, which is introduced in the following paragraph.

Bin-width correction The average R_γ in each p_T bin is shown at the bin center, since R_γ changes only modestly as a function of p_T . A more careful treatment is needed for a steeply falling exponential or power law spectrum. The average p_T of the measured particles in a given bin will be smaller than the p_T at the center of the bin, because the spectrum falls steeply with increasing p_T . The size of this effect will be larger for a larger bin width. To have a correct representation of the yield in a p_T bin of finite width, the so-called bin-width correction needs to be applied. There are two common ways to perform the correction:

- Keep the yield of each data point unchanged, and move the data point along the p_T axis.

Figure 5.2: R_γ as a function of conversion photon p_T in 0-10% to 80-93% centrality bins.

- Keep the p_T at the bin center, and move the data point along the yield axis.

The two approaches are equivalent and we choose to use the second one in this work. We first fit the uncorrected spectra with an appropriate functional form f to approximate the true p_T dependence. We use a modified Hagedorn function in this study, as shown by the magenta dashed line in Fig. 5.3.

Figure 5.3: The invariant yield of direct photons as function of p_T before bin-width correction.

The correction factor r can be estimated via:

$$r = \frac{\frac{1}{\Delta} \int_{p_T^c - \Delta/2}^{p_T^c + \Delta/2} f(p_T) dp_T}{f(p_T^c)} \quad (5.1)$$

where Δ represents the bin width. The corrected yield for a given p_T bin is then calculated as:

$$\left. \frac{dN}{dp_T} \right|_{corrected} = \frac{\left. \frac{dN}{dp_T} \right|_{uncorrected}}{r} \quad (5.2)$$

The corrected direct photon spectra for 0–20%, 20–40%, 40–60% and 60–93% Au+Au collisions are shown in Fig. 5.4. The number of binary collisions (N_{coll}) scaled p+p fit is also shown as an estimate for the prompt photon contribution. The p+p fit is performed on the combined p+p results from different datasets, and a pQCD inspired functional form $f = A(1 + p_T^2/p_0)^n$ is used to extrapolate data down to very low p_T . The error band around the central fit function represents the uncertainty propagated from both the data and the unknown true functional form of the spectrum shape down to very low p_T .

As can be seen in Fig. 5.4, the direct photon yield at high p_T (> 5 GeV/ c) can be well described by the N_{coll} scaled p+p result and pQCD calculation, which confirms that the high p_T direct photons are dominated by photons produced from initial hard scattering processes. However, a clear excess is visible below 4-5 GeV/ c , which is theorized as being due to thermal radiation from the QGP and hadron gas.

Figure 5.4: Invariant yield of direct photons as a function of conversion photon p_T in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality bins.

5.2 Discussion

We first compare the direct photon p_T spectra with the theoretical models introduced in Sec. 1.4.3, as shown in Fig. 5.5. Since the new result is very consistent with the previous low p_T direct photon results, we reach the same conclusion as before – the current models under-predict the direct photon yield below 3 GeV/c. The new data shows a clear excess for 3-4 GeV/c. While it is not clear what is the main source(s) of these photons, one thing we can see is that the theoretical calculations also underestimate the photon yield in the intermediate p_T region.

Figure 5.5: Invariant yield of direct photons in the 20-40% centrality class compared to a few theoretical models.

This comparison can also serve as a good example showing the complication of experimentally studying direct photon production mainly arises from the following aspects:

- Multiple sources contribute to photon production from the early to late stages of the system evolution.
- Photon emission is convoluted with the dynamical expansion of the system.

To dissect the different photon sources, one way is to study the properties of direct photons in different transverse momentum regimes. In general, photons produced at earlier stages exhibit a “harder” shape (more yield on the high p_T side), while photons produced at the later stages show a “softer” shape (more yield on the low p_T side). By selecting photons from particular p_T range, we can enhance our sensitivity to photons emitted from certain stage of the collisions. In the following section, we discuss in detail the properties of direct photons from the low p_T (more sensitive to late emissions) to the high p_T (more sensitive to early emissions) regime.

5.2.1 Low p_T Direct Photon Excess

To have a closer look at the direct photon excess above the prompt photon expectation below 5 GeV/ c , we subtract the N_{coll} scaled pp baseline from the total yield. The results are shown in Fig. 5.6. If we assume the very low p_T photons are dominated by thermal radiation, the spectra will be of exponential shape and the inverse slope of the exponential fit will indicate the average temperature (convoluted with the space-time expansion). We thus fit the excess photon spectra with $f = A \times \exp(-p_T/T_{\text{eff}})$ in the 0.8-1.9 GeV/ c region, with the fit shown by the red lines in Fig. 5.6. The exponential fit can reasonably describe the excess photon spectra below 2 GeV/ c with an inverse slope of ~ 260 MeV. However, the data points start to deviate from the single exponential fit above 2 GeV/ c . Such an observation implies a larger contribution of photons emitted at earlier time, like QGP or pre-equilibrium photons, toward higher p_T ($> \sim 2$ GeV/ c). To distinguish these two regions, we refer to the $p_T < 2$ GeV/ c region as the low or very low p_T region and the $2 < p_T < 4$ GeV/ c region as the intermediate p_T region in the following discussions.

Figure 5.6: Excess yield of direct photons as a function of conversion photon p_T in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality bins.

5.2.1.1 Very Low p_T Region

The extracted T_{eff} is ~ 260 MeV, which is consistent with the T_{eff} extracted from previous low p_T direct photon results (the gray points in Fig. 5.6). This region is generally believed to be dominated by thermal radiation from the hadron gas phase. Because of the fully developed velocity field at this stage, the extracted value of T_{eff} is much higher than the true medium temperature due to a strong blue shift effect. A naive analogy is to the Blackbody radiation emitted from an expanding surface, which gives the following formula:

$$T_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{\frac{1 + \beta_{\text{flow}}}{1 - \beta_{\text{flow}}}} T \quad (5.3)$$

where T is the true temperature and β_{flow} corresponds to the medium velocity. The surface velocity can be as large as almost 0.6 at the very late stage of the system expansion, which gives a factor of two difference between the true temperature T and effective temperature T_{eff} . This would be an over-estimation of the blue-shift effect for the earlier thermal radiation (i.e. QGP). To better understand the relation between T and T_{eff} for photon emission from different time, we need a realistic hydrodynamic simulation to model the whole history of photons emissions from the dynamically evolving system, which is discussed in more detail in Sec. 5.2.1.4.

The extracted T_{eff} in the four centrality classes in Fig. 5.6 does not show a strong dependence on centrality. To examine this more closely, we carried out the same fitting procedure in finer centrality bins; the extracted T_{eff} as a function of centrality is shown in Fig. 5.7a. As centrality itself is not a physical quantity and can be defined differently for different experiments, we re-plotted the extracted T_{eff} as a function of the measured charged particle multiplicity at mid-rapidity. The charged particle multiplicity is directly related to the energy density of the collision system (see Sec. 1.2.2.1) and increases monotonically towards more central collisions, and for higher collision energies. The result is shown in Fig. 5.7b. It is not conclusive whether there is a systematic trend in T_{eff} as a function of charged particle multiplicity given the uncertainties on the data points, but there is a hint of a possible increase of T_{eff} towards higher multiplicity.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.7: (a) T_{eff} (fitting range 0.8-1.9 GeV/c) as a function of centrality. (b) T_{eff} (fitting range 0.8-1.9 GeV/c) as a function of charged particle multiplicity at mid-rapidity.

5.2.1.2 Intermediate p_T Region

For p_T below 2 GeV/ c an exponential function with an inverse slope ~ 260 MeV describes the direct photon excess (prompt contribution subtracted) very well. However at higher p_T the inverse slope increases. To look into the magnitude and shape of the deviation, we fixed the inverse slope to 260 MeV and refitted the data. The ratio of data to fit result is shown in Fig. 5.8.

Figure 5.8: Left: An example of the fixed T_{eff} fit in the very low p_T range. Right: Ratio of excess yield of direct photons over the exponential fit result (T_{eff} fixed to 260 MeV) as a function of photon p_T in the 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality bins.

The change in inverse slope is not a surprise. There are multiple photon sources with different p_T shapes and they play a dominant role in different p_T regions. It is thus but natural that a single exponential function that works well in some region, would fail in other regions. The question is what is the major photon source(s) which gives a harder p_T dependence in between 2 and 4 GeV/ c . A harder p_T shape implies that these photons are emitted from early stages of the evolution. One candidate is thermal radiation from the QGP phase; then the deviation means the QGP *over-shines* the hadron gas in this intermediate p_T range. Following up on this assumption, we perform another exponential fit in the $2 < p_T < 4$ GeV/ c range, which is illustrated by the blue line in Fig. 5.9. T_{eff} is about 400 MeV with relatively large uncertainties. There is no strong centrality dependence observed.

A similar fitting procedure is performed on finer centralities classes and the result is shown in Fig. 5.10a. Another representation using charged particle

Figure 5.9: Two different exponential fits on the excess yield of direct photons as a function of conversion photon p_T in the 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-93% centrality bins. The red line corresponds to the fit performed from 0.8 – 1.9 GeV/c. The blue line corresponds to the fit performed from 2 – 4 GeV/c.

multiplicity as the x axis is shown in Fig. 5.10b. From Fig. 5.10b, T_{eff} shows no dependence on charged particle multiplicity. The most central collision result (0-10%) shows a slight enhancement but with large uncertainties.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.10: (a) T_{eff} (fitting range 2.0 – 4.0 GeV/c) as a function of centrality. (b): T_{eff} (fitting range 2.0 – 4.0 GeV/c) as a function of charged particle multiplicity at mid-rapidity.

5.2.1.3 Comparison with LHC Results

As we see a hint of an increase of T_{eff} from peripheral to central Au+Au collisions at a beam energy of 200 GeV, it is natural to compare with the T_{eff} of low p_T direct photons from higher a beam energy, namely Pb+Pb collisions at 2.76 TeV, as shown in Fig. 5.11.

Figure 5.11: T_{eff} (fitting range 0.9-2.1 GeV/c) as a function of charged particle multiplicity at mid-rapidity.

This T_{eff} is obtained from direct photons in 0-20% Pb+Pb collisions measured by the ALICE experiment [57]. Due to the slightly different p_T coverage of the ALICE data, the T_{eff} was extracted from p_T of 0.9 to 2.1 GeV/c. To compare to our results we refitted the Au+Au data for the same p_T range. The central Pb+Pb result is slightly higher compared to central the Au+Au result, although given the uncertainties they may also be consistent with each other. The change of the inverse slope above 2 GeV/c is also seen in the direct photon results in the most central Pb+Pb collisions. This is shown in Fig. 5.12 while it is similar to Fig. 5.8. A similar trend is observed in the Pb+Pb result – excess yield consistent with the exponential fit with $T_{\text{eff}} \sim 260$ MeV at low p_T and increasing inverse slope above 2 GeV/c. The T_{eff} is extracted in the intermediate p_T range (2-4 GeV/c) from the Pb+Pb results and compared to the Au+Au results in Fig. 5.13.

Figure 5.12: Ratio of excess yield of direct photons over the exponential fit result (T_{eff} fixed to 260 MeV) as a function of photon p_T .

Figure 5.13: T_{eff} (fitting range 2.0-4.0 GeV/c) as a function of charged particle multiplicity at mid-rapidity.

5.2.1.4 Comparison to Hydrodynamics Model

We compared our data to a theoretical calculation [51], which uses the hydrodynamic model (hydro model) to study T and T_{eff} for photons emitted at different times. The calculation is done for both Au+Au collisions at RHIC energy and Pb+Pb collisions at LHC energy. Fig. 5.14 shows the temperature profile of the collision system and the amount of photon radiation is indicated by the color. The hydrodynamic evolution starts from the initial temperature at the QGP formation time, which is set to 370 MeV for Au+Au collisions in 0-20% centrality and set to higher value, 453 MeV, for Pb+Pb collisions in 0-40% due to a higher energy density in the collision system. As one can see from the figures on the left, the true local temperature T of the medium drops and hence the medium radiate fewer thermal photons per unit time (emission rate approximately $\propto T^4$) as time evolves.

Figure 5.14: Contour plots of the normalized differential photon yields $\frac{dN^\gamma(T,\tau)/dydTd\tau}{dN^\gamma/dy}$ (left) and $\frac{dN^\gamma(T_{\text{eff}},\tau)/dydT_{\text{eff}}d\tau}{dN^\gamma/dy}$ (right) calculated from the hydro model. Top panels corresponds to Au+Au collisions at 200 GeV in 0-20% centrality. Bottom panels corresponds to Pb+Pb collisions at 2.76 TeV in 0-40% centrality. Figure taken from [51].

A significant amount of thermal photons are emitted at the earlier time ($< \sim 2$ fm/ c) when the temperature is the highest (the hot QGP phase). However most of the photons* are emitted later around the QGP to hadron gas phase transition region because of the larger emission volume. That corresponds to a relatively narrow temperature range, which is around 150-220 MeV. The distribution of the photon yield as function of T is shown in Fig. 5.15. Different colored curves represent photons in different p_T windows. In the very low p_T window (~ 1 GeV/ c), the majority of the photons are emitted from 150-220 MeV, while the hot QGP radiation dominants at higher p_T (~ 3 GeV/ c). The same “double-peak” structure is also seen for the thermal photons produced in the Pb+Pb collisions at LHC energy. The main difference is that the higher temperature peak sits at a higher mean value and has a broader width. This result is qualitatively consistent with the change of inverse slope around 2 GeV/ c observed in the measured excess photon spectrum for both Au+Au result and Pb+Pb result, see Fig. 5.12.

Figure 5.15: The differential photon yield, as a function of the temperature T , for different windows in the photon transverse momentum (different colored curves) for (a) Au + Au collisions at the RHIC and (b) Pb + Pb collisions at the LHC. Figure taken from [51].

Moreover, it is also consistent with a lower T_{eff} extracted in $p_T < 2$ GeV/ c of the spectra and higher T_{eff} extracted in $2 < p_T < 4$ GeV/ c . To put this statement in a more quantitative footing, the blue-shift of T_{eff} due to the radial expansion of the medium needs to be accounted for, which is evaluated in this calculation and shown on the right side of the true emission temperature profile in Fig. 5.14. In the earlier time ($< \sim 2$ fm/ c), the radial flow is not yet fully developed hence the T_{eff} is close to the true temperature T for photons emitted during this time. As the system expands faster towards later time, a shift towards higher effective temperature T_{eff} become more and more visible.

*About 70% of the total thermal photons are emitted after 2 fm/ c in this calculation.

For the photons radiated from 220 MeV to 150 MeV, the decrease of temperature and increase of blue-shift effect happen to balance each other and the corresponding T_{eff} collapses to a very narrow temperature range. Such effect is shown by the hot spot at $T_{\text{eff}} \approx 260$ MeV for Au+Au collisions in 0-20% centrality in panel (b) and the hot spot at $T_{\text{eff}} \approx 300$ MeV for Pb+Pb collisions in 0-40% in panel (d) of Fig. 5.14. The difference of T_{eff} for these later emissions at different collision energy is mainly due to the larger radial flow effect at higher collision energy.

This in fact ties back to the measured T_{eff} in the low p_T region very nicely (see Fig. 5.11). A more quantitative comparison between hydro prediction and experimental data is shown in Fig. 5.16. In [51], T_{eff} is extracted in a similar manner as the experimental data – an exponential fit in the low p_T range ($0.6 < p_T < 2.0$ GeV/c) for the calculated direct photon spectra in four centrality classes for Au+Au collisions. We perform a linear interpolation between adjacent $T_{\text{eff}}^{\text{hydro}}$ values; the result is shown as the red curve. The hydro model describes the data very well – both the central value and the centrality dependence – except for the most peripheral data (beyond 60% centrality). The weak increase of T_{eff} towards more central can be of a similar reason as the increase from lower to higher collision energy – a larger radial flow effect for system with higher energy density. The most peripheral data points are systematically higher than the model prediction. However, given the big uncertainties, it is not conclusive whether such a deviation is significant or not.

Figure 5.16: T_{eff} (fitting range 0.9-2.1 GeV/c) as a function of charged particle multiplicity at mid-rapidity. Left: T_{eff} is extracted in 0-20% to 60-93% centrality classes. Right: T_{eff} is extracted in 0-10% to 70-80% centrality classes.

For photons with higher p_T (> 2 GeV/c), the blue-shift effect is smaller hence the T_{eff} has a wider distribution but since the average T is higher at

LHC energy, we expect a higher T_{eff} from LHC result. In Fig. 5.13, we see the central value of T_{eff} is slightly higher at higher charged particle multiplicity, but the uncertainties do not allow us to further assess the overall trend. Although it is not clear what is the dominant photon source in the intermediate p_T range, if it is QGP radiation, the T_{eff} could reflect the true temperature of QGP because of the smaller blue-shift effect. The extracted T_{eff} is about 400 MeV, which falls into the theorized temperature range for QGP, but more differential diagnostics are needed to verify if the QGP radiation has the largest contribution in $2 < p_T < 4$ GeV/ c .

5.2.2 High p_T Direct Photon

From Fig. 5.4, one can see the direct photon yield above 5 GeV/ c is very consistent with the N_{coll} (number of binary collisions) scaled pp result and the pQCD calculation, giving strong evidence that the high p_T direct photons are dominated by the prompt photons produced in the hard scattering processes as described in Sec. 1.3.1. To show the comparison between the high p_T direct photon yield and the N_{coll} scaled direct photon yield from p+p collisions, we calculated the nuclear modification factor R_{AA} via Eq. 1.11 (see Sec. 1.3.1.3) for photons with $p_T > 4$ GeV/ c . Fig. 5.17 shows R_{AA} as a function of p_T from central to peripheral Au+Au collisions. We can see that the R_{AA} of high p_T direct photons is consistent with unity within uncertainties.

Figure 5.17: Nuclear modification factor of high p_T direct photons in Au+Au collisions in 0-20%, 20-40%, 40-60%, 60-93% centrality classes.

However, such an agreement is not completely trivial if we look more closely

at the components of prompt photon production. The prompt photons can be categorized into the following two classes:

- *Isolated photons:* Photons produced from quark-antiquark annihilation and quark-gluon inverse Compton scattering.
- *Fragmentation photons:* Photons produced from either fragmentation or Bremsstrahlung from quarks.

While isolated photons are expected to scale with the number of binary collisions, the fragmentation photon production is subject to medium effects, which should be absent in elementary pp collisions. As the partons traverse the dense colored medium created in heavy ion collisions, they strongly interact with the medium and experience energy loss. If a fragmentation photon is produced after the quark loses part of its energy, the momentum of the photon should be smaller compare to the case without energy loss. As a result, part of the high p_T fragmentation photons will migrate to the lower p_T side, which means one would observe a suppressed yield of photons at high p_T . The effect on the total prompt photon production depends on the proportion of the fragmentation contribution. As shown in Fig. 5.18, fragmentation photon production is a smaller contribution ($\sim 20\%$) in the very high p_T region (> 10 GeV/c), but increases towards lower p_T and overtakes the isolated photon production below 4 GeV/c.

Figure 5.18: Fraction of fragmentation photons and isolated photons in a pQCD calculation.

The energy loss effect alone could lead to a maximum 20-40% suppression of the prompt photons in Au+Au collisions at the RHIC energy, according to [141]. However, no significant suppression of high p_T direct photons is observed either in this work or the previous high p_T direct photon measurements.

One explanation for this is the induced photon emissions due to the parton-medium interactions. It is predicted that when an energetic quark scatters around the dense medium, more Bremsstrahlung photons will be produced, which is often referred to as *jet-Bremsstrahlung photons* [142]. Another possible source described in [143] is a fast parton interacting with the thermal bath and converting all its energy into a photon along its original direction, which is often referred to as a *jet-conversion photon*. These two effects will enhance the photon yield around and above 5 GeV/c. Such enhancement balances the suppression due to the parton energy loss, and hence we see no (or a small) modification from the medium at high p_T .

To study more closely if there is any (small) modification due to the QGP medium, we compare the R_{AA} result of high p_T direct photons in the most central Au+Au collisions (i.e. 0-10% and 10-20%) to several theoretical models, as shown in Fig. 5.19. The isospin effect accounts for the difference between the photon production cross section in proton-proton, proton-neutron and neutron-neutron scattering. The cross section of hard scattering processes is related to the parton distribution function (PDF) of the participating partons inside the nucleons (see Sec. 1.3.1.1). Experimental evidence shows that the PDF is different when the parton is inside a nucleus, which is often referred to as a nuclear-PDF (nPDF). The nPDF effect can also modify the hard scattering photon production cross section in nucleus-nucleus collisions as compared to proton-proton collisions. Here we compare our data to the “EPS09 PDF” calculation [144], which also includes the isospin effect.

Both isospin and nPDF effects happen at the initial stage of heavy ion collisions, and hence they are usually called the initial state (IS) effects. On the contrary, the effects due to the formation of QGP are usually called the final state (FS) effects. Two calculations are shown Fig. 5.19: “prompt + QGP” [15, 145] calculates the energy loss effect on the fragmentation photons and the enhancement of photon radiation due to jet-plasma interactions in the hydrodynamics framework; “coherent + conversion + ΔE ” [146] takes into consideration the energy loss effect, jet-conversion photons and medium induced jet-Bremsstrahlung with the Landau-Pomeranchuk-Migdal effect. Both calculations include the IS effects. The FS effects are limited to $\sim 30\%$ in $2 < p_T < 5$ GeV/c. With the current accuracy, our data can not exclude any of the compared models; however it slightly favors the models with FS effects included.

5.2.3 Centrality Dependence

Now that we have looked at direct photon production as a function of photon p_T , another differential analysis which can help us gain more information on

Figure 5.19: Nuclear modification factor of high p_T direct photons for the most central Au+Au collisions (0-10% in the top panel and 0-20% in the bottom panel).

the origin of the low p_T photons is the centrality dependence. As discussed in Sec. 1.4.4, the direct photon multiplicity shows a power law scaling with the charged particle multiplicity at mid-rapidity:

$$\frac{dN_\gamma}{dy} = A \times \left(\left. \frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta} \right|_{\eta \approx 0} \right)^\alpha \quad (5.4)$$

where $\frac{dN_\gamma}{dy}$ is the integrated direct photon yield over a certain p_T range and can be calculated using:

$$\frac{dN_\gamma}{dy} = 2\pi \int_{p_T^{\min}}^{p_T^{\max}} dp_T p_T \left(\frac{1}{2\pi p_T} \frac{d^2 N}{dp_T dy} \right) \quad (5.5)$$

We integrate the direct photon yield over a broad p_T range and plot it against the charged particle multiplicity, which increases monotonically towards central collisions. We use the finer centrality bins so that we have more points to do the fit using Eq. 5.4. The results are shown in Fig. 5.20. For photons with $p_T < 5$ GeV/c, the extracted slope α is ~ 1.1 . For photons with $p_T > 5$ GeV/c, the extracted slope α is consistent with 1.25. The previously reported slope (central value) in [54] and [52] is slightly higher, but taking into consideration the uncertainties on the slope, the previous and new results are consistent with each other, as can be seen when we overlay the results in Fig. 5.20.

The high p_T photons (5-10 GeV/c) scale with $\alpha = 1.29^{+0.08}_{-0.08}(\text{stat})^{+0.13}_{-0.09}(\text{sys})$, which is consistent with N_{coll} scaling that has been observed to follow $N_{coll} \propto N_{ch}^{1.25}$, as shown in Fig. 5.21. This N_{coll} scaling behavior confirms that the majority of the high p_T photons originate from hard scattering processes and also serves as a validation of using the N_{coll} scaled pp to estimate the prompt photon contribution in Au+Au collisions.

The scaling behavior of the low p_T photons (< 5 GeV/c) somehow resembles that of the high p_T direct photons, with slightly smaller scaling power $\alpha = 1.10^{+0.02}_{-0.02}(\text{stat})^{+0.11}_{-0.08}(\text{sys})$. To study the scaling power α of photons yield from different p_T regions systematically, we extract α for several non-overlapping p_T ranges. The result is shown in Fig. 5.22. With the current uncertainties, we do not observe a strong p_T dependence for α .

We compared the direct yield as a function of centrality with the hydro model. In the model, the yield of thermal photons from the hadron gas scale as a function of $dN_{ch}/d\eta$ with a power of 1.23, while the QGP thermal photon yield shows a significantly stronger dependence on $dN_{ch}/d\eta$ with a power of 1.83. In the model, the relative contribution of photons from the QGP com-

Figure 5.20: Integrated direct photon yield versus charged particle multiplicity at mid-rapidity for different p_T integration ranges.

Figure 5.21: Number of binary collisions N_{coll} as a function of charged particle multiplicity for different collision systems and beam energies. Dashed lines represent a simultaneous fit on all the data points using the functional form shown on the figure. $\alpha = 1.25 \pm 0.02$ is the extracted slope from the fitting procedure.

Figure 5.22: Extracted scaling factor α for different p_T integration ranges. The width of the uncertainty box around each p_T point indicates the width of p_T bin.

pared to those from the hadron gas increases with p_T . Thus the scaling power α demonstrates a modest increasing trend towards the higher p_T integration ranges, as shown in Fig. 5.23.

Figure 5.23: The centrality dependence of low p_T direct photon multiplicity in Au+Au collisions at 200 GeV predicted from the hydrodynamics model. (a) as a function of N_{part} (b) as a function of $dN_{\text{ch}}/d\eta$. Figure taken from [51].

However, this trend is not observed in the data, and the extracted α from the data is systematically lower than the hydro prediction, as shown in Fig. 5.22. To view the discrepancy more clearly, a direct comparison of the direct photon yield as a function of centrality and the hydro predicted slope is made in Fig. 5.24.

Figure 5.24: Integrated direct photon yield versus charged particle multiplicity at mid-rapidity for different p_T integration ranges.

5.2.4 Revisiting the Direct Photon Puzzle

Having compared our results with several of state of the art theoretical models. We find that none of the current calculations can describe all experimental observables simultaneously, but such a comparison can help us narrow down what the missing pieces in the current theoretical picture may be.

For the centrality dependence, the hydro model predicts a much larger α than the value extracted from experimental data. Combining this with the observation that the measured low p_T direct photon yield is higher than the theoretical calculation, this may indicate that there is an addition source of photons. This could be a higher photon emission rate and(or) that there is an enhancement of photon emission around the quark-hadron phase transition. The latter might also explain the large direct photon flow signal at low p_T .

We observed a transition in the p_T dependence of excess photons around $p_T \sim 2$ GeV/c. The T_{eff} is significantly higher (around 400 MeV) in the $2 < p_T < 4$ GeV/c range as compared to the $p_T < 2$ GeV/c range. As we discussed in Sec. 5.2.1.2, one possible explanation is that the thermal radiation from the QGP takes over in this p_T range. However, that should lead to a larger α for photons in the intermediate p_T range that is not observed in the data (see Fig. 5.25).

Figure 5.25: Extracted scaling factor α for different p_T integration ranges compared to the hadron gas scaling factor and QGP scaling factor calculated from the hydrodynamics model.

The discrepancy between the expected strong centrality dependence due to the QGP contribution and the observed $\alpha \sim 1.1$ in the intermediate p_T range could imply the following scenarios:

- The hadron gas over-shines all other sources up to $p_T \sim 5$ GeV/c.
- There are some other dominant photon emission sources with a similar centrality dependence as the hadron gas.
- The thermal radiation from the QGP is significant but mixed with photons from sources with a much smaller centrality dependence compared to the hadron gas.

Here we list a few novel photon sources that can potentially fulfill the above assumptions:

Parton-medium interactions Photons produced from parton-medium interactions are predicted to have a significant contribution for p_T in the range 3 to 4 GeV/c at the RHIC energy [14, 15], which is supported by the high p_T direct photon R_{AA} results. Currently this contribution is not well-implemented in the low p_T photon calculations and there is no prediction for the centrality dependence. These photons are theorized to have a negative flow signal.

K \emptyset MP \emptyset ST A recent model development shows that photons produced from the pre-equilibrium stage can play an important role at $p_T > \sim 2$ GeV/c. K \emptyset MP \emptyset ST [147, 148] provides a realistic model of the pre-equilibrium phase, based on which a quantitative calculation of the pre-equilibrium photon yield can be calculated, see Fig. 5.26. Pre-equilibrium photons exhibit a harder p_T spectrum and exceed the thermal contribution in the intermediate p_T range, This is consistent with the experimental data. However, the flow signal is predicted to be small since the pre-equilibrium photons are from the very early stage of the collision.

Bottom-up thermalization of the Glasma Another source of pre-equilibrium photons is radiation from the Glasma [16, 17], which is a conjectured transition state between the Color Glass Condensate (CGC) [150] and the thermalized QGP. Although there are still significant uncertainties in the computation of both the thermal and the Glasma photon rates, a recent calculation [18] (see Fig. 5.27) shows the Glasma photons dominant in the $2 < p_T < 3$ GeV/c range. The centrality dependence is claimed to be consistent with experimental data. There is no flow signal prediction yet.

Magnetic Field Effect The strong magnetic field present in the non-central heavy ion collisions is also believed to have some contribution in the intermediate p_T . Fig. 5.28 shows a comparison between data and a few existing calculations [19, 21] which include the photons produced from the initial magnetic

Figure 5.26: The yield (left) and elliptical flow v_2 (right) of photons from different sources in a hybrid hydrodynamics model. The pre-equilibrium photons are calculated from K ϕ MP ϕ ST. Figure taken from [149].

Figure 5.27: Comparison of the model with the yield from the $2 \leftrightarrow 2$ and collinearly enhanced rates, respectively, at $\sqrt{s} = 200 \text{ GeV}$, and $Q_s^2 = 1.67 \text{ GeV}^2$. Figure taken from [18].

field. This photon source is may have a negative α because the initial magnetic field increases toward more peripheral collisions, and thus more photons are produced in the peripheral collisions as compared to central collisions. A sizable flow signal is also predicted.

Figure 5.28: Yield and flow of photons estimated from models with initial strong magnetic field effects included. Figure taken from [24].

5.2.5 Conclusions

In this thesis, we presented a new measurement of low p_T direct photons in Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV using the 2014 dataset recorded by the PHENIX experiment. We analyzed a sample of photons that converts to electron-position pairs at the Silicon Vertex Track detector. A new tracking algorithm was developed to reconstruct and identify the conversion photons and distinguish them from background. Excellent purity and momentum resolution were achieved with the new algorithm. The increased luminosity in the 2014 Au+Au collisions combined with the larger number of conversions due to a higher material budget allowed this dataset to provide more than a 10-fold increase in statistics compared to the previous low p_T direct photon measurements.

We measured the direct photon invariant yield as a function of p_T in every 20% and every 10% centrality class. The new result serves as a fourth

independent measurement from PHENIX, and it is consistent with published results with significantly increased statistical precision and an extended p_T reach from 0.8 GeV/c up to 10 GeV/c.

We studied the excess photon yield above the prompt photon expectation and extracted the inverse slope (i.e. T_{eff}) of an exponential fit for $p_T < 2$ GeV/c. We found T_{eff} is about 260 MeV and shows a slight increase towards more central collisions, where the initial energy density is believed to be higher. The exponential function with a 260 MeV inverse slope can describe the excess yield very well below 2 GeV/c, however a clear deviation can be seen for $2 < p_T < 4$ GeV/c. Such a deviation may indicate a change of the dominant photon source(s) around 2 GeV/c. The shape of the deviation looks similar in different centrality classes and even at the LHC energy. The excess yield in this intermediate p_T range shows a significantly higher T_{eff} , about 400 MeV, but also no strong centrality dependence.

The centrality dependence of direct photon production is studied in detail with 10% centrality classes. We found that dN_γ/dy scales as $(dN_{ch}/d\eta)^\alpha$ with $\alpha \sim 1.1$ for photons of $p_T < 5$ GeV/c. α is extracted for photons in different p_T integration ranges and shows no significant increase or decrease towards higher p_T .

With the extended p_T reach almost up to almost 10 GeV/c, we also examined if there is any modification of the high p_T direct photon production in Au+Au collisions compared to the scaled p+p collisions by measuring the nuclear modification factor R_{AA} . R_{AA} is consistent with unity above 5 GeV/c, although there is a hint of enhancement for $5 < p_T < 7$ GeV/c and suppression for $7 < p_T < 10$ GeV/c in the very central Au+Au collisions.

None of the current theoretical models can describe all the mentioned experimental observations including the sizable flow signal for direct photons. Recently significant advancements have been made on the theory side – the existing emission rates haven been revisited and new sources have been proposed. Some of the new photon production sources, show promise to fill the pieces of the direct photon puzzle, but they need to be embedded into a more complete and realistic framework to compare with experimental data.

Appendices

Appendix A

Kinematics in Hadron-Hadron Scattering

We will now discuss how to relate the experimentally measured quantities – p_T , y_γ , and y_q – to the other quantities in Eq. 1.7 – x_1 , x_2 , Q^2 , \hat{s} , and θ^* .

First, we recall the definition of the rapidity for a particle:

$$y = \tanh^{-1} \beta_z = \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{1 + \beta_z}{1 - \beta_z} = \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{E + p_z}{E - p_z} \quad , \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where the z-axis is defined along one hadron beam directions. Under Lorentz boosts along the z-axis, the rapidity transforms as

$$y' = y - y_o \quad , \quad (\text{A.2})$$

with y' being the rapidity of the particle in the ‘prime’ frame and y_o being the rapidity of the ‘prime’ frame with respect to the original frame.

We can then relate the rapidity of a particle to its energy and momentum as [26]

$$E^2 = P^2 + M^2 = M_T^2 + P_z^2 = M_T^2 \cosh^2 y \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$M_T^2 = M^2 + p_T^2 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$P_z = M_T \sinh y \quad , \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where E , P , and M are the particle’s energy, momentum, and mass, respectively; and M_T is defined as the transverse mass.

If the scattering process $hadron_1 + hadron_2 \rightarrow X$ can be written on the parton level as $parton_1 + parton_2 \rightarrow parton_3 + parton_4$, then we can write the four-momentum vectors (E, P_x, P_y, P_z) in the hadron-hadron center-of-mass

frame as [151]

$$p_{had.1}^\mu = (E, 0, 0, +E) = \frac{\sqrt{s}}{2}(1, 0, 0, 1) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$p_{had.2}^\mu = (E, 0, 0, -E) = \frac{\sqrt{s}}{2}(1, 0, 0, -1) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$p_{part.1}^\mu = x_1(E, 0, 0, +E) = \frac{\sqrt{s}}{2}x_1(1, 0, 0, 1) \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$p_{part.2}^\mu = x_2(E, 0, 0, -E) = \frac{\sqrt{s}}{2}x_2(1, 0, 0, -1) \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$p_{part.3}^\mu = (p_T \cosh y_3, p_T \cos \phi, p_T \sin \phi, p_T \sinh y_3) \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$p_{part.4}^\mu = (p_T \cosh y_4, -p_T \cos \phi, -p_T \sin \phi, p_T \sinh y_4) \quad , \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where \sqrt{s} is the hadron-hadron center-of-mass energy, and $x_{1(2)}$ is the fraction of the hadron₁₍₂₎ momentum carried by parton₁₍₂₎. Note that we have ignored the masses of all particles in the four-momentum vectors above.

We can then write the parton-parton center-of-mass energy, $\sqrt{\hat{s}}$, as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{s} &= (p_{part.1}^\mu + p_{part.2}^\mu)^2 \\ &= E^2(x_1 + x_2, 0, 0, x_1 - x_2)^2 \\ &= 4x_1x_2E^2 \\ &= x_1x_2s \quad . \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Next, we need to define quantities in the parton-parton center-of-mass frame in terms of those in the hadron-hadron center-of-mass frame. The rapidities of the outgoing partons in the parton-parton center-of-mass frame, $y_{3(4)}^*$ can be written as

$$y_3^* = y^* = y_3 - \bar{y} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$y_4^* = -y^* = y_4 - \bar{y} \quad , \quad (\text{A.14})$$

where \bar{y} is the rapidity of the parton-parton center-of-mass frame relative to the hadron-hadron center-of-mass frame. We can immediately write

$$y^* = \frac{y_3 - y_4}{2} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

and

$$\bar{y} = \frac{y_3 + y_4}{2} \quad . \quad (\text{A.16})$$

This can also be written in terms of x_1 and x_2 as

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{E(x_1 + x_2 + x_1 - x_2)}{E(x_1 + x_2 - x_1 + x_2)} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{x_1}{x_2} \quad , \quad (\text{A.17})$$

using the definition of rapidity in Eq. A.1 and the parton 4-momenta defined in Eq. A.8 and Eq. A.9.

We can then write the transverse momentum (p_T^*) and energies ($E_{3(4)}^*$) of the outgoing partons in the parton-parton center-of-mass frame as

$$p_T^* = p_T = \frac{\sqrt{\hat{s}}}{2} \sin \theta^* \quad (\text{A.18})$$

$$E_{3,4}^* = \frac{\sqrt{\hat{s}}}{2} \quad , \quad (\text{A.19})$$

where, as above, θ^* is the scattering angle of parton₃ relative to parton₁. Using Eq. A.15, we can calculate θ^* directly in terms of the experimentally measured rapidities:

$$\cos \theta^* = \frac{p_{z,3}^*}{E_3^*} = \frac{\sinh y^*}{\cosh y^*} = \tanh \left(\frac{y_3 - y_4}{2} \right) \quad . \quad (\text{A.20})$$

Next, using Eq. A.12 and Eq. A.17, we can write $x_{1(2)}$ as

$$x_{1,2} = \sqrt{\frac{\hat{s}}{s}} e^{\pm \bar{y}} \quad . \quad (\text{A.21})$$

So, we need to express \hat{s} in terms of p_T , y_3 and y_4 in order to express $x_{1(2)}$ in terms of the same quantities. This can be done as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{s} &= (p_{part.1}^\mu + p_{part.2}^\mu)^2 = (p_{part.3}^\mu + p_{part.4}^\mu)^2 = M_{12(34)}^2 \\ &= (E_3^* + E_4^*)^2 \\ &= (p_T \cosh y^* + p_T \cosh(-y^*))^2 \\ &= 4p_T^2 \cosh^2 y^* \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.22})$$

where $M_{12(34)}$ is the mass of the parton-parton system. Using this result, we

can express $x_{1(2)}$ as

$$\begin{aligned}
x_{1,2} &= \frac{2p_T}{\sqrt{s}} \cosh^2 y^* e^{\pm\bar{y}} \\
&= \frac{2p_T}{\sqrt{s}} \frac{e^{\pm y_3} + e^{\pm y_4}}{2} \\
&= x_T \frac{e^{\pm y_3} + e^{\pm y_4}}{2} \quad ,
\end{aligned} \tag{A.23}$$

where x_T is a scaling variable [27].

Lastly, we can use this result to calculate Q^2 by rewriting $p_{part.1}^\mu$ as

$$p_{part.1}^\mu = \frac{p_T}{2} (e^{y_3} + e^{y_4}) (1, 0, 0, 1) \quad , \tag{A.24}$$

and then calculating Q^2 , in the ‘‘t channel’’ for example, as [151]

$$\begin{aligned}
Q^2 &= - (p_{part.1}^\mu - p_{part.3}^\mu)^2 \\
&= 2p_{part.1}^\mu p_{part.3}^\mu \\
&= p_T^2 (e^{y_3} + e^{y_4}) (\cosh y_3 - \sinh y_3) \\
&= p_T^2 (e^{y_4 - y_3} + 1) \quad .
\end{aligned} \tag{A.25}$$

In the ‘‘s channel’’, $Q^2 = \hat{s}$; and in the ‘‘u channel’’, $Q^2 = p_T^2 (e^{y_3 - y_4} + 1)$.

Starting with Eq. 1.5, we can derive Eq. 1.7 as follows. We can write \hat{t} as

$$\hat{t} = -\frac{\hat{s}}{2} (1 - \cos \theta_{cm}) \quad , \tag{A.26}$$

and \hat{u} as

$$\hat{u} = -\frac{\hat{s}}{2} (1 + \cos \theta_{cm}) \quad , \tag{A.27}$$

where θ_{cm} is the angle of the outgoing photon with respect to the incoming gluon.

Next, we use the QCD factorization theorem to write the proton-proton cross section as the product of the parton-parton cross section (Eq. 1.5) and

the quark and gluon pdfs:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^3\sigma}{d\hat{t}dx_1dx_2} &= \sum_q -\frac{\pi\alpha_s\alpha_{em}}{3\hat{s}^2} \left(\frac{\hat{s}}{\hat{u}} + \frac{\hat{u}}{\hat{s}} \right) e_q^2 [g(x_1)q(x_2) + g(x_2)q(x_1)] \\
&= \frac{\pi\alpha_s\alpha_{em}}{3\hat{s}^2} \left(\frac{2}{1 + \cos\theta_{cm}} + \frac{1 + \cos\theta_{cm}}{2} \right) \times \\
&\quad \left[g(x_1) \frac{F_2(x_2)}{x_2} + g(x_2) \frac{F_2(x_1)}{x_1} \right] .
\end{aligned} \tag{A.28}$$

Then, using the Jacobian [151]

$$\frac{\partial(\hat{t}, x_1, x_2)}{\partial(p_t^2, y_\gamma, y_q)} = x_1x_2 \quad , \tag{A.29}$$

and the fact that $\theta_{cm} = \theta^*$ when the incoming gluon equals parton₁, but $\theta_{cm} = \pi - \theta^*$ when the incoming gluon equals parton₂, we can write the proton-proton cross section as

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^3\sigma}{dp_T^2 dy_\gamma dy_q} &= \frac{\pi\alpha_s\alpha_{em}}{3\hat{s}^2} x_1x_2 \left(\frac{2}{1 + \cos\theta_{cm}} + \frac{1 + \cos\theta_{cm}}{2} \right) \times \\
&\quad \left[g(x_1) \frac{F_2(x_2)}{x_2} + g(x_2) \frac{F_2(x_1)}{x_1} \right] \\
&= x_1g(x_1)F_2(x_2, Q^2) \frac{\pi\alpha_{em}(Q^2)\alpha_s(Q^2)}{3\hat{s}^2} \times \\
&\quad \left(\frac{1 + \cos\theta^*}{2} + \frac{2}{1 + \cos\theta^*} \right) \\
&\quad + x_2g(x_2)F_2(x_1, Q^2) \frac{\pi\alpha_{em}(Q^2)\alpha_s(Q^2)}{3\hat{s}^2} \times \\
&\quad \left(\frac{1 - \cos\theta^*}{2} + \frac{2}{1 - \cos\theta^*} \right) ,
\end{aligned} \tag{A.30}$$

which is equal to Eq. 1.7.

Bibliography

- [1] David Griffiths. *Introduction to Elementary Particles*. Wiley-VCH, second, revised edition, 2008.
- [2] R.M. Petti. *Low Momentum Direct Photons as a Probe of Heavy Ion Collisions*. PhD thesis, Stony Brook University, 2013.
- [3] M. Tanabashi *et al.* Review of particle physics. *Phys. Rev. D*, 98:030001, Aug 2018.
- [4] Edward V. Shuryak. Quantum Chromodynamics and the Theory of Superdense Matter. *Phys. Rept.*, 61:70–158, 1980.
- [5] F. Karsch. Lattice Results on QCD Thermodynamics. *Nucl. Phys.*, A698:199–208, 2002.
- [6] A. Bazavov *et al.* Equation of state in $(2 + 1)$ -flavor qcd. *Phys. Rev. D*, 90:094503, Nov 2014.
- [7] *Theory Provides Roadmap in Quest for Quark Soup 'Critical Point'*, 2017.
- [8] J. D. Bjorken. Highly relativistic nucleus-nucleus collisions: The central rapidity region. *Phys. Rev. D*, 27:140–151, Jan 1983.
- [9] Peter F. Kolb. Expansion Rates at RHIC. *Acta Physica Hungarica A) Heavy Ion Physics*, 21(2):243–248, 2004.
- [10] K. Adcox *et al.* Formation of dense partonic matter in relativistic nucleus nucleus collisions at RHIC: Experimental evaluation by the PHENIX Collaboration. *Nucl. Phys.*, A757:184–283, 2005.
- [11] J. Adams *et al.* Experimental and theoretical challenges in the search for the quark gluon plasma: The STAR Collaboration's critical assessment of the evidence from RHIC collisions. *Nucl. Phys.*, A757:102–183, 2005.

- [12] B.B. Back *et al.* The PHOBOS perspective on discoveries at RHIC. *Nucl. Phys.*, A757:28–101, 2005.
- [13] I. Arsene *et al.* Quark-gluon plasma and color glass condensate at RHIC? The perspective from the BRAHMS experiment. *Nucl. Phys.*, A757:1–27, 2005.
- [14] J. F. Owens. Large-momentum-transfer production of direct photons, jets, and particles. *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 59:465–503, Apr 1987.
- [15] Simon Turbide, Charles Gale, Evan Frodermann, and Ulrich Heinz. Electromagnetic radiation from nuclear collisions at ultrarelativistic energies. *Phys. Rev. C*, 77:024909, Feb 2008.
- [16] T. Lappi and L. McLerran. Some features of the glasma. *Nuclear Physics A*, 772(3):200 – 212, 2006.
- [17] Larry McLerran and Bjrn Schenke. The glasma, photons and the implications of anisotropy. *Nuclear Physics A*, 929:71 – 82, 2014.
- [18] Oscar Garcia-Montero. Non-equilibrium photons from the bottom-up thermalization scenario. *arXiv*, pages arXiv–1909, 2019.
- [19] Berndt Müller, Shang-Yu Wu, and Di-Lun Yang. Elliptic flow from thermal photons with magnetic field in holography. *Phys. Rev. D*, 89:026013, Jan 2014.
- [20] Kirill Tuchin. Electromagnetic radiation by quark-gluon plasma in a magnetic field. *Phys. Rev. C*, 87:024912, Feb 2013.
- [21] Gök çe Başar, Dmitri E. Kharzeev, and Vladimir Skokov. Conformal anomaly as a source of soft photons in heavy ion collisions. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 109:202303, Nov 2012.
- [22] Hendrik van Hees, Min He, and Ralf Rapp. Pseudo-critical enhancement of thermal photons in relativistic heavy-ion collisions? *Nuclear Physics A*, 933:256 – 271, 2015.
- [23] H. Fritzsche and P. Minkowski. Measuring QCD compton effects. *Physics Letters*, 69B(3):316–320, 1977.
- [24] Gabor David. Direct real photons in relativistic heavy ion collisions. *arXiv:1907.08893v1*, 2019.

- [25] Tadaaki Isobe. *Production of Direct Photons and Neutral Pions in Relativistic Au+Au Collisions*. PhD thesis, University of Tokyo, 2007.
- [26] M. (Particle Data Group) Tanabashi *et al.* Review of particle physics. *Physical Review D*, 98(030001), 2018.
- [27] A. Adare *et al.* Direct photon production in p + p collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV at midrapidity. *Physical Review D*, 86(072008), 2012.
- [28] R. J. Glauber. Cross sections in deuterium at high energies. *Phys. Rev.*, 100(242), 1955.
- [29] M. L. Miller *et al.* Glauber modeling in high-energy nuclear collisions. *Annu. Rev. Nucl. Part. Sci.*, 57:205–43, 2007.
- [30] Sergei A Voloshin, Arthur M Poskanzer, and Raimond Snellings. Collective phenomena in non-central nuclear collisions. In *Relativistic Heavy Ion Physics*, pages 293–333. Springer, 2010.
- [31] Rupa Chatterjee and Dinesh K. Srivastava. Elliptic flow of thermal photons and formation time of quark gluon plasma at energies available at the BNL Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC). *Phys. Rev. C*, 79:021901, Feb 2009.
- [32] Roy A. Lacey. Recent results of source function imaging from AGS through CERN SPS to RHIC. *Brazilian Journal of Physics*, 37:893 – 902, 09 2007.
- [33] Simon Turbide, Charles Gale, and Rainer J Fries. Azimuthal asymmetry of direct photons in high energy nuclear collisions. *Physical review letters*, 96(3):032303, 2006.
- [34] Marcus Bleicher, E Zabrodin, Christian Spieles, Steffen A Bass, Christoph Ernst, Sven Soff, L Bravina, Mohamed Belkacem, Henning Weber, and Horst *et al.* Stöcker. Relativistic hadron-hadron collisions in the ultra-relativistic quantum molecular dynamics model. *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics*, 25(9):1859, 1999.
- [35] SA Bass and A Dumitru. Dynamics of hot bulk QCD matter: From the quark-gluon plasma to hadronic freeze-out. *Physical Review C*, 61(6):064909, 2000.
- [36] Peter Arnold, Guy D Moore, and Laurence G Yaffe. Photon emission from quark-gluon plasma: complete leading order results. *Journal of High Energy Physics*, 2001(12):009, 2001.

- [37] Jean-François Paquet, Chun Shen, Gabriel S Denicol, Matthew Luzum, Björn Schenke, Sangyong Jeon, and Charles Gale. Production of photons in relativistic heavy-ion collisions. *Physical Review C*, 93(4):044906, 2016.
- [38] Hendrik van Hees, Charles Gale, and Ralf Rapp. Thermal photons and collective flow at energies available at the BNL Relativistic Heavy-Ion Collider. *Physical Review C*, 84(5):054906, 2011.
- [39] Simon Turbide, Ralf Rapp, and Charles Gale. Hadronic production of thermal photons. *Physical Review C*, 69(1):014903, 2004.
- [40] W Cassing and EL Bratkovskaya. Parton-Hadron-String Dynamics: an off-shell transport approach for relativistic energies. *arXiv preprint arXiv:0907.5331*, 2009.
- [41] Gordon Baym and Leo P Kadanoff. Conservation laws and correlation functions. *Physical Review*, 124(2):287, 1961.
- [42] Gordon Baym. Self-consistent approximations in many-body systems. *Physical review*, 127(4):1391, 1962.
- [43] Benoit Vanderheyden and Gordon Baym. Self-consistent approximations in relativistic plasmas: Quasiparticle analysis of the thermodynamic properties. *Journal of statistical physics*, 93(3-4):843–861, 1998.
- [44] W Cassing. Dynamical quasiparticles properties and effective interactions in the sQGP. *Nuclear Physics A*, 795(1-4):70–97, 2007.
- [45] Wolfgang Ehehalt and Wolfgang Cassing. Relativistic transport approach for nucleus-nucleus collisions from SIS to SPS energies. *Nuclear Physics A*, 602(3-4):449–486, 1996.
- [46] EL Bratkovskaya and W Cassing. Dilepton production from AGS to SPS energies within a relativistic transport approach. *Nuclear Physics A*, 619(3-4):413–446, 1997.
- [47] O Linnyk, V Konchakovski, T Steinert, W Cassing, and EL Bratkovskaya. Hadronic and partonic sources of direct photons in relativistic heavy-ion collisions. *Physical Review C*, 92(5):054914, 2015.
- [48] O Linnyk, W Cassing, and EL Bratkovskaya. Centrality dependence of the direct photon yield and elliptic flow in heavy-ion collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}}=200$ GeV. *Physical Review C*, 89(3):034908, 2014.

- [49] A. Adare *et al.* Azimuthally anisotropic emission of low-momentum direct photons in Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. *Phys. Rev. C*, 94:064901, Dec 2016.
- [50] E L Feinberg. Direct production of photons and dileptons in thermodynamical models of multiple hadron production. *Nuovo Cimento A*, 34 ser.2(3):391–412, 1976.
- [51] Chun Shen, Ulrich Heinz, Jean-Francois Paquet, and Charles Gale. Thermal photons as a quark-gluon plasma thermometer reexamined. *Physical Review C*, 89(4):044910, 2014.
- [52] A. Adare *et al.* Beam energy and centrality dependence of direct-photon emission from ultrarelativistic heavy-ion collisions. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 123:022301, Jul 2019.
- [53] A. Adare *et al.* Detailed measurement of the e^+e^- pair continuum in $p + p$ and Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV and implications for direct photon production. *Phys. Rev. C*, 81:034911, Mar 2010.
- [54] A. Adare *et al.* Centrality dependence of low-momentum direct-photon production in Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. *Phys. Rev. C*, 91:064904, Jun 2015.
- [55] A. Adare *et al.* Low-momentum direct-photon measurement in Cu + Cu collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. *Phys. Rev. C*, 98:054902, Nov 2018.
- [56] A. Adare *et al.* Direct photon production in d +Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. *Phys. Rev. C*, 87:054907, May 2013.
- [57] J. Adam *et al.* Direct photon production in PbPb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 2.76$ TeV. *Physics Letters B*, 754:235 – 248, 2016.
- [58] M. Harrison, T. Ludlam, and S. Ozaki. RHIC project overview. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A499:235–244, 2003.
- [59] X Gu, Z Altinbas, S Badea, D Bruno, L Cannizzo, M Costanzo, A Drees, AV Fedotov, W Fischer, and D *et al.* Gassner. Stable operation of a high-voltage high-current dc photoemission gun for the bunched beam electron cooler in RHIC. *Physical Review Accelerators and Beams*, 23(1):013401, 2020.
- [60] R Calaga, W Fischer, G Robert-Demolaize, and N Milas. Long-range beam-beam experiments in the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider. *Physical Review Special Topics-Accelerators and Beams*, 14(9):091001, 2011.

- [61] W. Herr and B. Muratori. Concept of luminosity. 2006.
- [62] S. VanderMeer. CERN-ISR-P0/68-31, unpublished. 1968.
- [63] A. Drees and X. Zhangbu. Results from Luminosity Scans during the RHIC 2000. In *Proc. of the 2001 Particle Accelerator Conference, Chicago IL*, 2001.
- [64] A. Drees, X. Zhangbu, B. Fox, and H. Huang. Results from Vernier Scans at RHIC During the pp run 2001-2002. In *Proceedings of the 2003 Particle Accelerator Conference*, volume 3, pages 1688–1690. IEEE, 2003.
- [65] M. Blaskiewicz, J. M. Brennan, and K. Mernick. Three-Dimensional Stochastic Cooling in the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 105:094801, Aug 2010.
- [66] Robert-Demolaize *et al.* RHIC performance for FY2014 heavy ion run. In *5th Int. Particle Accelerator Conf.(IPAC'14), Dresden, Germany, June 15-20, 2014*, pages 1090–1092. JACOW, Geneva, Switzerland, 2014.
- [67] A.V. Bazilevsky. *PHENIX Data sets 2009-2016 (Run9-16)*.
- [68] *Run Overview of the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider*.
- [69] M. Adamczyk *et al.* The BRAHMS experiment at RHIC. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A499:437–468, 2003.
- [70] B.B. Back *et al.* The PHOBOS detector at RHIC. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A499:603–623, 2003.
- [71] K. Adcox *et al.* PHENIX detector overview. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A499:469–479, 2003.
- [72] K.H. Ackerman *et al.* STAR detector overview. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A499:624–632, 2003.
- [73] A. Adare, S. Afanasiev, C. Aidala, NN. Ajitanand, Y. Akiba, R. Akimoto, J. Alexander, K. Aoki, N. Apadula, and H. *et al.* Asano. An upgrade proposal from the PHENIX collaboration. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1501.06197*, 2015.
- [74] Chi Yang. The star beam energy scan phase ii physics and upgrades. *Nuclear Physics A*, 967:800 – 803, 2017. The 26th International Conference on Ultra-relativistic Nucleus-Nucleus Collisions: Quark Matter 2017.

- [75] A. Accardi, JL. Albacete, M. Anselmino, N. Armesto, EC. Aschenauer, A. Bacchetta, D. Boer, WK. Brooks, T. Burton, and N-B *et al.* Chang. Electron-ion collider: The next QCD frontier. *The European Physical Journal A*, 52(9):268, 2016.
- [76] H. Akikawa *et al.* PHENIX Muon Arms. *Nucl. Instr. and Methods*, A499:537–548, 2003.
- [77] M. Allen *et al.* PHENIX inner detectors. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A499:549–559, 2003.
- [78] K. Ikematsu *et al.* A start-timing detector for the collider experiment PHENIX at RHIC-BNL. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A411:238–559, 1998.
- [79] J.T. Mitchell *et al.* Event reconstruction in the PHENIX central arm spectrometers. *Nucl. Instr. and Methods*, A482:491–512, 2002.
- [80] T. Ludlam. Overview of experiments and detectors at rhic. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A499:428–432, 2003.
- [81] C. Adler. The RHIC zero degree calorimeters. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A470:488–499, 2001.
- [82] Gary J Russell. Spallation physics-an overview. *Proc. ICANS-XI, Tsukuba*, pages 90–25, 1990.
- [83] JP de Brion. Comparative Study of Aging of PMMA and PS Optical Fibers. *CEN, Saclay Report, DPHPE*, pages 86–07, 1986.
- [84] M. Csanad. Online monitoring system for the phenix ZDC and SMD. PHENIX internal technical note 419, 2006.
- [85] A. Bazilevsky. Explanation of PHENIX triggers, 2020.
- [86] Hijing event generator. <http://www-nsdth.lbl.gov/xnwang/hijing>.
- [87] S.H. Aronson *et al.* PHENIX magnet system. *Nucl. Instr. and Methods*, A499:480–488, 2003.
- [88] Yuriy Riabov. Low-mass Drift Chambers of the PHENIX central spectrometers at RHIC. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 494(1):194 – 198, 2002. Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Instrumentation for Colliding Beam Physics.

- [89] K. Adcox *et al.* Construction and performance of the PHENIX pad chambers. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A497:263–293, 2003.
- [90] K. Adcox *et al.* PHENIX central arm tracking detectors. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A499:489–507, 2003.
- [91] S. C. Johnson. Three dimensional track finding in the phenix drift chamber by a combinatorial hough transform method. In *Proc. of Intl. Conf. on Computing in High Energy Physics (CHEP 98)*, Chicago IL, 1998.
- [92] A. Chikanian *et al.* A momentum reconstruction algorithm for the PHENIX spectrometer at Brookhaven. *Nucl. Instr. and Methods*, A371:480–488, 1996.
- [93] L. Aphecetche *et al.* PHENIX calorimeter. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A499:521–536, 2003.
- [94] J. Badier, P. Busson, C. Chariot, L. Dobrzynski, and R. *et al.* Tanaka. Shashlik calorimeter: Beam test results. *Nucl. Instrum. Meth.*, A348:74–86, 1994.
- [95] H. Fessler *et al.* A tower structured scintillator-lead photon calorimeter using a novel fiber optics readout system. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A228:303–308, 1985.
- [96] S. Neumaier and J. Urbahn. WA98 - Large acceptance photon and hadron spectrometry of 160-A/GeV Pb Pb collisions at CERN SPS. 1995.
- [97] T. Peitzmann *et al.* A new monitoring system for the photon spectrometer LEDA in the WA98 experiment. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 376(3):368 – 374, 1996.
- [98] T.C. Awes, A. Bazilevsky, S. Bathe, D. Bucher, and H. *et al.* Buesching. High-energy beam test of the PHENIX lead scintillator EM calorimeter. *Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A*, 2002.
- [99] G. David, Y. Goto, E. Kistenev, S. Stoll, and S. *et al.* White. The PHENIX lead-scintillator electromagnetic calorimeter: Test beam and construction experience. *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, 45:692–697, 1998.
- [100] G. David, E. Kistenev, S. White, C. Woody, A. Bazilevsky, S. Belikov, V. Kochetkov, V. Onuchin, and A. Usachev. Pattern recognition in

- the PHENIX PbSc electromagnetic calorimeter. *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, 47(6):1982–1986, 2000.
- [101] N. Novitzky. *Study of the Neutral Pion and Direct Photon Production in Au+Au Collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 39 - 200$ GeV*. PhD thesis, University of Jyväskylä, 2012.
- [102] A.V. Bazilevsky, A.A. Durum, E.P. Kistenev, V.I. Kochetkov, V.K. Semenov, and S. White. Position Measurement of Electrons and γ -Quanta in the PHENIX Electromagnetic Calorimeter. *Instrum.Exp.Tech.*, 41:792–796, 1998.
- [103] T.C. Awes, F.E. Obenshain, F. Plasil, S. Saini, and S.P. *et al.* Sorensen. A Simple method of shower localization and identification in laterally segmented calorimeters. *Nucl.Instrum.Meth.*, A311:130–138, 1992.
- [104] A.V. Bazilevsky, V.I. Kochetkov, V.K. Semenov, S. White, and E.P. Kistenev. Electron/hadron separation in the electromagnetic calorimeter of the PHENIX setup. *Instrum.Exp.Tech.*, 42:167–173, 1999.
- [105] M. Aizawa *et al.* PHENIX central arm particle ID detectors. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 499(2):508 – 520, 2003. The Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider Project: RHIC and its Detectors.
- [106] Y. Akiba *et al.* Ring imaging cherenkov detector of PHENIX experiment at RHIC. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A453:279–283, 2000.
- [107] T. Sakaguchi *et al.* Development of front end electronics for PHENIX RHIC. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A453:382–385, 2000.
- [108] T. Sakaguchi. Introduction to PHENIX RICH detector, 2019.
- [109] Alan Dion. *Energy Loss and Flow of Heavy Quarks in Au+Au Collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV*. PhD thesis, Stony Brook University, 2007.
- [110] S.S. Adler *et al.* Phenix on-line and off-line computing. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 499(2):593 – 602, 2003. The Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider Project: RHIC and its Detectors.
- [111] GEANT. manual, v.3.2.1, CERN program library W5013, 1994.
- [112] Pythia event generator. <http://home.thep.lu.se/torbjorn/Pythia>.

- [113] S. Afanasiev *et al.* Measurement of Direct Photons in Au+Au Collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 109:152302, 2012.
- [114] A. Adare *et al.* Detailed measurement of the $e^+ + e^-$ pair continuum in p+p and Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV and implications for direct photon production. *Phys. Rev.*, C81:034911, 2010.
- [115] W. Anderson *et al.* Design, construction, operation and performance of a hadron blind detector for the phenix experiment. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 646(1):35 – 58, 2011.
- [116] Benjamin Banner. *Systematic studies of soft direct photon production in Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV.* PhD thesis, Stony Brook University, 2014.
- [117] Y. Akiba. Proposal for a silicon vertex tracker (VTX) for the PHENIX experiment. Technical report, BROOKHAVEN NATIONAL LABORATORY (United States). Funding organisation: DOE , 2004.
- [118] A. Taketani *et al.* Silicon vertex tracker for RHIC PHENIX experiment. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 623(1):374 – 376, 2010. 1st International Conference on Technology and Instrumentation in Particle Physics.
- [119] W. Snoeys *et al.* Pixel readout chips in deep submicron CMOS for ALICE and LHCb tolerant to 10Mrad and beyond. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 466(2):366 – 375, 2001. 4th Int. Symp. on Development and Application of Semiconductor Tracking Detectors.
- [120] Z. Li. Novel silicon stripixel detector: concept, simulation, design, and fabrication. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 518(3):738 – 753, 2004.
- [121] W. Fan *et al.* Track reconstruction of external photon conversions. PHENIX internal technical note 481, 2006.
- [122] D. Sharma. *ω and ϕ meson production in p+p and d+Au collisions at RHIC energies, using the PHENIX Detector.* PhD thesis, Weizmann Institute of Science, 2010.

- [123] S. S. Adler *et al.* Identified charged particle spectra and yields in Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. *Phys. Rev. C*, 69:034909, Mar 2004.
- [124] S. S. Adler *et al.* Detailed study of high- p_T neutral pion suppression and azimuthal anisotropy in Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. *Phys. Rev. C*, 76:034904, Sep 2007.
- [125] R. Hagedorn. Statistical thermodynamics of strong interactions at high energies. *Nuovo Cimento, Suppl.*, 3(CERN-TH-520):147–186, 1965.
- [126] D. Drijard, H. G. Fischer, and T. Nakada. Study of event mixing and its application to the extraction of resonance signals. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A225:367, 1984.
- [127] D. L'Hote. About resonance signal extraction from multiparticle data: combinatorics and event mixing methods. *Nucl. Instr. and Meth.*, A337:544–556, 1994.
- [128] A. Toia, T. Dahms, A. Drees, and A. Hemmick. Combinatorial Background: Event Mixing and Normalization. PHENIX Internal Analysis Note, 2006.
- [129] J. Nagle. *PHENIX Run-14 Au+Au 200 GeV Centrality Categorization*.
- [130] T. Todoroki. *Timing calibration for 200GeV Au+Au run (Run14)*.
- [131] Yunajie Ren. System size, energy, and centrality dependence of the η to π^0 ratio. Master's thesis, Stony Brook University, 2020.
- [132] S. Acharya *et al.* Neutral pion and η meson production at midrapidity in Pb-Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 2.76$ TeV. *Phys. Rev. C*, 98:044901, Oct 2018.
- [133] Mike Sas. Light Neutral Meson Production in the Era of Precision Physics at the LHC. the XXVIIIth International Conference on Ultra-relativistic Nucleus-Nucleus Collisions, 2019.
- [134] V. Ryabov. Hadronic Decays of Light Mesons Measured by the PHENIX experiment at RHIC. *Nuclear Physics A*, 827(1):395c – 397c, 2009. PANIC08.
- [135] R. Averbek. An electron cocktail for Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. PHENIX internal analysis note 349, 2005.

- [136] A. Adare *et al.* Measurement of neutral mesons in $p + p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV and scaling properties of hadron production. *Phys. Rev. D*, 83:052004, Mar 2011.
- [137] A. Adare *et al.* Production of ω mesons in $p + p$, $d + Au$, $Cu + Cu$, and $Au + Au$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. *Phys. Rev. C*, 84:044902, Oct 2011.
- [138] W. Fan *et al.* Run14 AuAu EMCAL Geometry Tuning. PHENIX internal analysis note 1409, 2019.
- [139] A. Adare *et al.* Enhanced production of direct photons in $Au + Au$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV and implications for the initial temperature. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 104:132301, Mar 2010.
- [140] A. Adare *et al.* Observation of Direct-Photon Collective Flow in $Au + Au$ Collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 109:122302, Sep 2012.
- [141] Sangyong Jeon, Jamail Jalilian-Marian, and Ina Sarcevic. The origin of large-pt π^0 suppression at rhic. *Physics Letters B*, 562(1-2):45–50, 2003.
- [142] Boris Georgievich Zakharov. Induced photon emission from quark jets in ultrarelativistic heavy-ion collisions. *Journal of Experimental and Theoretical Physics Letters*, 80(1):1–6, 2004.
- [143] Rainer J Fries, Berndt Müller, and Dinesh K Srivastava. High-energy photons from passage of jets through quark-gluon plasma. *Physical review letters*, 90(13):132301, 2003.
- [144] Francois Arleo, Kari J Eskola, Hannu Paukkunen, and Carlos A Salgado. Inclusive prompt photon production in nuclear collisions at rhic and lhc. *Journal of High Energy Physics*, 2011(4):55, 2011.
- [145] C Gale. Selective tracer signals of the qcd plasma state, edited by r. stock, 2010.
- [146] Ivan Vitev and Ben-Wei Zhang. A systematic study of direct photon production in heavy ion collisions. *Physics Letters B*, 669(5):337–344, 2008.
- [147] Aleksi Kurkela, Aleksas Mazeliauskas, Jean-François Paquet, Sören Schlichting, and Derek Teaney. Effective kinetic description of event-by-event pre-equilibrium dynamics in high-energy heavy-ion collisions. *Physical Review C*, 99(3):034910, 2019.

- [148] Charles Gale, Jean-François Paquet, Björn Schenke, and Chun Shen. Illuminating the early stages of relativistic heavy- ion collisions with photons and hadrons. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2002.05191*, 2020.
- [149] Jean-François. Probing early-time dynamics and quark-gluon plasma transport properties with photons and hadrons. 10th edition of the Hard and Electromagnetic Probes International Conference, 2020.
- [150] Larry McLerran and Raju Venugopalan. Computing quark and gluon distribution functions for very large nuclei. *Physical Review D*, 49(5):2233, 1994.
- [151] Mark Thomson. *Modern Particle Physics*. Cambridge University Press, 2013.